

**Women in Educational Leadership: Empowerment and
Challenges in Higher Education of Nepal**

**Thesis submitted for the Degree of Doctor of Business
Administration (DBA)**

By

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Declaration

I, hereby, declare that the dissertation entitled "**Women in Educational Leadership: Empowerment and Challenges in Higher Education of Nepal**" submitted to The University of the West of Scotland as the part of Doctor in Business Administration (DBA) degree is my own work.

In course of accomplishing the research, some literatures have been reviewed but they are clearly referenced.

I am very much conscious about university's plagiarism policies. Finally, I would like to certify that this is my original work and there is no plagiarism.

Date: 25/09/2019

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In course of accomplishing this work, I have got considerable support from different people and organizations to whom I would like to recall here.

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Abstract

This research explores existing empowerment practices and challenges of women leadership in Nepal. Four key objectives have been developed: to find out about women's experiences as leader in HE institutions; to investigate women's perceptions of gender equality in educational leadership; to critically evaluate the main factors/barriers that prevent women from taking leadership roles; and to offer recommendations to increase women's participation in leadership positions.

This research adopts Interpretivism epistemology, subjective ontology, inductive reasoning and qualitative research methods. Similarly, data is collected from 20 women leaders currently working in higher education institutes in Nepal and analysed using a thematic analysing with the help of NVivo software. The participants were selected using non-probability purposive sampling technique. 16 pre-planned questions followed by probing questions as necessary were asked to every interviewee to obtain in-depth information on the subject. All the participants were interviewed face to face using semi-structure format to get in-depth data for the research.

The study found that women had not any dreams to be a leader and had not achieved the leadership position as a result of a well-planned career trajectory and had largely achieved their positions by chance. According to most of the interviewees, the women perceived that their male colleagues were jealous and found it uncomfortable in working under female leadership. The female respondents have more home responsibilities and explain that it made them more difficult to fulfil their leadership roles. They felt that Nepalese society does not believe in women leadership and that women have to prove their ability in practice to gain acceptance. Similarly, there was a lack of role model for women to follow and due to burden of domestic

responsibilities women were finding less time for training, studying and building informal network with others co-female leaders.

Various organizations continuously working to increase social awareness, gender equality and to give women more opportunities but these efforts are inadequate to increase the number of women in higher education leadership positions in Nepal. The culture has been perpetually changing and women are being much more aware of their rights compared to the past but the shadow of patriarchal culture has not been completely eradicated yet. To resolve this problem more social awareness programmes and women education should be focused on.

Despite some limitations this study has managed to give some useful contributions to knowledge and practice. Very few research has been published in women leadership in the context of Nepal and it is obvious that still many studies needed on societal issues before addressing leadership effectively. In practice, various stake holders such as women, society, organisation and government can reference the findings and make changes to improve the situations of women leadership in Higher Education

Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter tenders a short introduction that clarifies the background and rationale for the research.

1.1. Research Background

Leadership is an ability to lead others and achieve the shared objectives through teamwork (Zegbdirferm, 2013). This research explores women leadership in the higher education (HE) sector in the context of Nepal.

Nepal has Male dominated patriarchal society where most of the decisions are made by males and perceived to be superior to females whose key roles are focussed on decision making within the household and in organization activities (Subedi and Gaulee,2023; Dahal, Topping and Levy,2021). This culture has suppressed Nepalese women and has made it difficult for them to gain leadership positions. Based on National Education Commission 1992 report only 23.34 % girls were enrolled in higher educational institutions in Nepal and that significantly increased over time. According to UGC report (2018/19), Girls' enrolment to higher education for 2011/2012 was 46% and it jumped further to 52% (more than boys) in 2018/2019 (Acharya,2021). Despite positive outlook of women enrolment in higher education programmes women representation in leadership positions remains low with males dominating the leadership structures in most organisations (Subedi and Gaulee, 2023). This research will identify the reasons behind this low representation and will recommend effective solutions.

Despite increasing numbers of women participation in workforce and an enrolment in higher education programme still few numbers of women hold top leadership positions (Alqahtani,

2020). The representation of women in leading position can differ from one country to another due to several factors including culture, tradition, education, and politics (Veur, Ohana and Titley, 2007). In the case of developing countries like Nepal, government, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and international non-government organizations (INGOs) are working together to empower and uplift women; so that, this inequality can be changed.

In Nepal, after the restoration of democracy in 1990, significant improvements have been brought by the government and women now have a quota in every sector including politics and government employment (Sharma and Tamang, 2016). This has resulted in more women taking leadership position and key positions of power, for example, previous head of state was female (Mrs. Bidha Devi Bhandari), and there had been times when there had been three females in key leadership positions of the state (head of state, head of judiciary body and head of the legislative body) at the same time (Sharma and Tamang, 2016). However, these few cases do not represent the overall women leadership situation of Nepal. The patriarchal social perception persists and women still focus more on household activities and many are not interested in achieving leadership positions. According to Bindu (2015), there is minimal female representation in political and administrative decision-making positions and in every sector including education institutions, most of the higher-level positions are held by males. Equal participation has not been seen because patriarchal social perception has not changed and many people in society believe that women cannot be leaders and that they are subordinate to males (Morley, 2015). Morley (2015) adds that although this perception has been gradually changing, the patriarchal culture has not been completely erased from social beliefs, norms, and values.

This research will explore what obstacles there are to empowering women for equal participation in leadership positions, how women perceive their leadership experience and the key challenges that they have faced.

1.2. Research Contribution

The higher education sector has the potential to contribute to the development of women's careers by changing social structures and perceptions related to the traditional status of women (Veur, Ohana and Titley, 2007). This research evaluates the experience of women in leadership positions in HE and explores their challenges in Nepal.

There are several past studies - including Mary Jackson's (2010) "Empowering Women of Nepal" and Governance Facility's (2017) "Status of Women and Youth Leadership in Nepal" - on women and leadership in the context of Nepal but no research can be found that particularly focused on women leadership in the HE sector. This research will contribute to understanding why women are under-representation in leadership positions and that knowledge will increase female participation in HE leadership positions. The Nepalese government and other countries that have a similar history and culture, and the NGOs and INGOs will also be benefited from the findings of this research. It significantly will, therefore, assist in the development of effective strategies for the career development of women in Nepal.

1.3. Research Aims, Objectives and Questions

1.3.1. Aims

The research aims to identify women leadership experiences (getting into and leading) in higher education institutes in Nepal.

1.3.2. Objectives

Based on the research aim, the following objectives are set:

- To explore women's experiences about leadership positions in HE in Nepal

- To interpret women's perceptions of gender equality in HE
- To identify any major factors/barriers that prevent women from taking leadership roles
- To recommend solutions to the increase in the number of women in leadership in HE institutions

1.3.3. Questions

RQ1. What are the women's experiences about leadership positions in HE in Nepal?

RQ2. What are the women's perceptions of gender equality in HE leadership?

RQ3. What are the main factors/barriers that prevent women from taking leadership roles?

RQ4. What can be done to increase women leadership in HE?

1.4. Research Structure

This research has been divided into six major chapters which are as follows:

Chapter 1: Introduction - This chapter has established the background to women in leadership and the challenges faced in the context of Nepal and clarifies the significance of the research issue.

Chapter 2: Literature Review - This chapter critically reviews facts, theories, and models related to women leadership in the context of Nepal. It includes facts presented by renowned scholars on the subject matter. This chapter is divided into different sections and sub-sections such as definitions of leadership, leadership -born or made, leadership theories, gender, women education, women empowerment and many more.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology - A research framework guides the entire study so that research objectives can be reliably and systematically explored. This chapter is divided into several sections and sub-sections such as research philosophy (Ontological and epistemological stance), research approach, research choice, time horizon, data collection, sampling and some ethical issues related to the research.

Chapter 4: Data Presentation and Analysis - This chapter systematically presents the collected qualitative information and analyses them. Based on NVivo data analysis software, the key themes are identified, and the information is categorized with regard to these. This chapter is divided into different sections and sub-sections including experiences of women leadership, achieving leadership positions, males' perception over female leadership, and patriarchal culture.

Chapter 5: Discussion - This chapter discusses the collected qualitative information using relevant literature of the second chapter. Every claim is discussed from different perspectives and supported by data. It makes the information meaningful and helps to derive a reliable conclusion. This chapter is also divided into different sections and sub-sections such as women experience in HE leadership in Nepal, gender discrimination, and leadership, women abilities and opportunities.

Chapter 6: Conclusion, Recommendations and Future research - The final chapter concludes the entire research findings and offers practical and theoretical implications and recommendations to the relevant authorities so that gender discrimination and increased participation of females in leadership can be achieved. Further, it provides a clear direction for future research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

This chapter reviews significant theoretical models and interpretations relating to the research. Women leadership, empowerment and key challenges in the higher education sector in Nepal are key issues to be critically reviewed but these issues are further divided into several titles and sub-titles as required.

2.2. Leadership

2.2.1. Definition of Leadership

The term leadership has been used differently in diverse situations and it is consequently difficult to find a single definition. According to Barman (2009) "leadership is the process of social influence in which one person can enlist the aid and support of others in the accomplishment of a common task" (P.63). This definition implies that it is an activity in which one person takes key initiatives to fulfil common goals. But influencing or persuading others and getting the job done can be a very complex role.

Seitchik (2014) defines leadership as the act of inspiring others for shared effort, shared vision and shared achievement. It indicates that leadership is about persuading the followers about the shared activities and processes to fulfil the shared objectives. Here, the inspiring capacity, shared activities and shared objectives are the cruxes that determine leadership.

Blair (2010) says, "Leadership is harnessing the energy and efforts of a group of individuals" to reach the common destination (P.79). The leader has to get the confidence of others so that

they can gain trust and support in transferring a vision into reality. This definition focuses on the ability to explore optimum potentiality and the right guidance to reach common destinations.

Leadership is the ability to be followed by others or the ability to direct others in a particular direction (Obasanjo, 2014). Without being followed by others, no one can be a leader. According to Barman (2009), it can be the capacity by which other people can trust and show their commitment. It means to say that there are particular attributes which are associated with the leadership and such attributes can lead a group. Goldsmith (2009) argues that in the group, there might be some common interests which should be well understood and then a clear roadmap or vision should be developed and communicated to address such interests; so that, other people in the group easily follow the particular person and regard as their leader.

Kuehler (2015) argues leadership is the ability to inspire motivation in others to influence them to act towards the desirable vision. He differentiates between management and leadership: management focuses on the task whereas leadership focuses on the person. Leadership brings changes or newness that contributes to motivating followers. The more a leader wins commitment or motivation, the more she/he can be successful to lead others in the common desirable destination.

Mason (2015) defines leadership as simply causing other people to do what a leader wants. This definition is quite similar to Kuehler's (2015) definition as it also indirectly advocates inspiring and motivating others. If leaders ignore other's (followers') interests, they cannot be good leaders since there will not be followers. According to Mason (2015) if the leadership helps others or can show how to reach the common destination, then the followers trust and do what a leader wants. While there are numerous definitions of leadership it is imperative to say

that all of the definitions concur that leadership is the ability to inspire others and get the job done to achieve shared objectives.

2.2.2. Leadership - Born or Made

Scholars agree that leadership is imperative to fulfil collective objectives by inspiring and motivating others. Leadership can explore the optimum potentiality of followers and lead the organization or team to new destinations. Although there is agreement on the importance of leadership, there great debate on "whether leadership is born or made" (Burns, 2012).

According to Engellau et al (2004) leaders are born with genetic factors of leadership, and those good leaders have charismatic attributes that are acquired at birth. Similarly, John, Robins and Pervin (2010) state that leadership is born but not made, and leadership attributes can be inherited automatically. It is well defined by the trait theory which adds that self-confidence, honesty, integrity, cognitive ability and motivation are the key attributes necessary attributes and they are acquired at birth and cannot be learned later (Ruvolo, 2004). According to trait theory leadership is the outcome of nature not nurture. This theory has led to organizations trying to see potential leadership traits before recruiting anyone as a leader in an organization. Tests and exercises are often used to identify applicants' propensity for leadership (Kuehler, 2015).

Hannah (2013) conducted a study regarding the relationship between brain and leadership and found that there are neurological differences between people who have inborn leadership attributes and those who do not have. His research suggests that inborn leadership brain is more active in function. But this finding has not been widely accepted and still, it has not been applied in practice. If these type of (leadership) researches are successful and accurate, it might make it possible to identify leader through brain scanning in the future. Recent researchers have

been studying leadership through a broad context using two models of emotional intelligence (EI) - the ability model and the mixed model. According to Mayer and Salovey (1997), the ability model includes four diverse ranges of attributes such as emotional perception, such as emotion, understanding emotions, and managing emotions. The higher the level of these attributes, the greater the leadership attributes. In the same way, a mixed model was developed by Goleman (1995) who has focused on four competency areas; self-awareness, social awareness, self-management and social skills. Based on these assessment criteria, an individual's emotional intelligence (EI) can be identified. Both of these models support the notion that leadership is born. Many researchers argue that EI is imperative to identify successful leadership. In order to better determine EI, Bar-on (2006) has developed a measure called emotional intelligence quotient (E.Q.). According to this measure the higher the E.Q. score the more successful they will be in leadership.

However, leaders with supposed inborn attributes may also be failures (Locke, 1996). It is imperative to say that the traits can be one of the indicators but it may not be everything as there is an equal role of learning or nurture as well. There is an equally strong argument that says leadership can be made as everyone is born with a blank slate (tabula rasa) and that nurturing plays an important role in developing the necessary leadership attributes (Locke, 1996). Great leaders emerge overtime in the history, for example, Abraham Lincoln, Nelson Mandela, Mahatma Gandhi. However, the great man theory - which was established by the Scottish philosopher and essayist Thomas Carlyle (1795-1881) - does not accept this concept. as the trait theory, it also says that great leaders are born with special qualities like heroic courage, divine inspiration and superior intellect (Carlyle, 1840). This theory rejects any concept that relates to leadership with learned attributes. Those attributes are risk-taking, Although the great man theory argues that the leaders should have heroic attributes and profound intelligent by birth, it was first criticised by Spence (1896) arguing that great man is

the product of society as, without social condition, leadership cannot be created. For example, the leadership of Mahatma Gandhi would not be there if India hadn't been a British colony at that time. Spence (1896) insists that the genesis or inborn attributes cannot be worthwhile if it is not supported by the social situation.

According to Matthews, Martha and Whiteman (2009), some special leadership attributes can be developed in anyone through teaching and learning. The supporters of this theory argue that nurturing skills can be key to increasing leadership (Engellau, Manfred and Varies, 2004). Talent can be in everyone but the ability is the outcome of hard work. If there is no hard work, leadership cannot be achieved even if a person has natural talent. Managerial grid and role theory come under behavioural leadership theory (Blake, and Mouton, 1994). In the managerial grid model, according to Blake Blake and Mouton (1994), there are five types of leadership styles which are based on behaviour traits whereas the role theory seeks to develop leadership skill through the means of role-playing (the details will be presented under leadership theories in section 2.2.3). According to Goldsmith (2009) leadership behaviour can be developed through training. One can develop necessary behaviours as required; thereby leadership can be learned.

Based on the above literature, it can be highlighted that some people might be born with a neurological difference and their emotional intelligence can be different. There might be a small number of people who are born with leadership attributes that contribute to building the leadership but the majority of leaders are made through effort and commitment. To summarise, leadership can be both born and learned but the born leaders are few and if their social situation or environment is unfavourable, their attributes can be meaningless. However, if there is an inborn attribute and suitable environment, there is a higher possibility that a good leader can develop. In this context, it can be said that leadership is the product of both nature and nurture.

2.2.3. Leadership Theories

Different types of leadership theories have been developed to broaden knowledge in understanding leadership. In this section, some of the key theories are presented and discussed.

2.2.3.1. *Great Man Theory*

This theory was first used by Thomas Carlyle (1795-1881) who argues that great heroes are the products of personal charisma and intelligence. Early academic studies on leadership were based on the assumption that leaders are born and are not made. Inborn or heredity attributes determine leadership; thereby it was assumed that leadership can be produced only from aristocratic families (Carlyle, 1840). This theory believes that the heroes or great man create history as they are dominant people in the society and such power was inherited through heredity. It closely associates leaders with a history of the nation (Carlyle, 1840). Later on, this theory was further clarified by other scholars by their researches. For example, Frederick Adam Woods (1873-1939) supported this theory and investigated 386 leaders of Europe from 12th century to 18th century and he concluded that leadership has inborn attributes which are only possible from aristocratic families and these leaders have key roles to set historical events (Waite, 2008). This idea was later criticised by Herbert Spencer (1820-1903) saying that the great man or leader is the product of society or environment.

2.2.3.2. *Trait Theory*

In 1936, Gordon Allport (1897-1967) discovered trait theory which assumes that people are born with some leadership skills (Hayes, 2000). Successful leaders are studied to determine the most important attributes that make an individual a leader and different researchers have identified various leadership traits. As great man theory, it also regards that leader cannot be made because leadership skills are inherited by birth. The great man theory only focuses on a

few leadership attributes but the trait theory identifies several attributes of the leadership and unlike great man theory it does not study the connection between leadership and historical events. Stogdill (1974) identified some leadership traits including decisive, dependable, assertive, self-confident, etc. and some skills as clever, creative, persuasive and organized. McCall and Lombardo (1983) found four key traits, emotional stability, admitting errors, good interpersonal skills, and wide intellect. However, the inherited traits cannot address problems in a different situation and trait theory has consequently been criticised as unpractical (John, Robins and Pervin, 2010). But it is contrasted with the behavioural theory.

2.2.3.3. Behaviour Theory

In response to the great man and trait theory, behavioural theory has been developed. This theory goes against mental or psychical inborn superiority in leadership because it assumes that the leadership is totally learned and there is no role of heredity; thereby the researchers started to study behaviours of the leaders instead of any innate traits assuming that everyone is born with a blank sheet and as she/he gets the right conditions, they can become leaders (Ajzen, 2005). According to Mullen and Goethals (2012) behaviours can be learnt; thereby the leaders can be made. This theory has been divided into two types: the managerial grid model and role theory.

A. Managerial Grid Model

The management grid has five different leadership styles which are related to managers' concern for people and task (figure 1).

Figure 1: Managerial Grid Model

(Source: Molloy, 1988, p 4)

The managerial grid model is formulated based on the x-axis (concerns for people) and y-axis (concerns for production) (Blake and Mouton, 1964). This model has 5 styles: (i) **impoverished style** represents managers' low concern for both people and production because they do not want to make any mistake or get into trouble; (ii) **country club- style** indicates to low concern for production but high concern for people because these types of managers believe that employees' satisfaction helps to enhance employees' performance; (iii) **middle of the road style** tries to make a balance between people and production because these type of managers believe that sustainable performance is only possible through the balance between them; (iv) **team management style** indicates to high concern for both people and production and these types of managers believe that both strong employees commitment and quality product are necessary to succeed an organisation; and (v) **task style** gives more focus on production but it does not focus on people because these types of managers believe that

production is the major thing that should be focused, and if they produce quality and suitable products, business can be successful itself (Blake and Mouton, 1964).

By observing the behaviour, a manager's leadership performance can be assessed by using this grid (Northouse, 2015). For example, if a manager cannot take risks rather wants to secure a job without any trouble, then he may fall under the impoverished style and he neither empowers employees nor tries to enhance quality and quantity of the product. Overall, his performance will be lower than the required to succeed in the organization. Also, it is related to seven key behaviours such as initiative, inquiry, advocacy, decision, conflict, and resilience (Ajzen, 2005). But it has some gaps for example Egner (2009) argues that the lack of empirical data could mean that assessment may not be reliable or valid. The model also does not take a wider range of internal and external variables into consideration.

B. Role Theory

Role Theory was introduced by Robert K. Merton (1910-2003) to understand human behaviour in a sociological and psychological context. This theory argues that human behaviours are guided by the expectations of individual and other people (Walker, 2013). As per those expectations, an individual's role can be determined in society. It further clarifies that every role is determined based on a specific context; so that, human behaviours are predictable. In the context of leadership, a leader defines his role based on how the followers want to see him (Turner, 2006). It means to say that the surrounding context or the expectations of the followers determine the role after leaders. It also explains the reproduction of behaviour where the particular role can be played and people's responses can be collected (Biddle, 2013). As any role becomes successful, it can be applied in real practice as a leadership role. According to Walker (2013), it can be applicable in conflict resolution and in studying the detailed behaviour of an individual. Further, it helps to understand the roles of different people in society.

However, Biddle (2013) argues that identifying suitable role can be difficult, costly and time-consuming and may not represent the reality as well because it is quite difficult to find the perfect role that could satisfy each follower.

2.2.3.4. Participative Leadership

The major assumption of participative leadership theory is that peoples' involvement in decision making contributes to increasing commitment, motivation, ownership, and responsibility (Northouse, 2015). It implies that people cannot increase their performance level if they are not given opportunities for participating in the decision-making process. Additionally, when people are involved in the decision-making process, there will be better decision making. According to Ricketts and Ricketts (2010), all of the key stakeholders' voices can be heard and each participant is given equal focus in this leadership style and it is, therefore; the opposite of the autocratic leadership style in which only the leader makes every decision and the followers must have to follow the decision without questioning, with equal participation of the followers unlike top-level decision of the autocratic leadership style. Mehrotra (2005) says that it can be effective to implement into practice but sometimes making decisions might be difficult as there are various arguments and in the larger organization, it is very complicated to ensure participation of each stakeholder. It can be divided into two different styles: Lewin's leadership styles and Likert's leadership style.

A. Lewin's Leadership Styles

Lewin's leadership styles were based on a leadership experiment conducted in 1939 that concluded that identified three types of leadership styles; autocratic, democratic and laissez-faire (Lewin, Lippit and White, 1939). Autocratic leadership takes decisions without consulting stakeholders. It can be applicable in situations where employees' motivation is not affected by not being part of the decision-making process (Daft, 2014). As the people are not

self-motivated and there is no honest working cultural tendency, autocratic leadership can be preferred. A democratic leadership style is established when people strongly participate in the decision-making process. The leader is facilitated by people but as there is a wider range of perceptions, coming to the final decision can be complicated (Callanen, 1999). For example, if there are 1,000 people, then there will be several perceptions which are difficult to collect and synthesise. Laissez fair leadership style minimises the leader's involvement (Pride, Hughes and Kapoor, 2009) and people are allowed to make their own decisions but are equally responsible for the outcome. This style can be highly effective if the people are capable and motivated - and the groups can run independently without central coordination (Lewin, Lippit and White, 1939). For example, in a team, people make their decision to fulfil their own role but they are guided by the team objectives.

B. Likert's Leadership Style

Likert's leadership style identified four types of leadership styles: exploitive authoritative, benevolent authoritative, consultative and participatory (Likert, 1967). Exploitive authoritative leadership style has low levels of concern over people and to get the job done the leader uses threat or fear (Aluya, 2009). As for example if there is punishment for the low performance, employees try their best to increase the level of performance and get rid of such punishment. A benevolent authoritative leader is more much concerned about the people and according to Ghuman (2010) motivates people by using rewards and listens to the people but a key decision is still made by the top management. It means to say that although the people are motivated, they are far behind from fully participating in the decision-making process. If the leader is deciding, he listens to people and rewards for the good performance, unlike exploitive authoritative leadership style. Consultative leadership style involves genuine efforts to facilitate the participation of people in decision making but still the decision is imposed by the

top management as there is no in-depth involvement of the people (Likert, 1976). It suggests that the major decisions are mainly decided by the leader and it may not care about the majority voice as well. According to Likert (1967) in the participative leadership style, there is maximum involvement of people and their voices are genuinely listened but the major decision is taken by the leader. He argues that it is a very fruitful style that increases motivation and the responsibility of the followers. The participation helps to own the decision as well.

2.2.3.5. Situational Theories

The key assumption of situational leadership theory is that the best action of a leader depends on the specific situation (Bertocci, 2009). It indicates that a single dogma or theory may not be applicable in all situations because in different situations the leadership has to act differently. According to Zehndorfer (2013), the situational decision can be affected by two factors like the motivation and capacity of the followers. In the same way, Bertocci (2009) argues that the relationship between leader and followers can also affect to determine leadership behaviour, and both are equally imperative. Thus, it can be said that specific situation and the leader's perception of the followers determine leadership style.

Tannenbaum and Schmidt (1958) have identified three forces that contribute to determine leadership behaviour: situational forces, follower forces, and leader forces. Situation indicates to both internal and external environmental factors. If an organisation has self-motivated, skilful and dedicated employees, a leader can use more liberal and participatory leadership approach whereas if the employees are not skilful and not proactive, the leader does not participate employees in the decision-making process and he can be strict in applying decision into practice (Bertocci, 2009). Although they share same external factors, internal factors might be different from one organization to another. The internal and external situations are the key forces in determining leadership behaviour. In the same way, a leader has to listen the followers'

voice which means to say that followers are also determined forces of leadership behaviour. The leader oneself can also be the determining force as his skills, abilities, experiences and family background also affect him to shape his leadership behaviours (Zehndorfer, 2013). All these forces are changeable; thereby the leadership style can be variable. There are different types of situational leadership styles such as Hersey and Blanchard's Situational Leadership, Vroom and Yetton's Normative Model, and House's Path-Goal Theory of Leadership.

A. Hersey and Blanchard's Situational Leadership

Hersey and Blanchard's situational leadership approach advocates that a leader should determine their leadership style based on their followers' development style (level of followers' willingness to perform the required task). This model depends upon the level of task and relation focus (Hersey, 2004). Relation oriented behaviour focuses on satisfaction and motivation of the followers whereas task-oriented behaviour gives more focus on the task that is required to achieve particular objectives of the team. Different leaders may give different focus on task and relation. Some of the leaders give more focus on task but others give focus on relation. Some of the leaders try to maintain balance between task and relation; so, they try to maintain equal focus (Heidrich, 2014). In this model, there are four leadership styles (S1 to S4) (Figure 2.) that are determined based on followers' willing to learn (Hersey and Blanchard, 1999).

Figure 2: Hersey and Blanchard's Model

(Source: Hersey and Blanchard, 1997, p.6)

S1 indicates to telling or directing which is associated with low commitment, low confidence and low willing to learn in the followers but there is high task focus and low relationship focus on the leadership (Hersey, 2004). In the same way, S2 refers to selling or coaching in which the followers have increased confidence and variable commitment but still, they are not willing to learn (Heidrich, 2014) In this style, the leader has a high task as well as relationship focus. Likewise, S3 is related to participating or supporting in which the followers have high competence and variable commitment but still they are unwilling to learn (Hersey, 2004). In case of a leader, there is low task focus and high relationship focus. Similarly, S4 indicates to delegating or observing in which the followers have high competence, high commitment and willing to learn (Landy and Conte, 2009). In case of leaders, they have low task focus and low relationship focus.

B. Vroom and Yetton's Normative Model

Vroom and Yetton's normative model assumes that the participants' acceptance contributes to increasing commitment and effectiveness of their activities. Decision acceptance is the degree

to which the followers accept the decision. The more decision acceptance the better decision can be implemented; thereby the leader tries to increase acceptance of the decision. According to Vroom and Yetton (1973), there are five types of decision procedures (figure 3). In A1 (autocratic1) procedure, a leader takes known information and makes decisions alone. Similarly, in A2 (autocratic 2) a leader collects information from the followers but again makes decisions alone. Likewise, in C1(consultative 1) a leader communicates with followers individually, listen to them but again makes decisions alone. In the same way, in C2 (consultative 2), a leader communicates with followers as a group, listen to them but again makes decisions alone. In G2 (group-based), a leader communicates with followers as a group and seeks the agreement of the followers on the decision (Vroom and Yetton, 1973).

Figure 3: Vroom and Yetton's Normative Model.

(Source: Avendano, Flores-Urbaz and Briceno,2020, p.2)

C. House's Path-Goal Theory of Leadership

The path-goal theory of leadership explains the ways that a leader motivates people to fulfil common goals and objectives (Northouse, 2015). According to this theory, a leader explains

the path, identities and eliminates the obstacles, and rewards the followers. House and Mitchell (1974) say that there are four types of path-goal leadership styles: supportive, directive, participative and achievement-oriented. Supportive leadership understands the needs of the followers and tries to fulfil such needs ensuring an effective working environment (Schermerhorn, 2011). The leader motivates and encourages followers, and this approach is appropriate as the work is stressful (House and Mitchell, 1974). In the same way, directive leadership style gives guidance or instructions. It may include developing time-schedule, encouraging followers and offering rewards. This approach is applicable if the task is complicated and followers are inexperienced. Participative leadership style focuses on consulting with followers and considering their ideas before making decisions (DuBrin, 2015). This approach is applicable as the followers are expert and experienced. According to Northouse (2015), achievement-oriented leadership sets goals (work and self-improvement) and the leader encourages followers to succeed in the goals. It can be best applicable if the task is complicated and followers are motivated.

2.2.3.6. Contingency Theories

This theory depends on different situational factors such as a leader's style, capabilities and followers' abilities to adapt the decision (Locke, 1999). It is also a sub-class of behaviour theory and it assumes that there is no single leadership style that can be applied for every situation. One style can be the best fit in a particular situation but it may not be equally applicable in other situations. It is quite similar to situational theory in the sense that both theories argue that there is no single leadership theory that can be applied in every situation; based on the changing situation, the leadership theory should also be changed. According to Fairholm and Fairholm (2009), the main difference between situational theory and contingency theory is that situational theory gives more focus on behaviour whereas contingency theory considers the

wider factors including leader's ability and other related variables. Contingency theory has three sub-divisions such as Fiedler's Least Preferred Co-worker theory, cognitive resource theory, and strategic contingency theory.

A. Fiedler's Least Preferred Co-worker Theory (LPC)

Fiedler's least preferred co-worker theory says that relationships, power and task structure are the responsible factors to determine leadership style (Barman, 2009). The leader asks followers to think of a person and to score positive and negative factors. It tries to find out whether the leaders see the followers as positive or negative. As the leader scores positive, then she/he can be considered as high LPC leader but if the leader scores negative, then she/he can be considered as a low LPC leader. The high LPC leaders are supportive and the relationship will be the priority than task whereas the low LPC leaders give much focus on task than the relationship (Bryman, Collinson and Grint, 2011).

B. Cognitive Resource Theory

This theory assumes that leadership style is shaped by the capacity or ability of the leader. The leadership capability depends upon intelligence and experience; thereby leadership style can be different from one person to another (Qutob, 2013). This theory predicts that a leader's cognition underpins for teamwork as she/he uses the directive approach. In the same way, the second prediction is that there is a significant role of stress as it affects the relationship between cognition and decision making. Likewise, the third prediction is that experience contributes to overcoming stress while making decisions. Also, the final prediction is that there is no relevance of intelligence and experience if the problem is simple (Barman, 2009).

C. Strategic Contingency Theory

This leadership style tries to use cognition through new styles to which it focuses on skills, its uniqueness, and centrality. As the leadership has related skills and expertise, it will generate effectiveness and efficacy. If it is used uniquely, others cannot copy it; thereby sustainable competitive advantages can be generated (Daft, Murphy and Willmott, 2010).

2.2.3.7. *Transactional Leadership*

This leadership style assumes that the followers can be motivated or encouraged by reward and punishment. In the same way, according to Dakhil (2008), there is a proper chain of command where the followers accept the leadership command. In the workplace or team, there is a clear structure, in which the subordinate has to obey the command as a result, they can get a reward. If the followers obey the command, there is no use of any punishment. According to Raman (2010), the leadership negotiates with subordinates with salary and reward. Then, the leadership allocates task and subordinates are supposed to accomplish accordingly. Here the leader does not care whether the subordinates have the adequate capability, skills, and resources or not. If she/he becomes a failure to accomplish the task, she/he will be punished.

It is based on contingent leadership style because the reward or punishment depends upon the performance of the subordinates. It is very easy to apply in practice however it is criticised on its assumption that a man may not be always guided by reward and punishment. Bertocci (2009) says that sometimes, people can work for reputation or contribution instead of merely reward.

Leader-member Exchange (LMX)

In the transactional leadership theory, leader-member exchange (LMX) can be considered as the key style which says that a leader can maintain the position through several exchange

contracts with her/his followers. It can be in-group and out-group agreement where in-group has better influences than out-group (Foster, 2012). The leader can allocate responsibility and in response salary or reward can be offered. The LMX process can be divided into three stages, for example, the first stage is role- taking in which the leader assesses the ability of the team members; the second stage is role making in which the leader allocates role; and the final stage is systematization in which the leader develops it as the ongoing system (Nelson, 2015).

2.2.3.8. Transformational Leadership

According to Dakhil (2008), transformational leadership tries to transform required skills and expertise on followers by inspiring, motivating, teaching and offering training. This theory assumes that the followers follow the leader who inspires them. Similarly, Bass and Riggio (2006) argue that followers who have passion can learn skills and expertise. Also, motivation and enthusiasm contribute to empowering the followers.

Northouse (2015) says that this leadership begins with developing the vision by which the followers can be connected. It can be developed by the team leader and the vision has to be later communicated with the followers. As the vision is effectively persuaded, then it motivates followers to achieve the vision. In the next stage, the leader can find some effective ways to forward the vision to a wider level. In the final stage, the leader has to be in the front line to directly motivate followers and get the job done. This process can be observed in the transformational leadership and there are different variants of transformational leadership styles such as Bass' Transformational Leadership Theory, Burns' Transformational Leadership Theory and Kouzes and Posner's Leadership Participation Inventory (Dakhil, 2008).

A. Bass' Transformational Leadership Theory

This leadership theory assumes that the alertness of the task contributes to motivating people. In the same way, it assumes that focus on teamwork enhances the performance of the followers (Bass and Riggio, 2006). It implies that trust, respect, and inspiration of the leadership effects in transforming the skills and abilities to the followers. According to Bass (1985), a leader can transform followers in three different way such as increasing alertness of the task, focusing on the team and fulfilling their needs. This kind of leadership has a key focus on influence, motivation, stimulation and consideration aspects to effectively transform necessary skills.

B. Burns' Transformational Leadership Theory

It assumes that working in a team and motivating can contribute to increasing knowledge and expertise in the related field. In this leadership style, the leader and followers engage in achieving common goals through morality and motivation (Burns, 1978). It is a continuous process where the motivation keeps on exploring the charismatic attributes of the followers.

C. Kouzes and Posner's Leadership Participation Inventory

The theory was developed by Kouzes and Posner (2002) by conducting a survey in which the sample respondents were asked to find seven of the most important leadership attributes. Based on the survey this theory has identified numbers of key leadership attributes such as honesty, forward-looking, competent, etc. Further, they identified that to be a successful leader, there are 5 ways which are important to transform others: modelling, inspiring, challenging the process, enabling and encouraging others.

2.2.3.9. Critical leadership Studies

Lastly, although there are many theories that emerged in the field of leadership over time there is no one theory that is superior to another and fits in every situation. The environmental

situation where organizations operate is rapidly changing and as a result vacuum is created. Therefore, whether the leadership theories are still capable of addressing real problems that the new generation of leadership is facing in a new dynamic environment is still not obvious. When it comes to leadership, the concept of one-man army (superhero figure) still appears. All success and failure are attached to the figure rather than collective achievement of desired outcome. As described by Dennis Tourish (2019), (leading figure in emerging area of 'critical leadership studies) as more and more management research being published on this field, it has lost its way and needs radical reform. According to him, management research suffers from failing to address practical problems managers and employees face, endless obscure theorizing, poor writing and research paper being retracted for fraud (Tourish, 2019).

Unlike before, most of the problem facing today is never faced before such as climate change, technological advancement, terrorism, changing nature of work and lifestyle and pandemic like Covid-19, that need collective response from different expertise and that require often acting independently (Tourish, 2020). Directive approaches often used in the past may not be useful in these new scenarios. To make leadership more configured to address wider stakeholders need for long run, more focus should be on facilitation of alternative viewpoint, leadership should be taken as firsthand of order than life of an organization and facilitating collective shared responsibilities across all departments rather than traditional centric approach (Tourish, 2019).

2.3. Gender

2.3.1. Gender: An Introduction

Gender is a social term that signifies males or females as social or cultural products than any biological construct. According to Rhynie and Secretariat (1999), "Gender refers to the socially

constructed, rather than the biologically defined, sex roles and attributes of females and males." Veur, Ohana, and Titley (2007) say that gender is "socially constructed roles, behaviours, activities, and attributes" which are different for men and women. These definitions clarify that gender is the socially constructed values and beliefs which are attributed to males and females. Further, it can be said that different societies might have their own type of gender attributes and different values for males and females can be constructed. According to Momsen (2009), it does not have direct relations with sex but indirectly while creating male and female values, society considers some biological aspects as well. For example, females can give birth and often need to take care of the child; thereby, in most of the societies, female values are often more strongly associated with household rather than other activities. Gilbert and Scher (2009) argue that biologically females are weaker than males and that some societies embrace the males' role as a protector to the females. In this way, by considering biological attributes males and females are given different roles.

It is imperative to say that some people consider sex and gender as synonymous but they are different from each other. According to Archer and Lloyd (2002), sex is related to anatomy or sex attributes whereas gender is the social role. Sex can be universal but gender roles can be different as per society. In case of transgender, the definition of sex or gender may not be applicable because particular sex attributes may not be found on them and they may not fully adapt gender attributes (Harrison and Williams, 2002). Alternatively, one's sex and gender attributes shape his/her behaviours.

2.3.2. Gender Discrimination

In society, there might be several types of discrimination. According to the definition of International Labour Organization (2003) discrimination refers to any type of distinction, exclusion or preference that is made based on a particular race, colour, gender, nationality,

opinion, etc. It is imperative to say that similar to racial discrimination, gender discrimination is also one of the major problems of society (Roemer, 2009). According to Boeri, Patacchini, and Peri (2015), gender discrimination is not only limited to a country, but it has also spread all over the world; only the discrimination ratio can be different. For example, women in the United State have also faced discrimination but that is not quite straight forward as in the developing countries like Nepal. In the rural area in Nepal, women are not getting equal education, health facilities and career opportunity (Dahal, Topping and Levy,2021). However, in the developed countries the discrimination is not so obvious; it exists on the psychology which represents in the behaviour (Joshi and Paci, 2001).

According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), gender discrimination can be divided into two types: direct and indirect. If a particular gender is excluded from certain opportunities through the means of legal framework although there is no less qualification and skill on that group, it is regarded as the direct discrimination. For example, before 1920, females were deprived of voting in the US (Flexner and Fitzpatrick, 1996). If intrinsically neutral rules and regulations negatively affect particular groups, then it can be considered as indirect discrimination (ILO, 2003). For instance, in many organizations, part-time employees are not given the same opportunities compared to full-time employees. Mostly, females are working a part-time job due to their household responsibilities and childcare. In this context, indirectly females are discriminated against males.

Roemer (2009) says that while selecting someone for employment, political belief, physical abilities, work efficiency, and particular faith could be the points of discrimination. In the same way, there should be particular protection to ensure equality among the employees. For example, for female maternity or pregnancy protections should be ensured. According to UNDP (1995) gender discrimination can be, mainly, seen in four areas:

2.3.2.1. Education

In developing countries, there is a higher difference in literacy rate. According to UNDP (2003) in 2001, there was only 67% female literacy rate of male literacy rate in South Asia. In developed countries, this kind of high discrepancy cannot be found. For example, the male and female literacy rate is neck to neck and in some countries like in the US, male percentage in college is higher (56%) than females (US Department of Education, 2016) but clearly discrimination impacts throughout females' careers can be seen, for example, "women hold only 20% of the professorship in UK universities" (Oxford Royal Academy, 2017). Although more women have received a university degree, in career development in the education sector, they are far behind than men which show gender discrimination.

2.3.2.2. Health

In developing countries, special health needs are often neglected and there is a big problem of maternal mortality rate. This might be considered as one of the serious gender discriminations (Gaimard, 2013). For example, according to the World Bank (2003), 2,000 women died per 100,000 live births in 1995 in developing countries. This rate has been reduced but still not satisfactory because of negligence on women health and lack of resources. According to The World Factbook (2015) in developing countries, there is still high maternal mortality rate as for example in Sierra Leone, Central African Republic, Chad, Nigeria and South Sudan the maternal mortality rate is 1,360, 882, 856, 814 and 789 in 100,000 live births respectively in 2015. It reveals that in the health sector, developing countries have to give much more focus on female health especially maternity.

2.3.2.3. *Economy*

To achieve long-term economic growth to eradicate poverty of any country, economic empowerment of women is considered to be a vital weapon (Duflo,2012). Therefore, taking care of underpowered females and involving them to the workforce can uplift countries' economy significantly. According to Scott et al (2010), mostly females work more in totally unpaid household activities. Further, in most of the countries, females mostly work in wages or part-time and there is very low female involvement in employment. For example, in Pakistan in 2011 about 82% males and 25% females and in Morocco in 2012 72% males and 25% females were employed (Verick, 2019). Most of the females in developing countries do not work in the organization and they do not hold the higher positions as well. It means to say that they do either an unpaid job or very low paid job; thereby, they have to be depended upon males. Although their household economy share is increasing, they have to depend upon males. Even in the same work also they are paid less than males in some of the societies like in rural parts of Nepal for the same job females are paid almost half of the male's wages (Joshi and Paci, 2001) In some of the countries, certain positions are not allowed to females. For example in Kuwait, females do not have access to the judicial career because of their cultural and traditional values (ILO, 2003).

Females have more unpaid household responsibility than males. According to the report of World Bank (2012) females work 1 to 3 hours more a day for housework and 2 to 10 hours to care. But in market activities, they spend 1 to 4 hours less than males. Anyway, this data could be adequate to prove that females are giving much more time for unpaid household activities. According to the report of UN Women (2016) in the European Union, 25% of women discontinue their job due to care and other family responsibility whereas in case of males it is only 3%. This data strongly supports the argument that females have more household

responsibility than males; thereby, they are deprived of the labour force or paid work. It can be said that gender inequality persists in every country but only the quantity of inequality can be different. Indeed, if combined both paid and unpaid work, female work more than males but their earning is very low. According to the report of OECD (2012) more males spend on leisure, self-care, and political activities but the females spend on unpaid household activities. In most of the developing countries, women work in a farm which is totally unpaid. Mostly, female work in vulnerable, low paid or unpaid jobs; so that, their economic contribution cannot be compared with males but as mentioned already, females work more hours than males. But according to Nganga (2011) to succeed in a business or grow economy, both males and females should be equally involved in economic activities. If they are deprived of the workforce and they are confined only in household activities, it badly affects economic growth.

2.3.2.4. Politics

Although women have been given right to vote in most of the countries, their participation in parliament and government is very low in every country for example according to UN Women (2019) in all national parliament there is only 24.3% female representation as per November 2018 and merely 11 women are head of state and 10 are head of government. In the World, the number of total MPs is 46,177 in which 34,780 are males and 11,147 are females. In case of region-wise female representation, Nordic countries, Americas, Europe, Sub-Saharan Africa, Asia, Middle East and North Africa, and Pacific have 42.5%, 30.7%, 28.5%, 23.7%, 19.4%, 18.1% and 18.4% respectively in 2019 (Women in National Parliament, 2019). It shows that there is no significant difference between developed and developing countries. As females have low representation in decision making power, their voice cannot be heard or it can be outnumbered by the males' voice (Paxton, Hughes, 2015). No matter whether that is developed

or developing countries, the female representation in law-making or decision-making level is very low.

2.3.3. Minimising Gender Discrimination in Workplace

In most cases women are considered as a second-class citizen and discriminated in workplace (Cameron, 2017). To reduce gender discrimination in the workplace, awareness has to be increased along with developing suitable laws (Gaag, 2014). The government and related organizations should strongly act to reduce any kind of workplace gender discrimination. Nganga (2011) says that any obstacles, whether they are related to cultural, traditional or religious issues should be slowly identified and eliminated.

In the case of employment, ILO (2003) has made two considerable provisions. The first one is the Equal Remuneration Convention (no 100) that ensures equal pay not just for similar work but also for work of equal value. It clarifies that in wages there should not be different for male and female for the work of similar value. There might be different jobs for males and females but they should be evaluated based on value and wages should be determined. It secures females to be discriminated against by getting low wages. The second one is the Employment and Occupation Convention (no 111) that ensures equal treatment for every employee regarding occupational opportunities, education, and promotion. Job security, pension, and other opportunities should be equal to both male and female. In 1998 both of these provisions were put under the Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work. Likewise, convention no. 100 has been widely accepted and by 2003 it was rectified by 161 countries and convention no. 111 by 159 countries (ILO, 2003a). According to Busse and Spielmann (2003) along with ILO, the UN has also worked out to eliminate gender discrimination. In 1979 the Elimination of Gender Discrimination provision was introduced and its major aim was to

ensure equal wages between male and female. By 2003, it was rectified by 174 countries and they are committed for global development by equal participation and opportunities.

Busse and Spielmann (2003) conducted an empirical study to show the relationship between gender discrimination and foreign direct investment (FDI). The report has concluded that international organizations do not want to invest in those countries where there is a higher gender discrimination level. Although there is no direct relationship between gender discrimination and FDI, the companies find poor labour standard is unfair. Further, some of the companies argue that the World Trade Organization (WTO) should punish such countries which do not meet basic labour standard. There is the key argument that how WTO could play effectively to eradicate gender discrimination in the workplace in its affiliated countries. Some of the scholars say that trade sanctions can be one of the effective methods but it has not worked to give a better result. Nguyen and Zampetti (2004) say that if there is any trade sanction, instead of reducing gender discrimination, the organizations start to move women in other sections where they get lower wages and low level of facilities. It would be better to support the developing countries by providing economic aid and awareness program.

2.4. Gender and Leadership

Mostly, in leadership research, gender has often been replaced by sex with some collective sets of qualities labelled to men and women (Nganga, 2011). Men are regarded as being more aggressive, rational, logical, decisive, confident and independent – showing men being stronger and more capable of taking leadership positions. Women are described as sensitive, warm, talkative, gentle, submissive, and emotional – mostly taken as too weak to lead (Ibarra, Ely, and Kolb, 2013). Those qualities show men are more task-oriented, result-driven, and adopt transactional styles of leadership. Women are more likely to be seen as transformational leaders with a relationship-oriented and nurturing approach. Traditionally, leadership has always been

related to masculine characteristics and women with feminine characteristics may not be taken as a legitimate leader (Rhee and Sigler, 2015). Likewise, when it comes to taking the leadership roles; women are not taken seriously, in most of the cultures; leadership is directly related to masculinity. On the one hand, an ideal leader is characterised as independent, assertive and decisive and on the other hand, women are characterised as caretaking, nice and unselfish. This kind of social belief or practice puts females far away from acquiring any leadership position (Ibarra, Ely, and Kolb, 2013). Women adopting masculine characteristics are often judged unfavourably as they are not acting within the feminine gender role (Koch, 2005). So, in both ways, women are being treated unfavourably when it comes to judging women for leadership capabilities. Similarly, women have to put more effort than men counterparts to achieve top managerial leadership position (Yaruge- perales, Perez-Ledo and March- Chorda, 2021). Due to this reason, there are merely 24.3% women are MPs in the parliaments of nations in 2019 (Women in National Parliament, 2019).

Many studies show that women have developed value and characteristics which clearly differ from the traditional competitive, aggressive and controlling behaviour acquired by men leaders. Although women leadership style is different from men leaders; effective leadership is not the domain to any gender but rather they can learn from each other (Applebaum, Audet, and Miller, 2003). According to their findings, women's leadership styles are not less effective than men; rather, more effective in the context of team-based organisations. They also highlight the issue of women being less effective than men and argue that this is not true; thereby it is not fact-driven rather perceptual driven.

According to Ibarra, Ely, and Kolb (2013), when it comes to choosing between men and women for senior leadership positions; women are victims of gender discrimination. Women are often being judged by their gender rather than their skills and talents required for leadership

positions. Similarly, women are perceived as being less effective than men to lead the team. According to Watson and Hoffman (2004), although women are equally effective as male counterparts in influencing their team and taking effective decisions, women are rated lower and significantly less preferred than male leaders. Likewise, many studies on women and leadership show that men leaders are hugely preferred than women leaders by both male and female subordinates although their leadership styles and skills are similar to one another (Eagly and Karat, 2002).

According to an exploratory study by Buchanan, Warning and Tett (2012) examining whether women prefer to be supervised by female managers found that - women prefer male managers. This study also highlighted that women's perceptions towards female managers were more negative; meanwhile, male subordinates were more positive about male managers. Furthermore, in certain situations, women are likely to react more negatively to women leader's non-traditional behaviours. This is related to the study conducted by Biernat and Feuten (2001) that found out; women tend to demonstrate more gender bias compared to men (Rhee and Sigler, 2015). Various studies highlight situations to choose between highly qualified men and women candidates and – women constantly chose men over women (Biernat and Feuten, 2001). Thereby, women have to perform extremely well to prove themselves to both males and females.

From the various studies conducted over the years, it can be concluded that clearly there is gender bias in the workplace. To achieve leadership positions, women are pushed behind not only by male domination but also, to some extent, by a lack of support and trust from their own gender.

2.5. Glass Ceiling and its Challenges

The phrase "glass ceiling" was used by the feminist Marilyn Loden in 1978 to indicate barriers to be promoted in the higher positions in employment (Donald, 2015). Metaphorically, it implies an invisible barrier to the minority groups and females to cross a certain level. It makes great challenges to get equal opportunities for females. In the same way, according to Scott, Crompton, and Lyonett (2010), culture and tradition have created glass ceiling in different societies. The women are habituated on the particular culture as they are brought up within that culture and tradition. If they go against the culture, the society does not take it as normal and she could be considered as the antisocial woman (Mohanty and Biswal, 2007). In this regard, the woman must obey the culture. As for example in some of the communities, women are not allowed to be a priest. Indeed, a priest is the most respected position in society; he is considered as God. But the women are said that if they become a priest, then there will be great disloyalty to the God and he will be angry with humankind (Mohanty and Biswal, 2007). This kind of saying has been widely spread in the society and it becomes the social norms. In the name of culture and religion, no woman can dare to challenge this kind of culture but it is a kind of glass ceiling. It is perceived as the religious value but it has made women only as prayers and men as priests. It is also an important social position but males do not want to see female in that position. David and Woodward (2005) say that until and unless this kind of glass is not broken, it is impossible for the elimination of gender discrimination. It is imperative to say that this kind of glass ceiling exists in every country across the world (Donald, 2015). Here the question arouses what are the challenges to break such glass? Is it possible to easily break it and establish equality?

Of course, it is not easy to break glass ceiling because it has been applied to the marginalised groups which are themselves powerless; they are not in the place to decision making and they

are made dependent for the long time (Murry, 2010). If they are dependent, how they can challenge to the persons to whom they depend on? The social system, organizational structure, political structure, education system, etc. have some kind of unseen barriers which deprive women or minority groups to get opportunities regardless they have required skills and abilities (Peters and Wolper, 2018).

Theoretically, it is accepted that diversity in the workplace is required to incorporate women and other minority groups but in practice, it is not found (Ezbilgin, 2009). Developed countries claim that they have gender equality but in reality, there is a strong glass ceiling that cannot be easily broken (Gregory, 2003). As for example the following Table 1 illustrates the low number of female representation but at the same time, it can be said that the percentage of representation has been increasing in later years compared to the past.

Table 1: Female Representation in European Commission

Years	Female Representation
1989-1992	12%
1992-1994	6%
1994-1999	25%
1999-2004	25%
2004-2009	29%

2009-2014	33%
2014-2024 (February)	39.8%

Source: European Parliament Report, (2024)

According to Channar (2012) in democracy, majority voice is valid and implemented into practice. As the males are in majority in an organization, then their voice will be dominant and females will not be listened which is structural discrimination. Even though their organizations claim they have practiced gender equality as they select low numbers of female representatives, then there exists a glass ceiling. To break this type of glass ceiling, in every decision-making level there must be an equal number of females' representation (Gregory, 2003). If women are outnumbered by males, there will be a low chance of woman to be selected in leadership positions because males do not want to work under female leadership (Bhardwaj, 2005). According to Channar (2012) mostly, males can be jealous over female and they do not want to see female leadership. Even in developed countries, most of the leadership positions are holding by the males. To solve this kind of problem, reservation quota might be one of the best methods (Channar, 2012). To ensure female participation and reduce gender discrimination, some of the countries have been securing women seats through a quota system in different areas from politics to civil service employment. For example, the new constitution (The Constitution of Nepal, 2016) of Nepal has secured 33% female representatives in parliament. In the same way, there must be one female either in the president or vice president position, and speaker or vice speaker of parliament. Likewise, in the local level also females' quotas have been guaranteed in different positions like there must be one female either in the mayor or vice mayor of the municipality and in every civil service employment position also there is female quota (The Constitution of Nepal, 2016). If every country has this kind of quota system,

there would be easy to break the glass ceiling but in most of the countries even in the developed countries also this kind of provisions cannot be found. Females are low represented; as a result, their voices can be invalid, and they become powerless (Donald, 2015).

2.6. Women Education

Women education has a direct relation to health, empowerment, employment, prestige, poverty alleviation and gender equality (Holsinger and Jacob, 2009). In the past, it was believed that women do not need any formal education. As they were deprived of education, they became backward. According to Reineke (2011), the feminist movement has contributed to revolt against the masculine domination and get equality in every aspect including in the education sector. Especially, in 1949, the feminist Simone de Beauvoir (1908-1986) wrote a female revolutionary book called *The Second Sex* which became very much famous in 1968 and since then the female movement got much popularity. This book contributed women to open their eyes to see existing gender discrimination and raise their voice for equality. They are considered as the second sex in society. Beauvoir (1949) says that women are treated as a slave and they do not have any freedom. She strongly states that without female participation in production and freedom from reproductive slavery, women cannot come forward and they can be always slaves. Of course, the female movement has contributed to increasing great awareness regarding female education. It could be in religious education, university-level education, primary education, secondary education, etc. It means to say that this movement opened the door to acquire a different type of educations.

Currently, especially in developed countries, there is not that much difference between males and females' percentage of receiving higher education. As for example in the UK gap between male and female in receiving University education was 9.2% in 2015 (Weale, 2015). In the same way, in 2013, over "six million students across OECD countries graduated from higher

education intuition with a bachelor's degree; 58% of them were women." In the case of country-wise data, 69% in Sweden. Except for a few countries like Japan, Germany, Korea, Switzerland, and Turkey, in the rest of the OECD countries, the female graduate number is higher (Damme, 2016). In the same way, it is imperative to say that 60% of low performers are males due to their negligence and low motivation in education. Anyway, it shows that in developed countries, there is no gender discrimination in education. But this kind of situation cannot be found in developing countries. Although there is awareness about education and the number of female students in primary, secondary and higher education have been increasing, the success rate is low. There is a higher dropout rate due to family responsibility, early marriage, and poverty (Haskin and Sawhill, 2009).

Although there was high discrimination in education between male and female, the gap has been continuously reducing due to awareness and growing importance of female education to develop a society. Currently, around two-third of the world females (796 million) in the world are literate (Pareja, 2017). Although in the urban both males and females almost equally attend school, in rural area discrimination has been still existing. According to UN Women (2012), in the rural area, 39% of females attend secondary school whereas 45% males. In the urban area, 59% of females and 60% of males attend secondary school. The UN data reveals that in the rural area there is twice the number of drop out of school as compared to the urban area. In most of the societies, females are not allowed to go far distance and take education. If their travelling distance to the school increases, mostly, females drop out their school. So, it seems that still lots of efforts are required to educate females from rural areas in developing countries.

2.7. Barriers to Women Leadership

Women are largely underrepresented in many top leadership positions across most institutions (Alison and Christy, 2014). Due to underrepresentation of women in top positions women's

leadership has always been a major topic of discussion (Soklaridis and Lopez, 2014). There might be many barriers in different levels within the process of career progression that creates a glass ceiling and prevent women from achieving higher leadership positions. Many researchers have tried to identify and categorise the barriers that come in the way of women's career progression in leadership (Cubillo and Brown, 2003). To reach higher position in organisational career women have to face many visible and invisible barriers such as lack of education, experience, training, lack of informal networking, stereotype attitude, biases in workplace, traditional cultural believe, lack of role model and mentoring and lack of risk-taking ability and lists goes on (Sabharwal, 2013; Kulkarni and Mishra 2022). According to the findings of Glass Ceiling Commission Report in 2005 mostly women tend to be left behind due to some obvious barriers and those can be categorised into four elements such as societal, governmental, internal business and organisational structure.

2.7.1. Societal Barrier

According to the report of the Glass Ceiling Commission Report (2005) societal barriers are related to social opportunities, prejudice, culture, gender and colour bias. Indeed, societal issues are the most influential factors which are not easily changed overnight as they are deeply rooted in the culture and social systems (Schwanke, 2013). Women bring up in a discriminated society; so, they are trained to internalize that culture. If a society does not want to see anyone go beyond the social norms it is difficult for women to revolt against this. It creates a kind of glass ceiling - a subtle and invisible obstacle. According to Eagley and Sczesny (2009), there are some key social aspects like social program and policy, and the social expectation of woman roles that are the key social barriers. As women are confined within household activities, they have limited knowledge about social changes. On the one hand, they are not given the opportunities to take the leadership positions and on the other hand, they are blamed as unable.

This kind of social double standard can be one of the key barriers for females to get leadership positions (Channar, 2012).

In the same way, social expectations of females can be a key societal barrier. Based on deeply rooted culture, male and female's roles are determined. In most of the societies, males are in decision making a place or leadership position; such societies do not want to see a female in leadership positions (Glass Ceiling Commission Report ,1995). If the female holds a leadership positions, the people in the society do not easily accept her as the leader due to patriarchal perception. Mainly in south Asian countries, patriarchal control is exercised over women (Abraham, 2000). Marriage is seen as a vital institution that defines status of women thereby demanding women to be fully obedient and self-sacrificing to a husband and her in-laws (Chaubey and Kuknor, 2024). It indicates that, by social structure, females are limited to a certain scope. Although it has been perpetually changing in most of the societies, females would not be allowed to go to school or college; they would not allow competing in leadership position; they would not allow walking independently; and they would not allow making key decisions (Kinnear, 2001). Still Men are perceived of being more superior to women when it comes to taking decisions and culturally many rituals are in a place that men are always on front to perform those rituals due the traditional culture (Gupta,2020). These kinds of boundaries create significant obstacles to females in getting leadership positions. As there are several layers of cultural boundaries and one has been accustomed to such culture, most of the women cannot dare to revolt against the established culture and come forward in society. According to Momsen (2009), as a woman gives birth a child, she is allowed to work part-time but the husband does not have such facilities which indicate that males do not have equal responsibility for his childcare. It implies that females are more responsible or committed to fulfilling household activities than males. If a female is supposed to work more in a house, she cannot compete with males to get a leadership position. Although the female participation in

the workplace has been perpetually increasing, their household responsibilities have not been decreased to that extent (Eagly and Sczesny, 2009). It is imperative to say that societal barriers cannot be changed overnight as people cannot easily give up their tradition. It can be changed slowly by increasing social awareness and making improvement in related laws.

2.7.2. Governmental Barrier

Most governments are influenced by traditional values and beliefs regarding the roles and responsibilities of females. For example, in Indonesia women role is regarded as women for the nation. They have to take care family and involve in community activities; thereby, they have to sacrifice their career opportunities (Alston, 2014). While designing any plan, the government does not give much priority to females; thereby, they can be back warded systematically and practically. The government offers up to 52 weeks as maternity leave for the women but only 4 weeks paternity leave in Indonesia (Addiat and Cassirer, 2014). It signifies more responsibilities of females for caring child. It is a kind of key barrier that deprives females of working at the office for 52 weeks which reduces her experience and confidence; so, how could she compete with a male at the same office. It means that knowingly or unknowingly government has created barriers to women for advancement in the leadership position. Different countries have their own policy regarding paternity leave. Majority of the countries either do not have such policy or have only a few weeks (Petts and Knoester, 2018).

According to Wolfson, Palumbo and Lindgren (2010), there is weak enforcement of the planning that directly affects minorities and female employees. Although the governments in different countries including India, Nepal and Indonesia make planning, there is the weakness in employment related to data collection and there is not consistently monitoring activities. It means to say that there are no effective up-lift government programs. It further arouses questions over females' capacity of being promoted in the leadership position.

2.7.3. Internal Business Barrier

In Wolfson, Palumbo and Lindgren's (2010) book it is noted that recruiting system can be one of the key barriers to for minority and women to get in the higher position. Most of the organizations promote from within. As in the organization, there are fewer numbers of females, then in case of promotion, there is a high chance of male to be promoted. If they have an equal number of males and female in the employment pool, then it would be an equal chance to be promoted female also (Thomas, 2016). But as there are a few females in the organization, they can be outnumbered by males and there is low chance for females to be promoted in leadership positions. If the higher positions are fulfilled by external sources, then there will be equal chances for both male and female to be recruited in the leadership positions. So, for women participation in higher positions, the outer recruitment system should be given focus than from internal (Jacobs, 2004).

Further, the organization might have limited human capital but it wants to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage (Jacobs, 2004). In this regard, the organization has the compulsion to offer the right job for right the employee. If the female is not as competent as male, the organization does not offer a particular position for that female. Rather it wants to find a suitable role for her (Conley and Wright, 2012). Further, Alston (2014) also says that most of the organizations do not want to offer the opportunity to women and support by offering relevant training. If there are several males and a few females working in an organization, it will be difficult for her to secure senior or executive positions.

2.7.4. Organizational Structure

Some of the organizational structures can also be barriers for women to reach in leadership positions. Such kind of barriers can be, sometimes, called as pipeline barriers. According to

Channar (2002), the lack of effective monitoring can be one of the organizational structure barriers. As the performance is not adequately monitored, then there is no value of capacity; and power comes forward. Besides, in organizations there is a kind of biased perception that male can better lead or manage an organization; thereby, females cannot be in priority for the managerial position (William and Dellinger, 2010). As the organization better evaluates and monitors the performance of both male and female, then it can understand the actual capacity. In the same way, mostly, females are placed in dead in jobs; so that, she does not have the opportunity to be promoted to a higher position (Paludi, 2012). Furthermore, there are different standards for performance evaluation for male and female. Such standards are supportive for males than female (Karsten, 2006).

Likewise, if there is a similar performance, males are preferred as they can give more time to the organization compared to females. Mostly, females are supposed to have more home responsibilities (Conley and Wright, 2012). Likewise, according to Gregory (2003) while making evaluation females' special qualities like commitment, honesty, hardworking, etc. are omitted and males' attributes such as risk-taking, quick decision making, etc. are included. Furthermore, in the organization males feel a kind of inferior to work under the female leadership (Conley and Wright, 2012). They become jealous over females; thereby, in unseen ways, they try to pull females legs from getting higher positions. It shows that a kind of male-oriented psychology also creates a kind of tough pipeline for females to be promoted in higher positions. Masculine domination fully works in organization structure and from initial placement to the evaluation process, females are treated differently which might be one of the major barriers to women for getting managerial or leadership position (Peters and Wolper, 2018).

2.8. Women Roles in the Current Economy

Females' role has been perpetually increasing to underpin economic well-being of a nation. According to Doepke and Tertilt (2019), Women's position in any society is directly co-related to the level of economic development of any nation. Women employment can have significant role to reduce household poverty hence promoting overall economic growth of a nation (Kabeer, 2021). From the consumer perspective, females have a key role in decision making related to household goods and services including buying day to day kitchen goods, clothing, cars, etc. Marti (2006) says overall, only in the household products and services, females make decisions of purchasing about 4 trillion dollars annually in product and services.

World Bank's Report (2001) highlights that the society which has gender discrimination has less rapid economic growth and has more poverty than the society which has gender equality. It has helped to empower women and equally participate them in the workforce. Now, in most of the societies, females are getting equal education and social opportunities that have contributed them to earn money. According to the World Bank (2001), if women farmers get as equal human capital and inputs as males, farming productivity can be increased by 6%-20%. It has clearly shown that females are more effective and efficient than males. According to O'Leary, Unger and Wallston (2014) women fulfil their roles and responsibilities more honestly and sincerely than men. The report published by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2012) also concludes that equal participation of both males and females in the labour force has contributed to rapid economic growth. If the country where females are not given equal opportunities in the workforce, the economic development is slow. Since women are under presented; it is costing the overall economic development. Gender inequality is costing the economy around 15% of its GDP (UN Women, 2023). It has also clarified that there is an invaluable role of females in economic development. Considering

the fact, the women involved in the workforce has been perpetually increasing all over the world.

In the report of the World Bank (2012), it has been revealed that the share of women's household economy has been increasing which implies that they have good purchasing power. Most of the household purchasing decision is made by females; so that, their decision can significantly affect the economy. On the one hand, their earning has been increasing as the number of females in the workforce has been increasing and on the other hand, their share in the household economy has been increasing. Both earning and buying decisions are imperative to develop the economy. In this current scenario, nobody can imagine economic growth without female empowerment and equal participation.

According to UN Women (2012), gender inequality can be one of the key reasons for hunger and poverty. As females are deprived of education and equal opportunity, it is impossible for rapid economic growth. In developing countries, 43% of the agriculture labour force is generated by females. Further, it mentions that if females are participated in farming, national agriculture output can be increased by 2.5% to 4%; so that, the world poverty can be reduced by 12% to 17%. It shows the important role of females in agriculture sectors to reduce poverty. It is imperative to say that female role can be equally important in different types of employment. Especially, in developing countries, they are merely limited in agriculture sectors as for example almost 70% females are working in agriculture and more than 60% females are employed in sub-Saharan Africa in agriculture but they do not have necessary capital and infrastructure for farming; so that, it has been affecting to increasing production (UN Women, 2012).

Although there is more females' involvement in agriculture, only less than 20% of women have ownership of the land. Interestingly, most of the women in Sub-Saharan Africa spend "40

billion hours a year collecting water." (UN Women, 2012) Compared to males, females spend much time in household activities; so that, they can be deprived of employment opportunity and their approach to the economy cannot be strong. Although they also have a share in the household economy, mostly they have to depend upon the males as they do not have employment opportunity.

According to OECD (2012) female education significantly contribute to higher economic growth. Due to the impact of equal education for both males and females, the economy has been increased by 50%. Still, females have not got a higher position as per their education; they are only confined to lower positions. For better economic support, they should be given equal opportunity in the higher positions in the workforce.

Gupta (2000) argues that if both males and females are engaged in the jobs, the economy can be sharply boosted but as females are confined within household activities neither the economy can be developed nor the society can be forwarded. In every sector from employment to education, both male and females should have equal participation. Although the women are increasing in the workforce for couples of decades, still there is a higher gap. According to the International Labour Organization (2014), male employment to population ratio was 72.2% whereas female employment to population ratio was only 47.1%. It shows that there is still a huge female population that has not been given the opportunity for employment.

According to the report of UN Women (2012) in most of the countries, females are paid 60% to 75% of males' wages. Which shows clear gender discrimination which has affected women earnings. Further, it is important to say that they are engaging in low productivity activities and informal sectors which make them economically dependent on males. Although females work long hours, they are not economically independent. The more they are organized and they work in formal sectors the more they can earn good money and its economic contribution can be

higher. Women working trend has been perpetually changing and they are also interested to work outside instead of merely confined in the household activities or working in low wages. According to the report by ActionAid (2015), if the women's participation and wages gap are fulfilled, their income can be increased by 76% which could be USD 17 trillion. It shows the huge potentiality of females in economic development.

2.9. Women Leadership in the Workplace in the Developed Countries

The number of female workers in the past was very low but it has been perpetually increasing every year. In the workplace, females are being as equal stakeholders as males. According to the report of the US Congress Economic Committee (2010), the women participating in the workforce has been grown by one third from 1970 to 2010. In the case of the education and healthcare sectors, it has been accounted for 77.4% of female participation. It is important to say that along with increasing females in the workforce, there is a significant increase in female higher education. In the case of the USA, females' higher education attainment percentage has increased by 20% in 2010 compared to 1970. Along with increasing females' number in higher education, their employability has also been promoted. It means to say that education has helped them to change their professions. In the past they used to be limited to the household and community activities but later on their scope has been widened. It is imperative to say that it is not only the case of the USA, but the same situation can also be found across the world. In the USA, over 51% of females are working in management and professional sectors which is one of the greatest achievements (US Congress Economic Committee, 2010). But this kind of situation cannot be experienced elsewhere although they are slowly coming to higher or professional positions (Hakim, 2004).

Currently, women are being the key engines to drive the national economy. In every nation, there is a significant portion of women involved in the workforce. According to the report of

the US Congress Economic Committee (2010) in the US, there are over half of the total women at the labour force. In the case of the UK over two-thirds of women aged 16-64 are employed (Catalyst, 2016). Even though, women participation in the workplace seems improving; this has not reflected well enough when it comes to leadership positions. Many studies reported to have higher financial performance on S&P 500 companies with more female representation in decision making than those have less women representation and yet companies on S&P 500 have only 4.4% female CEOs (Elias, 2018). However, in the case of Norway, data is very much close to 50/50 with 46.7% of female board members in the companies in 2015. Anyway, it can be claimed that except for fewer developed countries, there is a very low percentage of females in the leadership position despite many studies suggesting improvement in companies' overall performance with more female participation (Kulkarni and Mishra, 2022).

It is crucial to say that in the workforce, there is significant improvement of women involvement (Elias, 2018). The participation of female workforce can be different as per different countries. For example, in Asian countries, there is 81.7% in Nepal, 23.6% in India, 36% in Bangladesh, 23.9% in Pakistan, etc (UNDP, 2019). However, work nature and payment condition of the employment are different debatable issue. Nevertheless, this data reveals that Nepal has the highest percentage of the female workforce (Acharya, 2020). As there is a higher female workforce, it helps them to be more independent economically. Further, higher workforce participation can significantly contribute to attaining higher positions as well.

There is no doubt that women are not supposed as equal as men in the past. They were not given any political right. In the case of the US, the 19th amendment made on 26 August 1920 had given political right to vote. Although they are given the political right, they could not come into the political mainstream for a long time. Last few decades are imperative from female political participation, awareness, education, workforce, etc (Ryan, 2013). Nowadays,

females are getting more power and they are trying to be as equal as males. According to Holsinger and Jacob (2009) until and unless, there is equal participation of female in each area, the discrimination may not end. As for example if their participation is low in politics, then they cannot have the opportunity to make national laws and policies. If they are in a decision-making position, then they can represent their voice otherwise they have to rely on males who may not make laws and policies in favour to the females; so that, they can have legal boundaries to come forward and compete with males (Iwanaga, 2008).

At present, women are considered a critically essential part of the workforce as they have participated in most of the occupations. Their involvement in the workforce has been significantly increasing not only in developed countries but also in developing countries (Klasen, 2019). In 1984 there were 53.6% of women were in the labour market but this percentage has increased by 59.2% in 2008 in the US (US Congress Economic Committee, 2010). This data signifies that women are continually attracted in the labour market. The labour force participation rate of females has been increasing which can be proved by US Congress Economic Committee Report (2010). In 1984 there were only 53.6% of payroll employed women but in 2009, it is accounted for 59.2%. Similarly, the payroll females have also been increased from 44% to 49.8%. It is imperative to say that at the time of recession in industries, construction and manufacture sectors there were high demands of males; thereby, it created a higher gap between males and females' participation in the labour market. According to US Congress Economic Committee (2010) in case of non-farm payroll employment, the gap between male and female has been ended as males' employment has been decreased whereas females' employment has been increased. Similarly, according to the report of World Bank (2017), there is 39.28% women workforce in the world. Anyway, current data shows that female participation in the workforce is significant to underpin world economy.

According to the report of the Institute for Policy Report (2016) still there is very low female participation in policy-making level either it is in the parliament or government or organizations. In the US, 21% US Senate members, 19.1% US House members, 24.8% state legislators, 8% governors, 21.1% US cabinet members, 5.4% Fortune 500 CEOs, 20.2% Fortune 500 board members and 26.4% college presidents are females (Brown, 2017). This kind of data represents the actual position of females in developed countries and the same kind of situation has been seen in developing countries. Most of the high-level jobs are occupied by males and females are not given much opportunity to be promoted. "Gender stereotypes are holding women back." (Institute for Policy Report, 2016) In the US, people tend to believe that men are "agentic" which means that they are producers and the products of the social system. They tend to think that they are rulers by culture and tradition; thereby, they want to continue or follow the trend. The US people tend to think that females are "communal" which indicates nice, friendly and caring. They believe that a leadership position can be better handled by an agentic person than the communal person which means that females are not suitable for administrative or leadership position. It tries to clarify that masculinity perception has become one of the key barriers for women to get higher positions.

According to Eagly and Carli (2018) even those women equally qualified and capable as men are less likely to take leadership positions or leave early due to work/family trade-offs. Similarly, the report of The Rockefeller Foundation (2016) also found that throughout the business world, there is a lack of female representation in the leadership position. It says that only 4% of females are holding leadership positions in Fortune 500 companies which is worse than 20% in the Senate. In their research 24% say that in their companies, there is no female in a leadership position at all; 34% say that their companies encourage females to take a leadership position. Also, 9 out of 10 respondents say that due to tradition and expectation of male leadership culture are the main causes of females' lack of representation in leadership positions.

Traditionally is believed that females cannot make strong decisions; they are only good for loving and caring; so, the leadership position is not offered to the females although they qualify (Hutchison and Jankins, 2013). In the research of The Rockefeller Foundation (2016), 2 in 3 Americans say that females should start from the higher position instead of entering in the lower position and wait to be promoted in a higher position. Further 8 in 10 American women believe that as there are not more females in the leadership position, the inspiration is not there for females to take higher positions. They have a kind of psychology that females cannot lead the organization. If they had seen any female leaders, then they would be inspired and motivated but as there are no females in the leadership position, they do not make it as their dream position (Gregory, 2003). If there is any female who is in the top leadership position, people believe that she cannot lead the organization. This kind of mentality has been massively working to stop women from being promoted to higher positions in both developed and developing countries (Carreon, Cassedy and, Borman, 2013). As there is no trust, then, it can be very much difficult for women to come forward in the workplace.

Wages gap can be considered as one of the important examples of gender discrimination. According to US Congress Economic Committee (2010) although there is significant progress, still there are some challenges for women to come in higher positions. In the last few decades, the wage gap has been narrowed down but still on average full-time working women earn 80 cents while men earn 1 dollar. Such kind of wage difference can be found across the world but wages gap difference has been continuously narrowed down (Higgins, 2016). In most of the organizations, there is equal pay but, in some organizations, still there is a kind of discrimination. Similarly, Hoffman and Averett (2015) say that in most of the developing countries, female in rural areas work for wages which can be a seasonal or part-time job. The discrimination does not only exist in physical activities, but it also equally exists in skilled jobs because in some communities it is believed that females are less capable compared to males

(Klaveren and Tijdens, 2012). Due to this kind of masculine superiority complex, females are being discriminated against even though their performance is as equal as males or better.

2.10. Challenges of Women Empowerment in Developing Countries - South Asia

Empowerment is a process for personal gain and control in the life of people by the development of activities and structures, so the participation encouraged and which affect directly (Bystydzienski, 1992). Empowering women to take a role on educational leadership is widely adopted issue in the educational sector after lots of hard work it has shown some sign that women are at least beginning to cross the traditionally stiff barriers of the society (Evans, 2014).

Empowerment of women is a very rich topic used in educational leadership, which consists of educational empowerment, political empowerment, knowledge empowerment and psychological empowerment (Stromquist, 2015). However, the culture in the institutions is not as favourable as it should be in some cases. Some institutions are often promoting the culture that hurt and disempowered women such as cracking of jokes and making unpleasant remarks about them (Higgins, 2016). Women empowerment is a broad issue as it can be achieved through various aspects. Empowerment helps to change personal defeats into victories by providing tools for women to better control their life (Higgins, 2016).

Therefore, empowerment is directly linked to the excess of education; Education empowers women by giving personal targets and respect. Although, there are many scholars have produced work on empowerment it is criticized by some scholars. Empowerment is dependent on the individuals and it needs further research to have a complete understanding of the nature of empowerment (Hutchison and Jankins, 2013).

Morley and Crossousard (2014) researched women in higher education and leadership in South Asia. In their research, some key barriers to women leadership are mentioned below:

2.10.1. The Power of the Socio-culture

Although in some nations of South Asia, there are females head of the state like the president of Nepal and prime minister of Bangladesh, due to the socio-cultural perspective, females are deprived of getting leadership position (Manchanda, 2017). This kind of culture makes males always ruler and females to be always ruled (Morley and Crossousard 2014). Interestingly, the first world prime minister was Sirimavo Bandaranaike, who was from Sri Lanka in 1960 but still in South Asia, there is negative culture toward empowering and offering leadership position for a female (Haq, 2008).

2.10.2. Social Class and Caste

According to Morley and Crossousard (2014) among the females also, only the higher class and caste woman get opportunities for leadership positions. It means to say that if a female is from lower class or caste, she does not dare to be a leader because she believes that the richer or upper caste people cannot be ruled by her. Further, the so-called higher class or rich people do not want to be under any one's leadership who is poor or from a lower caste. This kind of class and caste perception has been deeply rooted in the society; thereby, it also could be one of the key barriers to pull women back from getting any leadership position (Hausmann, 2009). In the countries like Nepal and India this kind of social prejudice can be found; so that, if the woman is from lower class or caste, she does not dream to hold any leadership position (Morley and Crossousard, 2014).

2.10.3. Lack of Investment

Morley and Crossousard's (2014) report found that in South Asian countries, there are not many women empowerment programs which is due to lack of investment. The government does not invest as much as it is required to empower, train and increase women awareness. In order to build a career, there is no such structure or advice; thereby, the women cannot get leadership positions. If it is available for the required advice and career development opportunities, their number would also be increased in leadership positions. Some of the national and international organizations are working on this issue but they have limited resources and they are running some small projects that do not have much impacts on increasing women leadership (Chalise, 2017).

2.10.4. Organizational Culture

In most of the organizations in South Asian countries, there is a patriarchal culture that makes females uneasy, unfriendly and unaccommodating (Morley and Crossousard 2014). There is direct or indirect gender discrimination in the organization that creates a kind of obstacle in holding leadership or administrative position for the women. The employees are not habituated to work under women leadership; so, they do not support women rather they try to pull the legs down if there is any woman in the leadership position. According to Day (2014), it is the fundamental organizational culture in the patriarchal society. Of course, if there would be women-friendly culture, then it would make women easy to come to the leadership position in any organization. Although the situation has been perpetually changing, still the organizations prefer males in leadership positions as they do not trust over females (Day, 2014). In addition, women are experiencing gender discrimination, in most cases, from their male counterparts (Evans and Maley,2020).

2.10.5. Perceptions of Leadership

Morley and Crossousard's (2014) research found that most of the women do not like leadership position as it requires more commitments and it is a very challenging position in the increasing global competition. The women who were entered in the leadership position were happy but they are feeling a kind of stress because they do not have adequate training. Mostly, females have more household responsibility and they want part-time or less stressful position; thereby, they do not want to take responsibilities. According to Gandhi and Sen (2020) Women should be able to put their opinions and ideas freely but not able to do so due to restrictions and family responsibilities women tend to give less time to develop right networking that indirectly makes women less aware of ongoing situation of an organisation. Sekine (2017) also says that there are low numbers of female leaders which creates a kind of impression that leadership is not suitable for the females. They fear about managing home and leadership responsibility and they believe that if they have a leadership position, they cannot give time for home. This kind of perception discourages women to be a leader.

2.10.6. Recruitment and Selection

Constant under representation of women leaders compared to men in Leadership positions across many sectors and countries shows a significant gender bias in hiring and promoting leaders (Player et.al, 2019). Appointing in a leadership position is not fair or transparent in the South Asian countries as well (Morley and Crossousard, 2014). There is political, gender, economic, etc. influence; thereby, it is difficult for females to be selected in the position although she has adequate skills and abilities to handle the position (O'Connor, 2010). Further, while selecting for the leadership position, it is said that female should have much more household responsibilities that may affect in giving time and outcome of a company (Ezibilgin,

2009). Although this kind of gender discrimination is prohibited by ILO, it has been existing in practice mostly in the private sector organizations (O'Connor, 2010).

2.10.7. Family

In the South Asian countries, most of the families expect women to remain in the house and offer care services to other family members therefore women built up their leadership skills around maintaining work- life balance as more women leave their career halfway due to childcare issue and other family responsibilities compared to western countries (Bhattacharya, Mohapatra and Bhattacharya, 2018). Some of the families believe that females do not need any education. They are discriminated in education; thereby, they cannot get a leadership position (Rao, 2005). In the same way, it is imperative to say that a family does not want females to give much time outside a home. According to Chalise (2017) in the patriarchal society, if women do jobs outside the home, the family feels a loss of pride and social respect. Millions of women in south Asia are confined within household activities thereby unable to take advantage of growing labour market (Asadullah, Savoia and Sen, 2020). As a result, three time less women are holding full time jobs than men (Hafeez et al., 2020). It is believed that if the family is poor and males in the family are not capable to do any job, only then females do outside job. This kind of concept creates challenges for females to do any job and holding leadership position is out of their imagination (Ezbilgin, 2009).

2.10.8. Gender and Authority

Leadership is perceived as masculine attributes (competitive, ruthless and politically networked) in the patriarchal society; so, the women think that leadership is not a suitable position for them; it should be held by the males (Morley and Crossousard 2014). As they believe males have authority to be leaders, they cannot be motivated to take any leadership

position. In the South Asian countries, females are discriminated from getting leadership positions. In the powerful authorities, females are supposed not to work as that is not a proper job for them. This kind of gender discrimination can be one of the major barriers for women any leadership position in the South Asian countries.

2.10.9. Corruption

In South Asian countries, there is high corruption and to get a leadership position, people are doing corrupted practices. According to Kanbur, Rhee, and Zhuang (2014), the one who has power or smart in corrupted activities may get such a position. Comparatively, females do not have much political power or such corrupted mind because they are confined within the house (Ezbilgin, 2009). If the society is corrupted, there is no value of skills, abilities, educations and experiences. There will not be any fair competition rather the one who can give a bribe, he will be the leader of the organisation. In this kind of situation, females find difficult to secure leadership positions.

2.11. Women Leadership in the Education Sector in Nepal

According to Falch (2010), Nepal has a patriarchal culture that makes males superior to females. As a female is grown up in this culture, on the one hand, they do not have the courage to be a leader and on the other hand, there are lots of cultural barriers including more women roles in household activities, negative social perception about women employment, social discouragement for women leadership and many more (Chalise, 2017). In this regard, women leadership in Nepal is very low in every sector including in education.

Nepal has been following patriarchal social norms and values since its civilization where diverse female social status could be observed in different historical periods (Yadav, 2016). Mostly, females were dependent or subordinate to males and it was believed that female could

not sustain without males' protection; thereby, a widow would immolate alive on her husband's pyre which was understood as Sati practice and it was later abolished by Chandra Shamsheer in 1920 (Shehan, 2016). It depicts a precarious situation of women for a long term and there was not an issue about their participation in decision making. They used to serve merely as subordinate to males; thereby, leadership role has become irrelevant to them in the past but, at present, the situation has been rapidly changing in the wake of the feminist movement (the 1970s).

Available evidence clearly suggests, although still long way to go, Nepal has experienced a significant shift from its strict patriarchal social practice to gender equality and social inclusion due to increasing access of education, health facility, social media and awareness programmes (Sharma, 2021). The key impacts of this awareness movement were seen in Nepalese society in 1990 after the restoration of democracy. They started to involve in politics and different employment sectors coming out from household grips. NGOs and INGOs started to emerge as mushrooms for the purpose of empowering women; girls were also started to be sent school for former education, and they were allowed to work outside the home as well. It is obvious that society became a bit liberal but still the women did not get as many opportunities as they should get (Kolas, 2017). So, they continued the struggle against patriarchal tradition and through the interim constitution (2007), they became able to secure several rights like 33% reservation quota in every political leadership sector including parliament and every social service employment.

At present, the patriarchal concept has been gradually changing and women are more easily accepted in the leadership position (O'Connor, 2010). As for example, due to the reservation quotas system, in 2018 women share in parliament stands at 33.5% which is much better than

countries such as India, Bangladesh and Pakistan with women share of 11.7%, 20.3% and 20% respectively (UNDP, 2019).

In the education sectors also, more females are coming due to the reservation quota (Chalise, 2017). In the past, girls were not sent to school and if they were sent, most of them could not complete their school level education because of their responsibilities in the household activities and early marriage (Sekine, 2017). They used to do lots of work in the house; they had to give much more focus on household activities than the study. In this regard, the number of females would be very low in higher education. But now the society is being aware of female education, which is due to the effort of government, NGOs, and INGOs (Timsina, 2011). As families are being more informed; women's education is taken as an important step to grow the economy. In 1981, women literacy rate was only 9.2% compared to 31.7% of men since then changed significantly reaching 59.72% in 2018 (World Bank, 2020). Even more surprisingly literacy rate among young female aged between 15-24 is 90.88% compared to men with 94.03% (World Bank, 2020). The reports reveal that in Nepal, females' percentage are increasing in education. As they are well educated, they will have a better chance to get better positions in the education sector and able to fulfil all reservation quotas. However, in the private sectors, there is no reservation quota for females but in the civil services the quota is available for females. Quota system in civil service has massively encouraged them to join in leadership position including in the education sector (Khadka and Sunam 2018). Although women applicants in civil service have outnumbered male applicants; as per Department of Civil service commission Nepal 2018, women hold only 15% in 2010, 18% in 2015 and 23% position in 2018 (Wagle, 2019). Women participation in the civil service is increasing due to reservation quotas. According to Public service commission report (2018) total 5728 women were joined the civil service to make up the reservation quota of 33%. Females have their own reservation quota which guarantees 33% female representation. At the same time, the capable females can

fight in open competition as well. In this scenario, it is getting easier for females to gain leadership positions in the education sector in civil services.

However, even with the quota system, and with more female applicants, more males acquire jobs in the civil service than females. This is partly due to the relatively poor performance of female concerning the Public Service Commission (PSC) exam, with only 38% of females passing the test in 2016. This might relate to the lower levels of female participation in education than males, despite recent improvements. In the HEI sector, this has resulted in most leadership positions being dominated by men. Tribhuvan University is the oldest and largest public university in Nepal. Its high-level leadership positions are male dominated with five males and only one female (Tribhuvan University Website, 2018). This kind of representation can be seen in every other education leadership sector. Although there are some females in leadership positions, the number is too low.

Research has been conducted to explore the reasons behind low numbers of females in leadership in education sectors in Nepal and most of the researchers found that there is an unseen barrier (glass ceiling) that has played an imperative role for not getting females in the leadership position (Morley and Crossousard, 2014). Cultural, traditional, home responsibility, organizational structure, corruption, political influence, etc. become major challenges to come females in key authority. Mostly, the political interruption can be seen in HEI in Nepal. Women face several challenges going through selection process as it is not based on merits rather promoting elite applicants and undermining women mainly from lower casts (Dong, 2016). Also, the candidate who has a close relation to the political party might have a greater chance to be selected in the leadership position at universities. Most of the male candidates spend their time serving political parties' interests; so, males have higher chances to be selected in

leadership positions than females (Khati, 2005). This kind of trend can be found in every sector including educational leadership.

2.12. Endeavours Gender Inclusion

Gender equality has been one of the major issues in Nepal; thereby, in the recent decade, lots of improvements have been seen. There is no doubt that for a long-time woman have been suppressed by masculine culture. As a result, they are behind than males economically, culturally and politically (Pokharel, 2008).

To empower female leadership and include them in a mainstream, at the government level, so many efforts have been done. According to Chalise (2017), Nepal is the leading position to honour and follow international documents related to women equality and empowerment. It has rectified all the women related documents prepared by The International Labour Organization (ILO), The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organizations (UNESCO), etc. Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), Beijing Platform for Action (BPFA), and Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) are considered some of the imperative documents related to women equality and inclusion, which have been rectified by Nepal.

Women leadership empowerment movement in Nepal can be traced back to 1918 along with the establishment of the women's committee (Chalise, 2017). After that, females are participated in the major decision-making places but were very low in number. According to Manandhar (2020) in the Rana regime, most of ruling positions were held by the males. In Nepal, there was Sati practice, in which wife should be burnt in alive with husband's corpse. Which was abolished by the Prime Minister Chandra Shamsheer Janga Bahadur Rana on 28th June 1920. Since then, perception towards women started changing for better and women were

attempting to be included in the decision-making process at the national level. After the restoration of democracy in 1990, female awareness has significantly increased as numbers of NGOs and INGOs started to work to empower women and encourage leadership positions (Karkee, 2016).

As a result of strong women voice, in the constitution assembly (2008) females got 33% representation. But before that in the parliament, there would be less than 6% female representation. In the local level election of 1997, there were 20% of women due to reservation, but this reservation has increased to 33% now. In 2017 local level election, there were altogether 45,000 female participants and out of them, 11,630 were elected which represents 41% of totality. Those women were from different geographies and social backgrounds (UNDP, 2017).

In the same way, in the parliament also the constitution has secured women's 33% reservation quota. Furthermore, in the top positions from the local level to the national level, female's position has been secured (Constitution of Nepal 2015). As for example, in the parliament, if the speaker is male, vice speaker must be female. So, it can be said that the government has made adequate reform to encourage females and get in the leadership position in the political sector. As every party must have 33% women, they are empowering themselves and at the same time, the reservation quota has encouraged women to take the leadership positions. As there are more women leaders, it can be easy for other women to find role models.

After the restoration of democracy, numbers of NGOs were opened and INGOs were entered into Nepal. They focused their programs in the rural areas and started to empower women by giving health education, educating women rights, encouraging to do jobs, participating in organizations, giving leadership skills, and so on (Sharma and Tamang, 2016). As per the required, they are giving different types of education and the women continuously became

empowered and they started to take a leadership position (Kolas, 2017). In this regard, it can be said that there is a prominent role of such organizations to empower women and include them in the mainstream.

Not only in political sectors, but women are also being equally inclusive in the service sectors as well. From the government level, females' reservation quotas have been secured, which makes females easy to get civil service jobs. Nowadays, the females' number is increasing in higher education and they are also equally competitive as males (Hutt and Onta, 2017). If institutions compromise policies providing flexible working hours for work life balance to women that can attract more women to leadership positions (Maheswari, Nayak and Ngyyen, 2021). Furthermore, as they have reservation quota; in the coming day, women representation in the leadership position of the service sector can be increased.

2.13. Conceptual Framework

Figure 4: Conceptual Framework

(Source: Created by Author)

Although there is a persistent debate on whether leadership is born or made, most of the scholars argue that both inborn attributes and environment are equally imperative to create effective leadership in both genders. According to Kumar and Meenakshi (2009), some of the leadership attributes are inborn and impossible to teach. If an individual has inborn abilities and has a supportive environment, leadership can flourish and conversely in the absence of an appropriate environment, inborn leadership attributes may not be sufficient for leadership characteristics to develop.

Regardless of gender inborn attributes and environment are essential. According to trait theory, a leader has inborn attributes including self-confidence, honesty, integrity, cognitive ability and motivation (Ruvolo, 2004). Similarly, Great Man Theory argues that leaders are born but also require sophisticated family environment (Kouzes and Posner, 2002). Other theories like behavioural theory, participative leadership theory and situational theory challenge this and argue that leadership does not depend on birth attributes and that learning or teaching is more important (Mehrotra, 2005). These theories argue that anyone can be a leader if she/he is interested and that effective environment can allow these skills to develop.

Society cannot discriminate between the genders so, the only issue relating to women's leadership relates to the environment, where there are major differences in how males and females are treated. Aspects such as family, culture, tradition, religion, health and education play important roles in developing inner leadership attributes (Kuehler, 2015). In many South Asian countries, the dominant masculine cultures dare not challenge these perceptions and rarely go on to take leadership roles (Pokharel, 2008). Although the situation has been gradually changing, females continue to be deprived of education and opportunities.

Women face societal, governmental, internal business and organizational barriers. According to the Glass Ceiling Commission (1995), most societies want to encourage more female leadership but some societies women themselves do not take on such roles. At the governmental level, there is also a kind of biased practice with males normally in key positions making national laws and policies that discriminate against females (Burns, 2012). Organizations also frequently promote people from within. If more males working in the organization, then there are fewer chances for women to be promoted. If there is a voting system, and males are in the majority, males will easily reach leadership positions and this acts as an internal barrier for women (Glass Ceiling Commission Report, 1995). According to Channer (2002), there is a lack of effective performance monitoring systems and the biased perception that males are favoured for leadership positions - plays an important part in this continuing discrimination (William and Dellinger, 2010). Another aspect of this bias is a common belief that females cannot give much time to the organization as they have family responsibilities (ILO, 2003). Women are also characterised as committed, honest and hard-working (Nganga, 2011) whereas males are seen as risk-takers, decision-makers and confident attributes that organizations often find suitable for leadership roles (Rhee and Sigler, 2015). Additionally, some male employees do not want to work under female leadership.

To empower women and secure leadership positions in different sectors, lots of efforts have been done from private as well as government sides in Nepal. The government has launched several empowerment programs in both rural and urban areas. It has given higher priority to women's education. To encourage females to go to school, it has been offering free education as well as some other incentives like lunch and stationery goods (Timsina, 2011). In the same way, to promote female leadership, it has been managing some reservation quota for the females in every public sector including in political leadership. Similarly, numbers of NGOs and INGOs are perpetually working towards increasing female leadership in every sector. Due

to these efforts, women leadership has been increasing but there are key challenges that continue to impede the empowerment of women.

Although there are lots of efforts from private and government side to empower women, there are still only a few women in leadership positions. Indeed, the empowerment program has not been as effective as it should be because of various hindrances. For example, the power of the socio-culture is strong and cannot be changed overnight. The impact of masculine culture means that many Nepalese women do not want to be a leader and suppose that leadership is only suitable for males (Pokharel, 2008). Organizational culture, perception of leadership, policy of recruitment and selection are all challenges to the empowerment of women in Nepal (Timsina, 2011). Due to these facts still there is a very low number of women leaderships in every sector including higher education.

The conceptual framework is closely related to the research questions: The first question (What are women's experiences of women leadership in HE in Nepal) is represented by the top second right box in the figure. The second question (What are women's perceptions of gender equality in HE leadership) is addressed by the last left box. The third question (What are the main factors/barriers that prevent women from taking leadership role) is associated with the third right box whereas the final question (What can be done to increase women leadership in HE) is related to the third left box.

2.14. Conclusion

This chapter has demonstrated that many long-standing issues prevent women from being equally represented in leadership positions around the world. This study looks at women in Nepal in the education sector. From the various literature it is clear that although women were confined within household responsibilities and economically dependent on males for a long-

term, this situation has been gradually changing. In this chapter also presented various literature, theories in relation to the study and the conceptual framework that provides a clear framework for the research process. The next chapter, Research Methodology, will be presented with relevant methods and methodology that guides the research.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1. Introduction

A research methodology is defined as a framework that systematically and scientifically guides the research process to accomplish research aims and objectives (Kothari, 2009). This research aims to uncover the underlying experiences that women in leadership in higher education institutes of Nepal have experienced in order to investigate the challenges, and perceptions on gender equality regarding women's underrepresentation in leadership positions within Higher Education of Nepal. How a researcher assumes about the world helps to adopt a particular type of research methodology (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). It means, how a researcher views the world as part of the research philosophy leads to adopting a particular type of research methodology. In this chapter, the philosophical stance chosen that led to select particular ontological perspective, research approach and method selected are discussed. In this chapter, the data collection procedures, the rationale for the use of the data collection methods, data analysis process, ethical issues and limitations of the research are also explained. This research is designed to address the following research questions:

RQ1. What are women's experiences about women leadership in HE in Nepal?

RQ2. What are the women's perceptions of gender equality in HE leadership?

RQ3. What are the main factors/barriers that prevent women from taking leadership roles?

RQ4. What can be done to increase women leadership in HE?

3.2. Philosophical Issues

According to Kothari (2009) research philosophy contributes to establishing uniformity of knowledge throughout the research. According to Howell (2012), the different types of research philosophies all shape how research is undertaken. There are several variants of research philosophies such as positivism, realism, objectivism, interpretivism, subjectivism, pragmatism, functionalism, interpretive, radical humanist and radical structuralism (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). It is significant to explore philosophical issues while specifying the research methodology that going to be adopted for particular research (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Lowe, 2002). As suggested by Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2007) four sets of assumptions that underpin the issue of a social world that need to take into consideration while developing the research methodology. Which are epistemological related, ontological related, human nature related and methodological related. Therefore, this chapter discusses the research philosophies in terms of epistemology, ontology, research approach and research methods in the following sections.

3.2.2. Ontology (Exploring Nature of Reality)

Ontology deals with the nature of reality. Ontological beliefs are categorised as subjectivist and objectivist ontology (Bryan, 2016). This research has adopted the belief of subjective ontology.

Subjectivist ontology believes that social phenomena are constructed by perceptions and consequent actions of social actors (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). It also argues that depersonalization of an author does not construct any truth (Kothari, 2009). It means that researcher knowledge, feeling and experience should be equally given place in the data analysis process. And it is not possible to fully detach an author's perception from the process of data analysis. Similarly, this ontology also believes that truth can be established through inter-

subjectivity. According to Scott and Morrison (2007) this kind of subjective concept has been acclimatized by interpretivism but add that merely an author's perception or bias cannot be enough to determine the truth as it cannot ensure validity and reliability; thereby, it is imperative to support the personal argument with logic, reason, theory, and model.

This philosophy is criticised in the sense that it can be biased due to subjective data collection and interpretation. According to Willis (2007), as the researcher's perception is given space, the research cannot be scientific and the conclusion cannot be valid. This kind of strong criticism is supported by positivists like Stephen Hawking (1942-2018) who argue that if the author's personal feeling or experience is allowed in the research, the findings can be less credible and the constructed truth can be less generalisable. In this regard, they stress on avoiding any influence of the researcher in both data collection and analysis process.

Denscombe (2009) says that objectivism requires a simple research issue but, in this study, it is not straightforward and requires subjective information and their interpretation based on context and relevant theories. To understand the experiences and challenges of women leaders in the higher education of Nepal, it is imperative to highlight the particular context and accommodate the feelings, experiences, and emotions of sample respondents. Based on the theory or approach that is used to interpret the data, there will be multiple meanings of this research.

Objectivism ontological position is also not suitable because it fully ignores personal feelings and attitudes as it regards truth exists beyond the human mind (Bernstein, 2008). Further, it uses human senses to collect objective information but in order to explore the feelings and experiences of women leadership in Nepal, subjective information is required as the theories are different, the truths can be varying but objectivism does not accept it. It regards single and ultimate truth of the information, but it is not possible to apply in reality because the human

mind is necessary to evaluate the data and every mind-set is based on culture, knowledge, and understanding. In this sense, the objective ontological stance cannot be applied to investigate the experience and challenges of women leadership in Nepal. Adopting subjective ontology means participants' feelings and experiences are appreciated as researchable data and interpreted in the study (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007) and participants are recognized as being part of the study rather than separate from the topic of the research. In another word, Subjective ontological stance is required when dealing with complex nature of human being and objectivism cannot bring out every element of complex human beings. Thus, after evaluating all of the relevant ontological modes, the researcher has selected subjectivism ontological position.

3.3. Research Methods

There are two research methods which are widely used in management and research. These are qualitative and quantitative research methods. These two research methods are differentiated due to their data collection techniques and analysis procedures (Sander, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). Since both research methods have own choice and characteristics; it is significant to choose the appropriate method depending on the research requirements.

3.2.1. Epistemology (Exploring Knowledge)

Epistemology addresses knowledge in discipline that is under investigation (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). It is concerned with questioning the sources of beliefs that form knowledge. In other words, it explores the nature of knowledge. Based on the philosophical view epistemology is categorised by realism, positivism and interpretivism (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). However, Positivism and interpretivism are two widely used philosophies. For this research, interpretivism epistemology is adopted.

Interpretivism advocates and emphasises that it is crucial for the researcher while conducting the research, to understand the differences between people and objects (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). Interpretivism research philosophy argues that subjective data can be collected by using human senses but there are multiple truths as truths vary as per the theory or model that is used to interpret the collected data. This research philosophy was developed in response to the single and ultimate truth of positivism research philosophy and it argues that truth is not objective but can be subjective and constructed by culture, language, social norms, religion and many more (Yin, 2013). This Epistemology believes in gathering data by using observation, focus groups and interviews and it can be highly suitable for any subjective research where different perspectives can be found (Kothari, 2009).

Interpretivism philosophy is highly applicable for this research because to collect information related to feelings, emotions and experiences of women leaders in higher education in Nepal, qualitative data is required. This research adopts an interview data collection instrument which is justified by this philosophy. It is conducted in the context of Nepal and relevant theories should be applied to interpret the data. Also, Interpretivism helps to control research bias by helping a researcher to put his/ her own beliefs of the realities aside and interpret through the viewpoint of the participants (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007). Which is emphasized by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016) saying the challenge for the researcher is to go into the social world and understand the world from participants' point of view. Thus, the interpretive perspective is highly appropriate to research on human perceptions and experiences within complex and unique social settings (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023).

In contrast, positivist epistemology cannot be suitable for this research because it believes in the objective reality of the phenomena and usages deductive research approach and quantitative research method. Similarly, realism is also not applicable as the data are collected using

interview data collection instrument by which the respondents' feeling, emotion and experience can be easily gathered. The collected data are not evaluated using the particular context because this research is not limited within a particular context but according to Rescher (2005), it is most applicable to evaluate particular context. Rather it uses relevant theoretical information; thereby, it is imperative to say that this epistemological stance does not apply to this research.

To address the research problem, qualitative data related to experiences and challenges of women leaders should be interpreted using thematic analysis, therefore, interpretivism research philosophy is highly applicable. Therefore, interpretivism epistemology is adopted for the research. While selecting this philosophy, the researcher reviewed all other philosophies, but they were found to be irrelevant.

3.3.1. Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methods

Mostly quantitative research method starts with a statement of the problem and before coming to conclusion, hypotheses are created and tested. In quantitative research findings are tested with hypothesis so the results can be either accepted or rejected (Cresswell, 2003). Quantitative research usages numerical numbers and needs huge data collection using techniques such as survey, interviews and questioners.

Qualitative research method, unlike quantitative, gives less focus on numerical data rather it is used to investigate human-related issues; that is almost impossible to addressed using numbers. Qualitative research is quite popular to study human's feelings and emotion that quantitative research is unable to do. Qualitative research assumes that "meaning is embedded in people's experiences" (Merriam, 2001). Experiences, feelings and perceptions can only be interpreted through the study that adopts a qualitative approach. Qualitative research is concerns more on addressing research questions and understand the issue rather than validating the result (Cresswell, 2003). Thus, the finding of the research is not predetermined and mostly later

interpreted. The qualitative research method is effective to address the issues related to culture, feelings, opinions, behaviours, values and experiences (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). In a qualitative research method, collected data are explained, interpreted and described using inductive reasoning (Creswell, 2003). Qualitative research is conducted in various ways – case study, content analysis, ethnography, grounded theory and phenomenology (Leedy and Ormrod 2001).

This research aims to investigate the experiences and challenges of women leaders in higher education in the context of Nepal it needs a data which is qualitative in nature and any numerical data cannot adequately address the research issue. To address the research questions, it needs the subjective data. This research is more about human feelings, experiences and perceptions which cannot address using quantitative methods as this method treat people as object and given no value of human sentiments. Therefore, the researcher has selected qualitative methods for data collection. Also, using the qualitative method allows asking open-ended questions and probe as required to get deeper data. Therefore, it is clear and justifiable to use the qualitative research method for the study.

From the discussion above it is obvious that the research usages subjectivist ontology, interpretive epistemology, inductive research approach and qualitative research methods have been adopted.

3.4. Research Approach

According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2023), the research approach refers to the process of analysing information to come to the conclusion. There are two variants of research approach: inductive and deducting reasoning.

Inductive reasoning develops a generalisable theory by evaluating particular information. It means to say that this approach moves from particular to general where it observes information, tests them and develops a theory. Mostly, it is used in order to investigate the complex research issue where the pattern of the information is identified, and a conclusion is derived (Kothari, 2009). It can be the most suitable reasoning in the sense that it thoroughly investigates the information using relevant theories, models, arguments, and logic.

In this method, no hypothesis is created because it does not test any particular information using generalisable theory rather it develops a new theory or logic. This method is guided by research aims, objectives and research questions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). The pattern that it follows is shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Inductive Reasoning Process

(Source: Created by Author)

Inductive reasoning is the most suitable approach to investigate the experiences and challenges of women leaders in higher education institutes of Nepal. This research requires subjective information and qualitative data analysis process to minutely evaluate the underlying pattern and develop a new concept or theory instead of merely testing some facts.

Deductive reasoning is opposite to inductive reasoning as it begins from the theory or particular method and ends with testing the particular fact. In other words, it moves from general to

particular. Before gathering the information, it develops a particular hypothesis which is tested using information. In the end, the hypothesis may be accepted or rejected (Bryman and Bell, 2015). By using general fact, it derives a specific conclusion. According to Kothari (2009), this reasoning cannot be applicable if the research issue is complicated. Further, it cannot be used in qualitative research where information requires to be minutely assessed. It is mostly used in quantitative research where objective data from a big sample can be collected to test a hypothesis using statistical data analysis method (Saunders, Lewis and Thronhill, 2023). This reasoning follows the following pattern:

Figure 6: Deductive Reasoning Pattern

(Source: Created by Author)

In the case of this research, the issue is complicated and it tries to discover new fact instead of testing the particular premise based on the established theory. Here, the research proceeds from the particular fact and fulfil research objectives. In order to find experiences and challenges of women leadership, it requires subjective information and they should be minutely assessed but deductive reasoning is not appropriate to assess subjective information. Further, it cannot find the underlying pattern of the data and it is impossible to identify the current experiences and challenges of women leadership. In this sense, deductive reasoning cannot be applied to this research.

3.5. Research Strategy

A research strategy is a method that is used to collect and analyse information. Based on the nature of the research issue, the strategy might be different. There are several types of research strategies such as case study, survey strategy, grounded strategy, archival strategy, ethnography strategy, phenomenology and experiment strategy (Kothari, 2009). This research has used phenomenological strategy as this belongs to qualitative research method, subjective research philosophy and inductive approach.

Using this approach helps to understand experiences from the point of view of participants (Leedy and Ormrod, 2001). The phenomenological strategy helps to address questions related to participants' experience regarding certain situations or events. Furthermore, this strategy leads to identifying common themes from the experience of participants. However, this strategy is criticised of having some influence of researcher while interpreting results. So, it is crucial to minimise those influences. Therefore, it is explained below sections how the researcher has tried to minimise his influence while analysing the data.

3.6. Research Choice and Time Horizon

Research choice refers to the research type that is determined based on the data being used in the research. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2023) say that based on the information, the research can be divided into three categories such as mixed research choice, the mono research choice and multi-research choice. In the case of this research, mono research choice is applicable because qualitative information can adequately address the research problems. Further, it is cost-effective, quicker and easier; thereby, mono research has been selected.

The qualitative information about experiences and challenges of women leaders in higher education institutions in Nepal can be adequate to accomplish research aims and objectives. If a single research type is adequate, it is not necessary to use a mixed research choice and make the research complicated and vague (Bryman, 2016). The qualitative information can be collected and they are interpreted to investigate the experiences and challenges of women leaders in higher education institutes in Nepal. In this regard, there is no issue of applying multi-research choice.

Time horizon covers the time period that is considered while collecting information. Some of the researches are limited within a particular time duration whereas others do not have any such limitation. By time horizon, there are two categories such as cross-sectional time horizon and longitudinal time horizon (Saunders, Lewis and Thronhill, 2023).

In cross-sectional time horizon research, the researcher is limited to use the information of the given time period (Kothari, 2009). In this research, the cross-sectional time horizon is not used because the research issue is not an event - it is related to the history of women leadership in the context of Nepal. It requires information from the past to present; thereby, cross-sectional time horizon cannot effectively address research aims and objectives.

Whereas longitudinal time horizon does not have any time boundary (Sekaran, 2000). This can be equally applicable in both qualitative and quantitative types of researches (Vollmer, 2014). Although it has several benefits, it is not blameless; it is blamed as time-consuming, costly, complicated to use and not applicable in short research work (Saldana, 2003).

In this research, longitudinal time horizon has been used because it contributes to collect women leadership's experiences of any time frame (it could help them to explain their experience since they have joined at the position without limiting to particular year). It contributes to collect a holistic picture of the experiences and challenges of women leaders in

the higher education sector in Nepal. Without a wider range of data from past to present, the research problem cannot be solved as the research issue is broad and it has related to historical time to present time; thereby, the researcher has selected this time horizon.

3.6. Data Collection

According to Kothari (2009) data is the information about a particular issue or object and in the research, it is considered as the vital part because the conclusion is derived based on the collected information. If the data are not fair or reliable, the conclusion cannot be valid and generalisable. In this regard, the researchers give much more focus on collecting authentic and bias-less information. Data can be divided into two types: primary and secondary.

3.6.1. Primary Data

Primary data is the first-hand information that is directly collected by the researcher from the field. It can be up-to-date and the researcher can collect the most suitable information to accomplish her/his research (Kothari, 2009). But it can be a costly and time-consuming type of information in the sense that the researcher has to collect the fresh data by herself/himself (Hair, 2015).

In the context of this research, it is primary research where researcher has collected qualitative information from 20 respondents who are in the leadership position in higher education institutes in Nepal. There are numbers of primary data collection instrument such as focus group, interview, questionnaire, observation, case study and scientific experiment but in this research, the author uses interview data collection instrument.

Interview is a key data collection instrument in which the researcher asks questions and the respondent answers as per her/his knowledge and experience (Kothari, 2009). Mainly, the

questions are open-ended in which the respondents are free to express their own views and experiences. According to Saunders, Lewis and Thronhill (2016), the questions are easy to develop but the answering can take a long time because WH questions demand long answers or detailed of the subject matter. In this instrument, the respondents can be influenced by the researcher; thereby, the collected data can be biased which affects the conclusion. In the same way, although it collects detailed information, it is a costly, time-consuming and difficult instrument (Skinner, 2013). By structure, it can be divided into three types: structured, semi-structured and unstructured (Saunders, Lewis and Thronhill, 2023).

Structured Interview: This kind of interview has already pre-planned questions, time, venue, recording system, etc. A researcher does not have any autonomy to make any changes; her/his role is only to ask questions and record the answers. It does not allow the researcher to do cross questions even the data are not clear (Kothari, 2009). Due to this strict nature, sometimes, it cannot collect vivid and intensive data; thereby, this research does not use a structured interview.

Unstructured Interview: Just opposite to structured interview, there is nothing pre-planned. A researcher suddenly meets the respondent and the interview takes place. It may not have a good recording system and if the researcher is not an expert on the subject matter, it is impossible to collect relevant data. Further, sometimes unnecessary data can be collected and necessary data can be missed (Bailey, 2008). Due to this type of demerit, this research does not use the unstructured interviews.

Semi-structured Interview: It is fully pre-planned but it allows autonomy to the researcher. Due to pre-planning, the questions are relevant, the recording system is standard, time is fixed, etc. In order to collect deeper and vivid data, the author can make cross questions or make any required changes (Mitchell and Jolley, 2009). These kinds of merits contribute to collect clear

and deeper data; thereby, this research has used semi-structured interview data collection instrument.

By the means, interviews can be divided into two types - face to face and telephone (Kothari, 2009). In face to face interview, both interviewer and interviewee must physically meet each other; thereby, it can be time-consuming and costly. But, as they are face to face, the interviewer can observe body language or gesture of the interviewee that contributes to collect more accurate and actual data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). But a telephone interview is taken through the means of a telephone in which the researcher does not need to physically meet the interviewee (Kothari, 2009). It is cost-effective and it can collect data from any corner of the world in a short time period but it does not allow an opportunity to observe the body language of the interviewees. In this research, the researcher has used face to face interview to collect more accurate data. The researcher has considered several other instruments before selecting interview data collection instrument- but found less appropriate to the research.

For example, focus group data collection instrument is not suitable to this research because each woman leader in higher education institute in Nepal is busy in her own duty and responsibility; thereby, to gather them in particular place and time cannot be possible. In the same way, the research requires responses of at least 20 participants but focus group uses the maximum of 12 respondents. In the focus group, every respondent may not be equally motivated and participated in a discussion. If there is no equal participation, the collected data cannot represent the actual information of the group. Considering these limitations, this research has not used this instrument. In the same way, the questionnaire is also not suitable because this is qualitative research in which subjective information of top position women in higher education institution in Nepal is required. In order to collect their experiences and

challenges, the objective questions are not suitable. Although the questionnaire can be used to collect qualitative information, compared to the questionnaire, it is less practical and effective; thereby, this research does not use questionnaire data collection instrument. Similarly, in this research, observation data collection instrument is not applicable because experiences and challenges of women leaders cannot be observed. Further, it collects biased information that makes the research less reliable. Also, it is time-consuming and costly as well. Likewise, in case of this research, case study data collection instrument is not applicable because by evaluating few cases may create difficult to find out generalisable experiences and challenges of women leaders in higher education institution in Nepal. They should be asked related questions; thereby, the necessary data can be collected. In this matter, a case study cannot cover sufficient information that is required to achieve the aim and objectives of the research. In the same way, exploring primary cases can be difficult in social science research issues. Likewise, the scientific experiment is also not suitable because the issue is related to social science instead of natural science. In the same way, the required data are not possible to collect by using human senses; experience and challenges of women leaders cannot be collected without asking them subjective questions. Furthermore, the collected data cannot be experimented in a scientific laboratory; thereby, this data collection instrument is not applicable to this research. For this research all the interviews conducted were face to face. It is considered to be best method to investigate the issues around life experience and it is still widely used in the qualitative method.

3.6.1.2. Face to face interview

To understand experiences and views of the world around us of others through verbal communication mainly face to face is fundamental part of social life (Serry and Liamputtong, 2017). Despite the advancement of technology for online interviews, face to face interview is still one of the highly used methods to collect the primary data, mainly for qualitative research

(Saunders, Lewis and Thronhill, 2023). Face to face Interview is considered to be the useful way of learning and understanding the world of others and the qualitative interview help to seek central themes around the experience and life of interviewees (Qu and Dumay, 2011). To drill down on a particular topic, schedule and unscheduled probe questions are asked (Qu and Dummay, 2011). According to Saunder, Lewis and Thornhill (2023) face to face interview help researchers to collect rich data and free of bias as interviewee can express freely and interviewer can be more aware of tone, body language thereby build rapport. To achieve research, aim and objectives of the research in-depth qualitative data is required and it is face to face interviews that can facilitate to collect quality data. Therefore, in this research all the interviews conducted were face to face and were in semi-structured format. The researcher has to travel to Nepal from the UK for this purpose; although, it costs more money and consumes more times as well. In Nepal, researcher has to visit different 20 respondents in different locations. Anyway, by face-to-face interviews means the researcher was able to create a more informal environment and the respondents can be more open or frank to answer the questions. To avoid personal influence, the researcher tried to play only the role of a mediator who asks pre-planned questions and sometimes does probing questions being completely neutral over the information.

3.6.1.2. Language used in interviews

The nature of the study demands depth and clear expression of the world around participants as it designed to find out women's experiences on leadership positions in higher education institutions. For this reason, women participants need to feel comfortable and that is can only be achieved if interviews are conducted in their own mother tongue (language). Therefore, all the interviews except one was conducted in Nepali language. Most of interviewees were asked the language they prefer to be interviewed before participations. It was necessary steps to take

the interviews in Nepali language as participants might express themselves not only words but also feeling and emotions without any hesitation due to language barriers. There are many literatures around translation process and its trustworthiness of the findings when interviews are conducted in different language. Quality translation is key part of the research as poorly translated data could change what themes emerge from the data, thus threatening the credibility of the research (Adamson and Donovan, 2002).

At the same time, in qualitative research, researchers' ability to develop trust and rapport with interviewees is vital to gain in-depth data (Bryen, 2012). This is achieved due to communication and language skills of both interviewee and interviewer and only possible if both have same mother tongue. For these many reasons all the interviews except one was conducted in Nepali language. Importantly, translating the interview in Nepali language and then translating in English would have been time consuming therefore it was translated straight to English as all interviews were recorded and stored and note was taken during every interview. Also, after translation completed most of the participants were sent the transcribed copy to check their interviews data. I (researcher) do have a good command in English language and at the same time as Nepali language being my mother tongue I have a good command in that language too. All the interviews were translated by the researcher (me) therefore there was minimum chance of losing the data throughout the translation process.

3.6.2. Secondary Data

Secondary data indicates the information that is already used by the previous researchers to accomplish their research objectives. According to Hair (2015), these can be both qualitative and quantitative. The sources of these data can be library and internet. As these data can be

collected from the table, they are called table data as well. The researcher does not need to go in the field or contact any sample respondents. Further, there might be lots of secondary data but every data may not be relevant and some of them might be outdated. Although they are efficient, easier and quicker to be collected, they do not cover recent changes and selecting the most suitable data can be a challenging job (Kothari, 2009).

This research uses secondary data to underpin the primary data. In the literature review, it has discussed some theories and other information which will be used to support and increase the validity of the primary data. Leadership styles, women leadership situation in developed and developing countries and leadership barriers are critically reviewed, and they can be used as the secondary data in the discussion chapter (Chapter 5). While using secondary data, both qualitative and quantitative data can be used as per required. It does not fully depend on secondary data but some literature can be used while interpreting primary data.

3.7. Interview Questions and formulation

3.7.1. Interview questions formulation

To collect the most suitable data, the questions have been pre-planned before conducting interview. Same questions have been asked to every respondent but in order to get deeper and clearer answers the author asks some probe questions as per required. The researcher has determined key themes of the research based on research aims and objectives to develop the questions. As the key themes are identified, it ensures that the collected data can be relevant to the research. The researcher has determined following eight key themes of the study; under which relevant question(s) has been formulated and explained reasons behind asking those questions in the table below.

Table 2: Themes and related interview questions

Themes	Interview questions	Reasons for asking the questions
Leadership Experience	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How do you describe your experience as a woman leader working here? 2. What made you decide to embark on this leadership position? 	<p>In today's society stereotype and gender bias are universal issues despite feminist approach to leadership holding many helpful characteristics in today's leadership (Fauzi, et al, 2024). It is clear from many studies and literature that it not always easy for women to taking leadership positions especially in developing countries (Maheshwari, Nayak and Ngyyen, 2021). Therefore, to address the first theme 'Leadership experience, of women two questions have been formulated to understand their experience as a women leader and the fact that contributed her to select the leadership position. These questions are good enough to get some knowledge about their overall experience of journey on their leadership career.</p>

<p>Patriarchal Culture and Perceptions</p>	<p>3. How do you find males' perception over female leadership?</p> <p>4. How has the patriarchal culture been affecting female to hold the leadership position?</p>	<p>Lower number of women in almost every organisation in higher education highlight that there is still domination of masculine leadership and has perceived male being superior to lead than female (Peterson, 2019). Second theme is about perception of women leadership in the society and effect of patriarchal culture. Different societies may have different types of perception over women leadership which can be experienced as a women leader. To collect this information, two questions have been formulated and they try to understand male perception and the impact of patriarchal culture over women leadership.</p>
<p>Women Education and Ability</p>	<p>5. Do you think females are getting equal education as males? Or there is some kind of discrimination?</p> <p>6. What do you think about women ability to</p>	<p>Many studies show that Despite leadership positions being dominated by male both male and female poses equal effectiveness when it comes to leadership position (Farhan, 2022). To grasp depth understanding on the issue of ability and education issue two</p>

	<p>lead the team? Do you think it is different from men or do you think women are more capable?</p>	<p>questions were formulated to cover the theme 'women education and ability. Again, women education and ability in which information about equal education between male and female, and women capability to lead team are the major issues raised.</p>
<p>Family Restrictions</p>	<p>7. What is your family response regarding this position? Do they support you?</p> <p>8. How do you manage both job and home responsibilities?</p>	<p>Especially in Asia women are expected to sacrifice their career and progression to take up for family and home responsibilities and not trusted to take crucial leadership positions (Maheswari, et al. 2021). Therefore, to uncover the issue in depth the fourth theme family restrictions is created and under this theme there are two questions that try to find the response of the family and her responsibility in the family.</p>
<p>Organizational Barriers</p>	<p>9. What is the recruitment and selection process of this institution? Is there any discrimination for</p>	<p>Due to many organisation culture and its setting, invisible behavioural and attitudinal barriers are being created which is making female more unsecure</p>

	<p>female? Did you find any difficulties to be recruited as being a female?</p> <p>10. How does this institute treat for male and female while promoting in the leadership position? Any Discrimination?</p> <p>11. Do you find any discrimination in payment between male and female in this institution?</p> <p>12. How is the working culture of this institution? Is it suitable for female leadership or patriarchal culture has made female leadership difficult to fulfil job responsibilities?</p>	<p>and going through emotional distress over time (Ely and Rhode,2010).</p> <p>Despite having many changes in policies in organisational level, discrimination and inequality issues still occur (Ardoin, et al. 2019)</p> <p>Likewise, Imminent gender imbalance in type of work is creating differences in wages and salaries among men and women (Larraz,et al, 2019).</p> <p>Women number in leadership in HE is still low despite having higher enrolment in higher education studies (Peterson, 2019). Since organisational policies, environment and its practices plays vital role for making working experience better (Cameron, 2017). To research in depth on the issue the fifth theme organizational barriers will play a vital role. Under this theme there are four questions related to recruitment and selection, promotion, payment and working culture.</p>
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<p>Government Support</p>	<p>13. What do you think about government support to encourage women to take leadership positions?</p>	<p>As pointed out by many empirical studies that government policies and support have significant effect on women participation and performance on any organisation. In order to find out about government support on encouraging women to improve and take leadership positions one direct question is asked and probe questions are asked if necessary.</p>
<p>Gender Discrimination</p>	<p>14. What are the major challenges that particularly the female leadership has to face in course fulfilling their roles and responsibilities?</p>	<p>Women are under-represented in most of the leadership positions, and they have to encounter many challenges (barriers) such as lack of support from family, organisation and government, various direct and indirect discriminations, stereotypical misconception about their ability to climb the ladder of leadership positions (Byrd, 2009). Although, if there are any discrimination issues in organisations many questions asked under ‘organizational barriers’ indirectly help to get the information out but still to</p>

		<p>cross clarify and get in-depth data under this theme called discrimination one questions is asked to get overall view on challenges and discriminations while fulfilling their responsibilities.</p>
<p>Empowerment situation</p>	<p>15. What might be the key reasons behind a low number of women leaders in higher education institutions?</p> <p>16. In your opinion, how could women's numbers be increased in leadership positions?</p>	<p>Women poses specific talent and tend be more resilient for this reason they have proven their significance in higher educational institution (European commission, 2018)</p> <p>Women have many qualities that is need of today's world in leadership and they are suggested to established transformational leadership style that can help to increase impact on the performance and thereby achieving success in workplace and it could be one way to fight gender equality issues (Bin Bakr and Alfayez, 2021).</p> <p>Higer education institutions should empower women to become role model by being exemplary leaders (Gorondutse, et al. 2019). Likewise,</p>

		<p>women should be supported by flexible working hours and policies to promote work life balance (Maheswari et al. 2021). It is not surprising to know that women tend to be equally qualified and capable to lead the organisation but still under-represented (Maheshwari, et at. 2021).</p> <p>It is imperative to address the issue therefore the final theme is Empowerment situation and under which there are two questions asked related to respondents' opinion what the key issue women are facing on their leadership journey and how can numbers of females leaders be increased in leadership position.</p>
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(Created by the Author)

3.7.2. Interview questions

Based on the research questions and literature review, 16 interview questions have been developed (Table 2).

Table 3: Questionnaire Set

S.N.	Questions	References
	Leadership Experience	
1.	How do you describe your experience as a woman leader working here?	Sandberg (2015)
2.	What made you decide to embark on this leadership position?	Pinckney and Stevens (2018)
	Patriarchal Culture and Perceptions	
3.	How do you find males' perception over female leadership?	Sandberg (2015)
4.	How has the patriarchal culture been affecting female to hold the leadership position?	House, Hanges and Javidan (2004)
	Women Education and Ability	
5.	Do you think females are getting equal education as males? Or there is some kind of discrimination?	Klein, Richardson and Grayson (2014)
6.	What do you think about women ability to lead the team? Do you think it is different from men or do you think women are more capable?	Rose (2012)

	Family Restrictions	
7.	What is your family response regarding this position? Do they support you?	Daniell and Hamilton (2010)
8.	How do you manage both job and home responsibilities?	David and Woodward (2005)
	Organisational Barriers	
9.	What is the recruitment and selection process of this institution? Is there any discrimination for female? Did you find any difficulties to be recruited as being a female?	Pinckney and Stevens (2018)
10.	How does this institute treat for male and female while promoting in the leadership position? Any discrimination?	House, Hanges and Javidan (2004)
11.	Do you find any discrimination in payment between male and female in this institution?	House, Hanges and Javidan (2004)
12.	How is the working culture of this institution? Is it suitable for female leadership or patriarchal culture	Donald (2015)

	has made female leadership difficult to fulfil job responsibilities?	
	Government Support	
13.	What do you think about government support to encourage women to take leadership positions?	Donald (2015)
	Gender Discrimination	
14.	What are the major challenges that particularly the female leadership has to face in course fulfilling their roles and responsibilities?	Gaag (2014)
	Empowerment Situation	
15.	What might be the key reasons behind a low number of women leaders in higher education institutions?	Daniell and Hamilton (2010)
16.	In your opinion, how could women's numbers be increased in leadership positions?	Eagley and Sczesny (2009)

(Source: Created by Author)

In the above table, the questions are divided into 8 categories where the first category has two questions which are related to women experience as a leader. These questions try to know women leadership experience in HE in Nepal and their experience in getting leadership opportunity. Similarly, the second category has also two questions which are related to the perception of women leadership in society. Basically, male perception over female leadership and the patriarchal culture's impacts are explored by these questions. In the same way, the third category has another two questions which are related to women education and ability. They attempted to find out whether there is gender discrimination in education in Nepal or not and whether women have the ability to lead a team or not. Likewise, the fourth category also includes two questions and they are related to family restrictions women have to face in their leadership journey. They try to identify to what extent the family has been supporting female to continue leadership position and helping in household activities. Similarly, the fourth category has four questions which are related to barriers in organizational level. These questions attempt to know about recruitment and selection process, promotion, payment, and working culture of different HE organizations in which the respondents are working in leadership positions at present. Next, there is a single question in the fifth category that tries to find out government support on women to increase participation in leadership positions in HE. Then, another single question is in the sixth category that is developed to know female leaders' perception regarding gender discrimination women are facing while fulfilling their roles and responsibilities. Furthermore, the final category has two questions which are related to female empowerment situation. They try get data on what could be possible reasons behind having low numbers of female leaders and solutions suggested from participants experience and point views to increase the numbers of female leaders within the HE.

3.8. Research Sampling

3.8.1. Sampling technique

Research sample refers to choosing some representatives from the totality. The population might be huge which cannot be used in the research from time, cost and uses point of view. In these regards, some sample representatives have to be selected but they should represent the key attributes of the total population (Bryman and Bell, 2007). In order to effectively select the sample representatives, there are some sampling methods which can be broadly divided into two types: probability and non-probability sampling (Thompson, 2012).

In probability sampling, every entity has equal opportunity to be selected in the research but in non-probability sampling, the samples are selected based on particular attributes; thereby, every entity may not have equal chance to be selected in the research (Sampath, 2001). Non-probability sampling is used if probability sampling cannot be used due unavailability of sampling frame. Non-probability sampling is suitable to answers research questions that need gaining inside and understanding rather than statical implication (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Unlike probability sampling, often used in quantitative research that select population with characteristics to represent a wider community; non-probability sampling is used in qualitative research, to investigate a specific topic, specific populations are recruited (Benard, 2013). In this regard, in non-probability sampling often total population is unknown or unavailable (Saunders, lewis and Thronhill, 2023). Since this research is purely based on qualitative methods, to address the research questions, twenty participants are selected. Participants selected are working in leadership positions in three different big universities situated in Nepal and its affiliated institutions (total of six institutions) using non- probability purposive sampling techniques. Participants for the research were selected carefully as in non-probability sampling participants are selected by their availability and willingness to

participants to fulfil the purpose of the study (Creswell, 2002; Sanders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). In purposive sampling techniques participants are selected strategically which are relevant to the research and its purpose rather than random basis (Bekele and Ago, 2022). Therefore, as a researcher I have followed clear guidelines outlining research questions, aim and objectives while selecting suitable participants for the study.

According to Merriam (2001) regarding sample size, “the question of how many numbers of participants, sites, or activities to answer the question posed at the beginning of the study” (P.64). However, in non- probability purposive sampling researcher select suitable participants and look for the saturation stage and stops taking new data when new opinions are not found. According to Creswell (2002) population is a group of people with similar characteristics and who provide the data to address the research questions. To address the research’s aim and objectives participants are selected based on their positions and institutions they work for to avoid collecting data from female leaders from same positions and to avoid collecting more data from one institution over others.

This research uses non- probability purposive sampling as the total women number in a leadership position in higher education institute in Nepal is not clearly identified. The researcher tried to find women leaders in higher education institution by using the internet and word of mouth. Also, some participants were identified by universities’ help and personal recommendation of participants. In this regard, although some participants are selected through snowball technique but the main criteria for selection are whether participants meet the purpose of the study. Therefore, participants were selected who were currently working in the university in various leadership positions using purposive sampling technique. For the process researcher had to contact the respondent and requests to participate in research and the interview process if the participant meet the requirement. Interview taking process was stopped with 20 interviews when I started to feel that no new themes were emerging.

To collect interview from 20 respondents, there were two main difficulties. The first difficulty was identifying women leaders in higher education institutions. It had to be searched on the internet, asked for help from the friends and visited different education institutes. When any women leader is found, she was requested to participate in the research process and scheduled time for an interview. The second difficulty was persuading them to take part in the interview and managing time because most of the time they used to be busy in their own work. As a result, it was needed to wait for many days to get their time and conduct the interview. Most of the participants were happy at the first time to participate except one who declined. Interestingly, some participants were eager to take part in the research: they approached me directly to request for a chance to have their say in the research.

3.8.2. Sampling criteria

In non-probability purposive sampling members of the population are selected aiming to achieving the purpose of the study. Participants are selected if they meet certain practical criteria such as their availability, geographical proximity, availability at that time and willingness to participate in the study (Farrokhi and Mahamoudi,2012). In purposive sampling participants are selected with knowledge and experience that can help to fulfil the purpose of the study and are available and willing to participate (Benard, 2002). This research is about finding women experience on leadership positions in higher education sector therefore participants are selected form three big universities of Nepal and other affiliated institutions. To achieve in-depth information on the issue female participants are selected working in 3 different categories of leadership positions, those are from teaching (Lecturers, professors and Assistant professors), Human Resources department (working in HR department) and Management (Head of departments, campus chief, assistant campus chiefs, and exam co-

ordinators). Female participants are selected from these categories because there might be a different experience as per their department of recruitment thereby data can be triangulated and help to go in-depth of the issue. Also, participants are selected if they have minimum of 2 years of experience in the sector but most of participants were having more than 10 years of experience in higher education. Due to their time of experience, participants were more knowledgeable about the issue and capable to express their thoughts and experiences freely. Thereby it helped to achieve in-depth data more easily in short periods of time.

3.8.3. Sample size

There is a persistent debate around qualitative research and its sample size determination (Vasileious et al. 2018) and it is always a challenge for quantitative researcher to define how many data to collect (Bryman, 2012). According to Baker and Edward (2012), size of quantitative interviews depends on type of research, selected strategy, purpose of the study and methodology adopted. Despite many attempts to draw numerical guidelines to assist inexperienced qualitative researcher from different scholars such as Morse (2000), Vasileiou, et al. (2018), Kindsiko and Poltimae (2019) and Baker and Edwards (2012), there is still lack of exact universally accepted sample size. According to Saunders, lewis and Thornhill (2019) non-probability sampling techniques (other than for quota sampling) is different from probability sampling because there is no rule about sampling size in non-probability sampling technique rather aligning a sample selection technique with purpose of the study is important.

Many literatures argue that qualitative research with purposive sampling is more about answering the research questions rather than number of participants, suggesting guidelines of looking at saturation of the information. Purposive sampling also known as a judgment sampling that recruit the participants by looking at their qualities and does not need to set number of participants (Etikan, Musa and Alkassim, 2016). Mainly in purposive sampling it is

advisable to look for saturation point while taking interviews (Dawson, 2002). According to Morse (2000) saturation of number of participants in a study depends on factors like quality and the amount of the data, nature of the topic, and scope of the study. Also, taking more interviews does not bring more opinion as we reach to the point where there might not be more opinion left, thereby taking one or two more interviews after that is probably the best way to conform the saturation point (Cobern and Adams, 2020). Therefore, in this research I started seeing the same themes keep emerging from different interviews from around 17 to 18 interviews but still wanted to take two more interviews to conform. Thereby I was quite confident that I have reached the saturated point as no new informative data was emerging.

Similarly, size of data required depends on place of study conducted, levels of organizational hierarchy used, comparison needed between different groups (Bryan, 2012; Kindsiko and Poltinae, 2019). Likewise, number of participants are also dependent on complexity of the research (Bekele and Ago, 2022). if the topic is more complex, hard to understand and most participants hesitate to express freely due to nature of the study then more participants are recommended to draw a valid conclusion. According to Benard (2023) to understand and uncover life experience there is growing support for 10-20 important participants are enough for qualitative study. It can be concluded that it is hard to specify exact number of participants required in qualitative research rather depends on nature of a study. Therefore, answering research questions is vital but same time number of participants should not be too small. According to Bryan, (2012) in qualitative research too small size of sample will make hard to reach saturation point and too large sample could make difficult in undertaking deep analysis thus taking extra time and cost in the research. In the study I was making sure the saturation point is met and data collected is sufficient to answer the research questions of the study.

This study is design to take views of females only not male and not intend to compare data between different level of hierarchy and gender rather only tries to explore the experiences of women in leadership. Thus, data needed is relatively in smaller size than some other studies. In this study, in-depth face to face interviews were conducted in participants' desired place, so they can express freely. Also, semi- structure interviews were conducted face to face made me to go in-depth of the issue and get rich data from each participant.

In Addition, the study is designed to take semi-structured interviews as a primary source of the data. Women working in leadership positions in higher education in Nepal is relatively small in numbers therefore sample of 20 in-depth face to face interviews from six different institutions were taken. Also, in order achieve rich data and to go in-depth of the issue data is collected by selecting female participants from three different departments i.e. Professors (Teaching), Management and HR (Human Resource). Female participants were selected from there different departments so data can be collected from three different perspectives thereby triangulating the data findings.

3.9. Data Analysis

3.9.1. Data transcribing approach

Transcribing data (interviews) is important part of research as it can directly impact the outcome of the study. Main aim of the study was to explore the experience of women of getting into leadership positions and leading. In this regards the study needs more about what women have experience over their journey in day-to-day life. It is more about women perspective therefore I have used Intelligent verbatim transcription process. In this process interviews are transcribed by word to word but details such as pauses, high or low pitches, body language and use of words flaws (such as uff,, oh,,hmm,) are not included unless it felt too necessary. I have

chosen this approach due to three main reasons: first the study is mainly from women side and questions on semi-structured interviews are clearly written, participants were assured of their privacy and use of pseudonym name therefore it is not necessity for participants to hide the information. Secondly, most of the participants had long years of experience thereby excellent on constructing their words and answers. That is why answers given were flowless and almost no hesitations while answering except some laughter. Therefore, it was less necessity to use different approach. Lastly, interviews transcribed in alternative approach is more time consuming, costly and not easily readable. Therefore, I used this approach to transcribe the interviews.

3.9.2. Data analysis process

Data analysis is a critical part of the research as it systematically evaluates information and derives a conclusion (Lamprecht, 2005). According to Kothari (2009), the data analysis process can be determined based on the data that has been collected. This research has collected qualitative information; thereby, it uses the qualitative data analysis process.

During the all the interviews, the researcher took some keynotes, but it was not my primary focus because all the interviews were being recorded with the permissions of participants; rather researcher was more focused on bringing flow to the interviews so that participants can express themselves freely without any hesitation. The qualitative data collected from 20 interviews were transcribed thoroughly so that even single information is not missed. Although the researcher tried to transcribe the interviews just after a day it was not possible, as sometimes, there were more than two interviews taken on the same day. It was quite time-consuming and daunting to translate the interviews as every interview is more than an hour and rich in data. When the researcher was listening to interviews over and over again while translating them, he did not just feel like listening to their stories but rather living those: which

helped him while analysing the data. Interview questions were carefully formulated using themes from the literature review and research questions but new themes were constantly emerging during the process. For thematic analysis of the qualitative data, all the data were put into NVivo software to systematically classify the data. Which undoubtedly helped me to identify the frequency and linkage of the key terms. Since thematic analysis focuses more on what is said rather than how it was said, constantly new themes were emerging from the data. There is no universal way of doing thematic analysis but it needs quite considerable time and effort (Howitt and Cramer, 2008). Systematic six steps process for thematic analysis of the data provided by Braun and Clarke (2006) was quite helpful and was followed.

Figure 7: Phases of Thematic Analysis

(Source: Braun and Clarke, 2006; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023)

The qualitative data collected from 20 respondents are systematically classified to find the trend of the data. In the same way, the author also presents key data from every question; thereby, no key information can be missed. After presenting the data, it becomes easy to analyse and discuss them. The data are analysed using related theories, methods, logics and arguments. While analysing, primary data are given key focus but to make the argument valid and generalisable, it is further supported by literature presented in the second chapter. In the same

way, the data are compared and contrasted as per required and based on this analysis, the conclusion can be derived.

3.10. Accessibility

Accessibility is the main issue as the sample respondents are special and they are at their own work most of the time. They have more responsibility to the organization and they are busy all the time; so, direct access can be very less. In this regard, all participants were prior contacted by email or phone call (which was accessed from the internet or word of mouth) to get permission to meet. Until the researcher collects 20 interviews, the contacting process continues. When the permission is granted, it becomes easy to meet and conduct interviews. The date, time and place of the interview can be determined via phone or email contact. So, it cannot be difficult to get access as the respondents are happy to participate in the interview process but as they ignore, then the accessibility can be difficult and such respondents are not forced to participate - rather others are contacted.

3.11. The Credibility of the Research

Qualitative researches are mostly criticised for adaptation of qualitative approaches. Critics of qualitative researches normally raised issues of being lack representativeness of the sample, methods of data collection, analysis process and interpretation of data. Concerns around credibility, reliability, validity and transferability are addressed differently by qualitative researchers (Fink, 2013). Participants viewpoints can have an impact on the credibility of the qualitative research (Hill, 2001). In order to increase the credibility of the findings data collection was triangulated by collecting from participants working in 3 different departments (management, professors/teaching and Human resource) to get different perspective asking same questions To retain the credibility of the findings, at the end of each interview some

participants were asked to make sure whether their expressed views were accurately reflected on the keynotes taken during the interviews. Likewise, in this research, the data are collected in the natural environment where the bias of the researcher is not manifested. After transcribing the interviews most of the participants were given a copy to check on all the information said in the interviews. The data shows the key experiences and challenges of women leaders in higher education institutions in Nepal and in course of collecting and interpreting data, the author's influence has been minimised to increase the credibility of the research. Further, the research process is fully guided by the proven scientific and systematic research method. analysed by using relevant theories, logic, concepts and arguments. In this regard, the conclusion of this research is highly credible.

3.12. Ethical Considerations

3.12.1. Introduction

In relation to social research, ethics refers to moral deliberation, accountability and choice for the researchers that go along the research process (Miller, Melanie and Birch, 2012). Ethics always lies at the heart of any research and it has some philosophies which are: the informed consent should be provided to participants; participation should not be obligatory but voluntary; any risks and harms associated to participants should be avoided; no unreasonable demand can be made to participants; and research should take careful consideration of anonymity and confidentiality (Ritchie, Lewis and Nicholls, 2013). And to conduct this study, the researcher has got an approval letter from the University of The West of Scotland, which can also be one of the bases of guiding criteria.

3.12.2. Informed Consent

The participants of the study must get confidence that they have given genuine voluntary informed consent. To meet this requirement, all of the participants were contacted prior to the interview; and informed of the area of the research, time schedule for interviews and the purpose of the research. As contribution is voluntary participants can withdraw at any point of time if they are unwilling to participate.

3.12.3. Recording

It is almost impossible to remember or take notes of all interviews taken; therefore, interviews taken were recorded using a voice recorder device and it was transcribed later. Participants' permission was taken before recording interviews because recording without permission is an unethical job.

3.12.4. Data Protection (Access, Storage, and Security)

Considering Data Protection Act (1998) personal information of each respondent is securely stored. This information is only used for this particular purpose. Further, without the consent of the respondent, no data will be passed to the third person. For the security purpose, all of the data are stored in the personal device which is secured by the password. All the participants are assured that the collected data will be kept secured. Data is placed in personal computer with the password protected and only accessible to me and my supervisors if needed. The data will be held securely protected before and after the submission of the thesis. It is kept securely after submission as it might be needed for possible further research.

3.12.5. Confidentiality (Anonymity and Privacy)

As the study is based on individual circumstances; confidentiality of the participants is taken seriously. To assure that confidentiality, interviews are conducted in participants' preferred

place. Even more, all participants' identity has been kept anonymous and the names of the institutes where they are working have also kept secret. So, no participant can be adversely affected by this research. In the course of analysis, if any data is found to have direct negative impacts on any organisation or any person are excluded from the research. Considering the ethics of respect, as participants have given valuable time from their busy schedules to help the researcher with the research; all interviews were taken the time and place preferred by the participants.

3.12.6. Researcher reflexivity and positioning (Insider/Outsider: Gender)

Researchers' roles and assumptions in data collection are define as reflexivity and positionality (Guilemin and Gulam, 2004). Reflexivity is about power relation between participants and the researcher and how participants see a researcher as. As participants should not feel judged and feel confident in taking part in the research therefore reflexivity is necessary part of developing ethical sensibility (Knott, et al. 2022). Following the guidelines suggested by Guillemin and Gillam (2004) I was fully aware that reflexivity is essential in all phases of research from formulating research questions, data collection, analysis and to drawing conclusions. According to Pring (2001) while conducting social research researcher's position matter most and gender (outsider or insider) issue is one of the important ethical issues to consider on interpretive qualitative research. Since I was outsider (male) conducting research on issue of females' experiences I was aware of possible bias. Therefore, I was taking appropriate suggestions and guidelines from my female supervisor and most of works are authorised by her before going to next steps. Likewise, all the research process were done in systematic way to minimise my personal influence over the research. Research questions were formulated carefully from literatures and the aim of the research. Participants were carefully selected considering suitability of the research. During interviews I was more self-reflective and was trying to put my thoughts, emotions and their triggers a side as I was aware that it can have a

direct impact over responses of the female participants. In order to detach my personal influence over the research process and not to miss any crucial information, all the interviews were recorder and live note was taken. After each interviews note were given to participants to re-check on data that they just had expressed.

Thankfully, All the females participated in the study were very receptive and cooperative when I reach out to them even though I was outsider (Male researcher). Researcher's position such as gender, race and personal experience impact the research (Hamzeh and Oliver, 2010). It could be true in very personal and sensitive research topics But, in this research, for being a male and still trying to research on females experience in leadership journey; I was welcomed generously by female participants. Most of the participants were happy and thanked me (being a male) for trying to investigate on barriers of females' leadership thereby expressed their experiences and point of views freely.

3.13. Limitations

This is the qualitative research that does not use any quantitative information; thereby, it may not obtain the objective conclusion. As per the theory and argument that is used to explain the data, the conclusion can be different. It has not used a wider range of sample respondents, unlike quantitative research, because qualitative research cannot accommodate huge numbers of sample respondents; so that, it may not cover the perception of the entire population. Sample of the research is quite small (20 Interviews) compared to quantitative research – so, results cannot be generalised (Denscombe, 2003). Similarly, Sample taken is not statistical: outcomes cannot be replicated.

Research data is collected in a certain period of time and the circumstances might have changed after that period. Therefore, findings for the research may not be certain all the time. Likewise, the research is conducted within the selected geographical area and context, so it cannot be seen as a complete representation of other territories.

Due to ethical consideration issue, it cannot use some of the information that is believed to have negative impacts on the respondents or any third parties. Also, it has not included any perception of male respondents. If it uses male respondents as well, the research could be extensive and could not be completed on time. Considering this fact, the males' perception has not been considered. Also, Interviews taken for the research are semi-structured so that may not be as efficient as unstructured interviews for participants to express freely.

3.14. Summary

This chapter covers the research methodology adopted and implemented in this research. The chapter started discussing philosophical aspects then followed by discussion and justification on epistemology, ontology, research approaches, research methods, research strategy, data collection methods and analysis of the data. Likewise, other significant aspects like ethical issues and limitation of the research were also broadly discussed. From this chapter, it is obvious that this research adopts Interpretivism epistemology, subjective ontology, inductive reasoning and qualitative research methods. Similarly, data is collected using semi-structured interviews and analysed using a thematic analysis. Next chapter discusses key findings from the data collection which are divided into themes and sub-themes. The chapter also gives some description about interviewees such as their positions, time of their service and the leadership styles they adopt.

Chapter 4: Findings

4.1. Introduction

The qualitative data were collected from 20 respondents by using semi-structured interview data collection instrument. All the interviews were recorded using a tape recorder and later on, each interview was transcribed. NVivo software was used to identify key themes. Except one, all of the interviews were conducted in Nepali language and later they were translated into English.

4.1.1. Description of Interviewees

Twenty interviews were collected by the means of interview data collection instrument where 16 pre-planned questions were asked to every interviewee. All of the names are pseudonyms. Table 2 presents a short introduction of the interviewees.

Table 4: Description of the Interviewees

<p>Sarita: She is the Head of Department of the University in Kathmandu. She started her career as a teaching assistant in 2000. She came from different institution with experience of 3 years as a lecturer. She uses a participatory leadership style.</p>
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<p>Kalpana: She is the Head of the Administrative Assistant of a government college in Kathmandu. She has been working in this position for 1 and a half years. Before this position, she used to teach in a higher education government school she was there for 6 years. She prefers to use a democratic leadership style.</p>

Rita: She has been holding Admission Chief position in an Engineering college in Kathmandu for 3 years and 4 months. She started from a junior position and continuously promoted as chief position. She has great teamwork ability.

Kamala: She is an associate professor in a government college in Kathmandu. She has been working in this position for 24 years. She does not discriminate her staffs; she wants to satisfy each and every one in her team.

Shanti: She is an associate professor at a private university in Kathmandu for 6 years and she is unmarried. She wants to bring changes in the patriarchal culture of her society by spreading social awareness.

Kumari: She is working as a lecturer and coordinator in a government college in Kathmandu for 11 years. She has a long teaching experience and she uses a transformational leadership style.

Shirjana: She has been holding the head of the department in an Engineering college in Kathmandu for 6 years after completion of her master's degree in education. She participates employees in a decision-making process.

Laxmi: She is the Chief of a government college in Chitwan for 5 years and she has PhD. She wants to be strict on rules and regulations.

Saraswoti: She is a lecturer and coordinator of a government college in Nawalparasi for 20 years. She is frank and uses a participatory leadership style to fulfil her roles and responsibilities.

Raji: She is holding a human resource manager position at a private university in Kathmandu for more than 12 years. She has an MBA degree and she focuses on teamwork.

Pooja: She is the head of an exam section of a private university in Kathmandu for 20 years. She has done a double master's degree and she uses a democratic leadership style.

Ambika: She is the head of the department of a government university in Kathmandu for 21 years. She has done PhD and she wants to transfer skills to the employees.

Sakuntala: She is the deputy administrator in a government university in Kathmandu. She is married and has done a PhD. She is very open to her employees.

Purnakala: She is a professor at a government college for 30 years. She has done a master's degree. She uses a transformational leadership style.

Samjhana: She is a program coordinator of a government college in Sunsari for 17 years. She is married and has done MPhil in population studies. She prefers to use a democratic leadership style.

Maya: She is holding the head of a department of a government college in Kathmandu for 38 years. She has done a PhD and she uses an autocratic leadership style.

Smirti: She is the head of department at a government college in Kathmandu for 31 years. She is married and uses a participatory leadership style.

Gita: She is the head of department of a government university in Kathmandu for 38 years. She is married and has completed a master's degree. She is not sure about her own leadership style.

Radha: She is an assistant professor at a private university in Kathmandu for 15 years. She is married and uses a democratic leadership style.

Anusha: She is the head of department of a private college in Kathmandu for 3 years. She has done a PhD. She gives focus on a democratic leadership style.

(Source: data from interviews)

4.1.2. Word Cloud on Response

The author asked 16 questions to every respondent to collect information about the main themes of the research. All of the answers were used to develop a general word cloud (figure 8) by which the keywords were identified to develop research themes. As the themes were created based on NVivo software, they were further evaluated based on related literature. If the identified themes did not correlate objectives and literature, it could be understood that there was a gap between the collected data and objectives, so that; the research could not resolve the problem. To avoid such gap, the themes generated by NVivo software were tested using objectives and literature - and it was found that the themes are strongly supported.

Figure 8: Core themes and sub-themes in NVivo

(Sources: Created using NVivo)

The above word cloud indicates that women, leadership, female, education, discrimination, responsibilities and culture are the keywords that are repeatedly used by the interviewees.

4.1.3. Research Themes

Based on literature review, objectives of the study, and NVivo software, eight key themes have been developed. The first theme is **women experience as a leader**. In different HE institutions, there might be different experiences of women. The second theme is the **perception of women leadership in society**. The third theme is **women education and ability** in which information about equal education between male and female, and women capability to lead a team are the major issues raised. The fourth theme is **family support and responsibility**. The fifth theme is **gender equality on the organizational level**. It deals about recruitment and selection, promotion, payment and working culture. The sixth theme is **causes of lower numbers of**

female leadership in higher education institutions in Nepal. The seventh theme is **the challenges of women leadership**, and the final theme is **solution or empowerment**.

4.2. Women Experience as Leader

4.2.1. Leadership Experience

Question 1 sought to know the experience of women leadership. According to the report of US Congress Economic Committee (2010) the women participation in the workforce has been increased by one third from 1970 to 2010 and their experience has been drastically changing but it has not been known in the context of Nepal; so that, this question tries to find out existing gaps or discriminations between males and females in workforce.

In the response of question number 1, some of the women leaders have felt easiness whereas some others have experienced great challenges to fulfil their responsibilities. Indeed, it is imperative to say that more respondents have positive experiences of leading the organization.

4.2.1.1. Positive Experience

Sarita says, "So if you asked my experience, it's quite good." Similarly, Raji says, "I don't feel any difficulty." Sakuntala says, "It is good" and she believes that if women do not have "weak mentality" they can be successful in their leadership role. She was empowered and motivated by her parents, and she feels herself a strong woman. Purnakala has also got positive experiences of this leadership position. She says, "I become very happy as I enter into the classroom and I am frank to the students. It is a quite an entertaining experience." She has got support from every employee and student; thereby, she has not got any difficulties to fulfil her roles and responsibilities. Similarly, Rita says, "In the beginning, I was working in a junior position but later I got promotion and got this chief position. It is good. I have got respect and

support from all employees." This information shows that she has got positive experience working as a female leader. Similarly, Shanti also does not feel any negative experience:

In my personal view, both male and female are equal competitors. The mathematics department's most senior professor who lives in a different room than me, but I have not felt any weakness. In the beginning, there were more boy teachers and only me as the female. So, I did not feel any challenge.

Here, Shanti does not feel any difficulties as being a female leader rather the employees have better faith and support to her. There is only one female teacher and the employees are quite supportive instead of making any discrimination. In the same way, Kumari says,

I came in this field from boarding school. In this field, we cannot say anything to the teachers as it is the government institution. If there is no class, just we have to remind. At that time some teachers are careless. One must be liberal in this position. If anyone shows the power of the position, it does not work. Sometimes, teachers do not fulfil their responsibilities.

Kumari knows how to manage employees; thereby, she has not got any problem. In government institutions, the leadership should be liberal instead of an autocrat. There might be some kinds of indirect effects of patriarchal culture but it is not directly exposed in practice and they have not faced any difficulties to fulfil their leadership roles and responsibilities.

4.2.1.2. Negative Experience

Some of the women leaders have experienced discrimination. The experience of Ambika is not so good, who says, "Being a woman, it is difficult to work." She has just mentioned difficulties but there is no clear explanation of how it was difficult to work as a female leader. In the same way, Kamala says:

Being a woman, it is great to secure the leadership position. I am happy with it. Although in slogan it is said that women should be promoted and given reservation quota, the male-dominated society feels uncomfortable to forward females and work under their leadership. There is a kind of unseen discrimination. They feel a kind of guilty while working under females' leadership. That I feel.

Kamala has experienced a kind of uneasiness in employees working under female leadership but she has not got any direct impacts on her. She has found that, still, society is not ready to give leadership opportunity to females. It signifies that more awareness programs are required and reservation quotas should be strictly applied. Likewise, Gita also says, "Definitely, it is difficult being a female. Sometimes, going here and there, attending meetings and looking after own department. Sometimes it is hard to manage teachers and students. Plus, the family needs to be looked after. It is difficult." Gita tries to say that leadership position is itself complicated and challenging, and for a female, it can be more complicated. The similar type of perception presented by Radha who says that as a woman holding leadership position is very challenging as she has more home responsibilities which are complicated to manage. Similarly, Anusha says, "It is challenging to be a women leader because people do not easily accept." It means to say that the employees and the entire society do not easily accept female leadership which makes a kind of uneasiness while communicating, supervision, and working together with the stakeholders. Shirjana also found it as a challenging job and she says, "There are lots of challenges. Most of the head of department (HOD) in this college are males and I am the only female HOD. Although my confidence level is high, I cannot speak at first which might be due to the impact of patriarchal culture." She has indicated lots of challenges but she mentioned one experience which is not that much good. If there were other female HOD (Head of Department), she would feel easy participating in meetings or discussion.

4.2.1.3. *Mixed Experience*

Apart from that Maya has a kind of mixed experience - "Sometimes I feel happy and sometimes a kind of discrimination." This data indicates that she is not sure whether as a woman leader there are some difficulties or not. In some cases, she finds support but sometimes a kind of difficulty has been faced in term of gender. Kalpana also has a neutral experience, who says that it is equally difficult for both male and female as it is a challenging job itself.

4.2.2. *Achieving Leadership Position*

Question number 2 was designed to find out the reason for working in leadership positions. Literature [for instance in the European Commission there were 12% female representatives in 1989-1992, 6% in 1992-1994, 25% in 1994-1999, 25% in 1999-2004, 29% in 2004-2009 and 33% in 2009-2014 (European Commission, 2013)] shows that although female participation in higher position has been continuously increasing, achieving such position is not as much easy to females as males. Whether it applies to higher positions at educational institutions in Nepal might be one of the key questions and to resolve this query, question number 2 remains significant.

4.2.2.1. *Leadership Position - Coincidence or Without Desire*

Some of the interviewees have got leadership position coincidentally. For example, Sarita says:

It's not a choice. I was a graduate of this department. I was a student of this department and I have got a leading position now which is because there was none to take the responsibility. Someone has to take the lead and I became ready to accept the challenge.

Here, it is clear that she has achieved the leadership position not because of her choice but because of a kind of compulsion. Similarly, Raji says, "I was suggested by my professors as I

had specialised in Human Resource and nobody here was equally qualified for the post; so, I joined." She was not looking for this position; she wanted to join a job and in course of a searching job, coincidentally she was offered this position. Similarly, Pooja was also not thinking about this position and she replies, "No, I had never thought of this field." As she completed her Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.), she was offered this position by the university as she was an intelligent student of the same university. In the same way, Purnakala says, "It is like a winning a lottery." It means to say that she got this leadership position by chance. Samjhana also says that she got this position by luck but not by strong desire or effort. As she got the position, her interest has been increased to do something in the education field. Likewise, Maya does not know why she selects education field and holds the leadership position. The same kind of expression can be found in Smirti - "I did not choose the teaching profession. It just came to me. Once you stay here, you need to build up your qualification. I was initially brought for 10 days and later I was given a contract for six months that I had to complete." This information shows that she was awarded this leadership position by others but she did not have any strong desire to get this position. In the same way, Gita says, "In Art Department, only art-related person could be the HOD. As seniority basis, I was promoted in this position." It shows that based on long involvement in the department, she has got the opportunity and she easily accepted it. Similarly, Kamala says:

I have not chosen it. My subject is education planning and management which is related to leadership. In this campus, as there was the vacancy of female assistant campus chief, other co-workers chose me. In the beginning, I was also not interested because it might have challenges because this position has to deal with several students and it may give me unnecessary burden but my co-workers, friends, sisters, everyone said that I have to deserve it. They said that people do everything to get such a position but why should I leave this opportunity.

The above data shows that there is no special reason to hold this leadership position. She was engaged by everyone not to lose the opportunity and she just accepted it. In the same way, Shirjana says:

I never thought I will come to the academic field and get this leadership position when I was doing my BE. I did my BE from India. In India, after BE only few students do ME (master's in engineering) as it is purely professional and academic field. Mostly other students go for MBA. I also joined for MBA on that particular perspective but due to my personal life, I came to the academic sector.

This information has clarified that she did not have any special cause and desire to get any leadership position in academic sectors but now she is holding it. In this way, in the course of a searching job, most of them get this position and they accepted it.

4.2.2.2. Leadership Position - Dream or Desire

But there are few respondents who have some kind of causes behind selecting this position. As for example, Ambika wanted to get involved in the education field where she especially interested to teach social behaviour holding a leadership position. She says:

I selected this profession is because the teaching profession is not just about teaching but to build good characteristics. I do not want students to get just a degree of master or bachelor rather I want to teach them about social behaviours that ultimately will contribute to having a good family and society as a whole.

In this regard, it was her dream to hold this leadership position. Similarly, Sakuntala was also interested to hold some kind of leadership position; so that, she could bring rural women into the mainstream. She had a kind of ambition and says:

I go around as a trainer in regard to women activities. I am quite interested to find the ways to bring women into the mainstream who are not able to do that. I came from Solukhumbu for study. As I was looking after my family It was necessary to work. Then I got the job here.

She wanted to have some kind of leadership position related to women empowerment. In the education sector, she could contribute to empowering women by encouraging rural women to get a higher education. In the same way, Anusha says, "It was my dream and I continuously work hard and after passing commission examination, I got this position." She wanted to get this position and she has great effort to achieve it.

Similarly, Kalpana says, "I wanted to get a governmental position. I am not working here as the social worker; I joined here for a job." She is not interested in any leadership position, rather she got it in the course of getting a government job. Although Rita did not have any dream to hold this position in the beginning, later on, she found it is quite fascinating. She says:

There was no exact planning to choose this sector. As I came to Kathmandu, I was in the struggle phase at that time. I was searching for job and I saw the vacancy of this institution. And in the academic sector, it is easy to manage time for ladies and there is respect in this job as well. There is no tight schedule. That's why, I applied, and I also become successful to be recruited immediately.

In the course of a searching job, as Kalpana, Rita is also fascinated by fixed time work in the education field. Mostly, women have more responsibilities at home and they want a fixed time job. Further, Rita finds it very much respected sector; thereby, she is attracted in this field. In the same way, Radha describes the reason behind selecting leadership position as:

After completion of my master degree, I was working for an international organisation but I was interested in the teaching field. I worked in India for three years and I earned good money as well. Later, I heard that a university is a quite good place to work for women as they can have a fixed time. Then I came here and applied for this position.

Here, Radha has two clear reasons for her HE leadership choice: the first reason is the interest in the education field and the second is her willingness to work on a fixed time basis.

Generally, the data suggests that most of the women interviewed did not hold this by desire and achieved their positions almost by default. Whether that was because they had not anticipated a leadership role because of societal norms something that needs to be considered.

4.3. Perception of Women Leadership in the Society

4.3.1. Males' Perception over Female Leadership

Mostly, in a patriarchal society, males are holding decision making power or higher positions but if there are females in such positions, the society cannot easily accept (Momsen, 2009). In this contest, it is imperative to find out males' perception over female leadership to which question number 3 was designed. Although there are mixed perceptions, the majority of the respondents say that males are jealous of female leadership due to male-dominant culture.

4.3.1.1. Positive Perception

Purnakala finds positive perception over female leadership but she is aware that there is a kind of negative perception in some corner of the mind. She says:

I always hear positive responses from men. They often say that women can do better. However, negative perception about women is rooted in their subconscious mind. It is all about how we all were grown-up. In a family, only girls work not boys. Due to that

grooming, even though both husband and wife are in the same status, he comes home, sits and waits for the wife to make a cup of tea. A wife feels bad but she does not really say anything. It is because of our grooming. Well-educated husband has in his mind that he needs to help wife but in practice he ignores.

She has not experienced any negative perception of males but she is aware of the patriarchal social culture. Although males want to treat women as equal to males, they are afraid of social trend and perception. In the same way, Rita says, "It might be but personally I have not felt that males are jealous of females." She knows that there might be negative perceptions of males over women leadership but personally, she has not experienced as she has got support from both male and female. Similarly, Shirjana has also not felt any discrimination between males over female leadership. She says, " I don't know about other organisations but there is no such issue here. Women are capable that is the only reason to be selected." This data indicates that there is no negative perception of males; only the competitive females come in the position as there is no special privilege for them. Overall, the above-mentioned data indicates that although females have not experienced any discrimination from males, they are aware of the impact of a male-dominated society.

4.3.1.2. Negative Perception

Some of the respondents find that males have negative perception over females as for example Pooja says:

We have a male-dominated culture where women are treated as second-class citizen. Even my husband, who is well educated, has done Ph.D. and professor, has that kind of attitude. For example, we both come to work at the same time around 9 and leave the office at the exact same time but once we enter a house, he has his own gents' style and I have to work on domestic work such as cleaning, arranging and cooking. However,

although women do double work, no man feels that way, neither my husband nor my senior bosses.

This data shows that due to male-dominated culture, males' perception over females is not equal. Even educated males have also a kind of discriminated perception over female leadership. They believe that females are not capable to lead any organization; they are supposed only followers. If any women get leadership positions, the male-dominated society does not easily digest. The same kind of perception has been expressed by Ambika, "There is a difference in the male thought process. Women were seen as if they are not capable and only suitable to stay in the house in the past but it is not like that now." This data indicates that males perceive women unsuitable for leadership positions but this kind of perception has been gradually changing along with increasing social awareness. Maya also finds that males are jealous. She says, "They are jealous and they do not want to see women leadership." As females are in leadership positions, males feel inferior to women; thereby, they do not want them to see in such positions. Raji says, "They (males) have a kind of jealousy." It indicates that males do not want to see women in the leadership position and they feel jealous if females are in the leadership position. They do not directly show jealousy but indirectly they do not want to tolerate women leadership.

4.3.1.3. Mixed Perception

Samjhana has mixed experience and she says, "It is mixed, some males perceive positively but some do not." Of course, it is imperative to say that every male may not think equal over female leadership; they might have their own perception which might be made through cultural norms and values. Radha also says:

To be frank, most of the men think that women are here for their entertainment. Women are here because they are bored at home. Men think that women are just wasting their

time and it is not necessary to be here at work at all. Even some of my colleagues have told me that they do not want their wives to meet me and think that I might mislead them. My husband sometimes makes a cup of tea for me which they consider as an inappropriate thing.

It means to say that males do not believe that females can also be leaders; they think females only their supporters. In order to create positive perceptions; female leaders should prove their ability at first. Until and unless they prove their ability, they are suspected whether they can lead the organization or not. Similar Kalpana says, " The males are jealous if females are promoted in higher positions." It might be due to patriarchal culture. In the same way, Anusha says, "They believe that females are not able to hold any leadership position; they want to see only males in the higher position." This is also a biased perception of males and it can be expressed in the workplace as well. Sarita also says:

Male dominance is there in our society but in case of professors or academic people, I don't think there is such things like she is a woman and you should not listen her or she can't do. There is nothing like that. I haven't experienced that.

This information suggests that although there is no direct discrimination of males, to some extent males' dominance is there and it affects woman leader to fulfil her roles and responsibilities. Overall, some males are jealous over women leadership and some males are quite supportive and positive to the women leadership.

Sakuntala says, "Lots of men have become positive and think that when women get chance they can be like me. In contrast, some men still think that women are weak. They take women as a second-class citizen." This suggests that while some males have positive perceptions of women's abilities in leadership positions but some are still governed by masculine culture, believing women to be less capable than males and unsuitable for leadership positions.

4.3.2. Patriarchal Culture

In the previous data related to male perception over female leadership, a glimpse of patriarchal culture in women leadership has been shown but it requires to be understood in detail as it is one of the major issues of the research. Still, the patriarchal culture has been strongly governing Nepalese society and its impacts have been seen in women empowerment and career development (Yadav, 2016). Question number 4 was designed to understand the impact of patriarchal culture on women leadership. Still, it is not easy for women to hold leadership positions in Nepal.

4.3.2.1. Gender Discrimination

In the patriarchal society, women might have more household responsibilities that affect to continue office work. According to Raji, "Women are perceived other ways than actually said." It means to say that in appearance there is equality between male and female but in reality, still patriarchal practice is there. The society treats women as they are inferior, and they know nothing. Ambika also says that due to the patriarchal culture, women do not get opportunities and if they achieve this position, proving their abilities can be the key challenge. She says:

I had been very much affected by the patriarchal culture in the past, but things have changed now. People are more supportive now than before. But still, in village areas, culture has negatively affected females. In those areas, family and society do not have supportive behaviour. Therefore, it is very difficult for women to come to leadership positions.

This information clarifies that the patriarchal values are weakening day by day; thereby, its impacts are not seen that much in the urban area but still it has been significantly affecting in the rural areas. Similarly, Sakuntal says:

It is all because of society and culture. There are lots of limitations for women in eating, wearing, visiting and many more. Why can't women go to the place that men go? Why can't women eat that men eat? When something is right for men to eat and wear; it must be right for women too. It is all because of society.

The patriarchal society has confined women in particular roles - mostly, in household activities. It has set rules that determine what she has and has not to do. They are made subordinated to males; thereby, Sakuntal fully blames patriarchal culture for making women backward in the society. In the same way, the Samjhana says:

In our organization, there is a particular group that makes every decision so do not value us. Everyone is just guided by that group. In the group, a majority are men and their decision can be decisive and women should obey it. I can think of one word 'rubber stamp'. A woman can be a rubber stamp to stay in this position as males have a significant role in making any decision.

This information suggests that women are deprived by the patriarchal culture and are not given the same opportunities as men. In this type of culture, women find it difficult to get into leadership positions and if they get, it can be further challenging to lead people as they do not easily accept women until they prove their ability. Further, Maya says:

Culture has huge impacts. The society has made women tolerable even they have faced any injustice. If women speak, the society does not consider good. If women do any courageous work, she is not appreciated because the society believes that she should only follow the male and should not do any extra things. In this kind of society, it is impossible to develop female leadership.

The above information has clarified that in Nepalese society, there is discrimination between males and females. Due to the patriarchal social concept, females are suffering to hold leadership positions. Similarly, Anusha says, " It is the major factor that becomes an obstacle to hold any leadership position. In this culture, women are only seen as subordinate or helper of the male." In this way, Smirti also feels a significant challenge of the patriarchal society in course of holding any leadership position. The society does not want to see women in the leadership position; thereby, it does not support them rather it creates obstacles in different steps. Radha believes that the "society in some cases stops women from moving forward." It means to say that the society does not want any progress or career development of females. To stop them from progress, the society creates barriers through cultural norms, language and traditional values. Likewise, Gita says, "Men also work in the leadership positions but they do not work as seriously as a woman. But women are not believed fully at first." As females are not believed, they cannot get support on the one hand and prove their ability can be challenging on the other hand; so, patriarchal society makes their leadership position very challenging.

4.3.2.2. Changing Patriarchal Belief

Some respondents do not feel any kind of negative impacts of the patriarchal society to fulfil their roles and responsibilities. Sarita says:

It's not easy for women. You know that you are also from the same country; same place; you must have seen in your family also. We have to take care of the family and this job also, but it's been not that much tough for me. Family support is there. My husband supports me.

In the case of Sarita, the family members are supportive and she has not experienced any difficulties. Pooja has also not faced any negative effects of patriarchal culture in the course of getting recruited and continuing in a leadership position. She says:

It is not hard. Only thing is that when meetings are arranged, I am not invited and I have told them many times not to avoid me. I do not complain about any other behaviour. We work in our exam section until 11 pm, but never felt any inappropriate behaviour. We work as a friend, talk as if we all are the same. But the only thing I feel is that I never invited to the meetings.

Here, Pooja's major concern is regarding the participation in meetings but in other aspects, she has not faced any difficulties due to patriarchal social practice. Similarly, Purnakala says that a new generation has been evolving in politics and she is hopeful that they can eradicate the negative effects of the patriarchal culture. In her own personal case, she has not experienced a negative impact during the course of fulfilling her roles and responsibilities. Similar experiences and thoughts have been expressed by Kalpana who says:

Culturally, this is our patriarchal society but from the next generation, it will not be so. Females will also come as equal to males. Before our generation, females were given education. There was female early marriage culture that used to become an obstacle to studying but it has been changed.

This data tries to clarify that in the past there were several challenges of patriarchal practice but now it has been changed; thereby, she has not faced any significant difficulty because of the cultural values.

4.4. Women Education and ability

4.4.1. Gender Discrimination in Education

Gender discrimination can be seen in many sectors including education. In order to secure leadership positions, education is the most significant component. As females are not given a

good education, they become backward and merely subordinate to the males because education is the only thing that opens doors for several career opportunities (Weale, 2015). Question number 5 was asked whether there is gender discrimination in education or not.

According to Sarita, in Nepal, women education was not given priority in the past days but there is equality at present. She says:

Yes, partly yes. Definitely. They have seen our mother, grandmother and doing the same thing. We have continued tradition but things are changing definitely. Women are also working outside the home. They are doing lots of bigger things which the males are doing. Things are changing. Nowadays, males are helping their family in the kitchen, in laundry things. Everything. That's really good.

It means to say that there was not equal education in the past but nowadays there is no gender discrimination in providing education. Similarly, Raji says, "I do not find that much discrimination at present context but it was in the past." This information also indicates that in education, both male and female are getting an education and there is not that much discrimination. Similar kind of perception is presented by Radha, who says that discrimination was existing in the past but now there is no discrimination. Similarly, Shanti says, "I do not think so." It indicates that Shanti does not find any gender discrimination in education. In the same way, Saraswoti, Ambika, Sakuntala and Samjhana have same perception that there is no discrimination in education between male and female. At present, a greater change in education has been found due to awareness brought by NGOs and INGOs. People realise that female education is equally imperative to develop their future career. But some of the interviewees find a kind of gender discrimination in education.

Pooja finds discrimination in rural areas but not in urban. She says, "Still in the remote area there is some kind of discrimination." In the remote area, there is a lack of awareness regarding

the importance of education on the one hand and there are more home responsibilities for females on the other hand. Anyway, women education between in urban and rural areas is not the same. Similar to Pooja, Kalpana also says, "Still in the rural area, females are deprived of getting the education. Males are given quality education while females are not." In the same way, other interviewees like Maya, Smirti and Laxmi also say the same thing that in rural area discrimination can be still seen but in the urban area no discrimination can be found. Purnakala says, "There is still some difference but it has been changing slowly. It indicates that gender discrimination in education has not been completely abolished but it is on the process and she is hopeful that in coming days there will not be any discrimination in providing education. The same kind of perception has been presented by Shirjana, Anusha and Rita, who say that there is no equal education - still males are given priority, but the situation has been continuously changing compared to the past. They are optimistic for the coming days that both male and female will get an equal education. They say that if females are not given a good education, they can be always backward, and they cannot be seen in leadership or decision-making positions.

4.4.2. Doubt in women abilities

If the opportunities are given, women are also equally capable of leading teams. Indeed, females are confined within four walls of the house and then they are charged as being less capable compared to males. Women are deprived of education and politics; and culturally, they are made subordinate to males. The patriarchal society does not want to see women in decision making or good social position; rather it wants them to see working in household activities (Kolas, 2017). But nowadays, the situation has been changed and women are also holding leadership positions. As both genders (male and female) are treated equally, there is no chance women to be less capable than men. It means to say that women are not unable, but the society

has made them less capable. In order to find Nepalese women ability to lead a team, question number 6 was designed.

Skills and abilities can be different from one individual to another and it cannot be said in general that women are less capable than men to hold a leadership position. According to Sarita:

No, no. I don't think it is more or less than men. Each gender has its own capacity but you know the professional capacity. Every individual is different. Even in males, it is different from one person to another. I don't think females are less capable than males. Individually they are different.

Sarita does not agree that females are less capable. Individually, a woman might be less capable than a particular man but in general entire women cannot be said less capable. Similarly, Raji says:

Women are humble as a result they can put their thoughts without being angry. Women talk in a way of requesting. We are softer and can't be harsh. That is why we are sometimes taken for granted. Woman as a leader focuses on teamwork. These qualities are vital to be a leader. Also, women can handle a difficult situation and cool it down.

She tries to stress that women are humble, patience and less arrogant; thereby, their performance can be better than males. Women leaders are helpful and they genuinely focus on their roles and responsibilities. In this sense, women are more suitable for the leadership position. Pooja also says, "I have many women working under me. But as I see, women work more than men do. Ladies do not walk around but gents just walk out of office talk to other gents. We cannot do that; we only concentrate on work." She tries to say that males are less honest in their work compared to females. In this regard, women better lead a team. In the same

way, Ambika says that women have personal abilities but they have not been recognized well. She says:

Personal abilities are there but unable to recognise those. Most of the women are unaware that they can move forward and nobody is there to make them aware. Family support is very less for women. In our society, still women are believed to be only inside the house, work and look after children. Educated families have different stories but with middle-class uneducated families are filled with such a kind of belief. Women in that scenarios are made aware neither by society, political parties nor by the government. No one available to encourage them to understand their capabilities thus they are lacked behind and unable to do something.

This information indicates that women are also equally capable but the culture has made them less capable. They are up brought in patriarchal culture and tradition that discouraged them to challenge males and grab any leading position. Sakuntala also agrees that women are not less capable but they made less capable by the society. In the same way, Purnakala also says, "Women are capable. They have to handle lots of senior post like campus chief, professors and many more but only it is given to women to fill the gap – when no one there to take a post." It shows that women are also equally capable but until and unless there are males to fill the position, women are not given opportunities. Similarly, every other respondent including Samjhana, Maya and Smirti also say that women are capable but patriarchal society is an obstacle to exploring this underlying ability.

4.5. Family Support and Responsibilities

4.5.1. Family Support for Women Leadership

Without family support, it is hard for women to hold a leadership position as she has more home responsibilities than males. If the family is understanding or supportive, she can give adequate time to achieve the strategic objective of the organization. Similarly, in the lack of cooperation from family, she cannot explore optimum potentiality and she can be a failure to effectively lead a team (Rao, 2005). Normally, in the patriarchal society, women are not allowed to work outside the home; they are not supported if they are working in any organization but this condition has been changed now. Due to a supportive family, the women are being able to give much time for office activities. In order to understand family support for female leadership in Nepal, question number 7 was designed.

4.5.1.1. Supportive Family

Sarita says that she has got full family support and she does not need to worry about family responsibility. She can give adequate time for office work. In the same way. Raji says:

They are happy with my success. I have very good support from my family. My mother also was in the academic field and she used to come late at home. From an earlier age, I have seen that type of working culture and I wanted to be like that. Moreover, my husband and his family have supported me a lot. I would not have been here without that support. Family support including husband is crucial to achieving something in life.

In well-educated family, there is no issue regarding family support; they share home responsibilities. Raji's family members are happy in her success and they are supporting as per required. Similarly, Pooja also says, "I have very good support of my family. My husband also

has done a lot for me, otherwise, it was not possible to come here. But the attitude of men will never disappear easily in Nepal." In order to achieve her leadership position, there is an imperative role of her husband and she is sure that without his support, it was impossible her to be in the current leading position. But she says that the impacts of male-dominated culture is still there in some families. Likewise, Ambika also says that her family is very much happy with her success and family members are supportive of succeeding in her leadership career. In the same way, according to Purnakala:

I have good family support. In my personal experience, I should not speak up on this issue. But in general, not everyone has received such a kind of support like me. When guests come home and see my husband is serving tea they surprised. I say to him that he must be an example, so others and our children can learn from that.

This information indicates that her family is supportive but as mentioned by Pooja in some families, there is no support for females. Similarly, Samjhana says, "I am very lucky" because she got supportive family members who have encouraged her for education and career development. Maya says:

In my family, my grandfather was a farmer. My father followed the same profession. They both were not quite educated. Thus, my grandfather wanted to educate us. My mother was from a well-educated family. But had married at the age of 10. I did not have any obligation to do housework. Once I completed my study, I got a job here. It was easy that time to get a job. As most of the women used to stay at home after completion of their study. The society had a culture that women should not work.

Although the society was rigid with females' autonomy Maya's family was different; so that, she has got a good family environment for study and career development. Similarly, Gita says, "To get success in any field family support is vital. I had very good support from family.

Otherwise, it would not possible. Even some of my friends completely had to stop their profession after marriage. But some have started their career after having children and grandchildren." Here, Gita finds herself to be lucky to get such family support. She says that after getting marriage most of the females get problems and they cannot continue their career. In the same way, other interviewees except Sakuntala find that their family members are happy with their success and they are highly supportive. It indicates that there is no issue regarding family obstacle in getting a leadership position and accomplishing their office activities.

4.5.1.2. Unsupportive Family

Out of 20 interviewees, only Sakuntala says that her family was not supportive; so that she had to do lots of struggle in the family. Her family members were uneducated, and they did not know about women equality and career development. But she had keen desire to brighten her future instead of confining into four walls of the home as her mother and grandmother; so that, she escaped from the home to get an education. She managed to achieve higher education and then got into leadership position. Although her family did not support her in the past, now they have realised the importance of education; and now they are happy with her success and they are supporting her.

4.5.2. Women Leadership, and Managing Job and Home Responsibilities

Managing both job and home responsibility is very difficult for women as they have more home responsibilities compared to males in the patriarchal society. Females need to take care of children, do shopping, prepare food, help in farming, and many more. It is imperative to say that most of the women are given much more household activities; thereby, they cannot give adequate time for office. On the one hand, leadership position is highly challenging, and it needs more time, on the other hand, she has higher pressure to accomplish home

responsibilities (Somasekhar, 2017). In this regard, most of the women find it is difficult to manage both home and office responsibilities but as there is a supportive family, then it can be easy to manage. To understand how the women leaders in HE have managed their home and job responsibilities, question number 8 was designed.

Sarita says, "It's difficult. You cannot mix up both things. I told you from 9 to 4 is my work time. So, no disturbance from home. After 4 it is family time. You have to separate. I separate these things." This information indicates that managing both home and office responsibilities is very hard but one has "to separate" time for different responsibilities. In the office hours one has to concentrate only in office work and after office hours, one has to concentrate only on housework. Raji also finds it is difficult to manage those responsibilities but her family members are understanding, which makes her easy to manage. Similarly, Samjhana says, "It is difficult but my family understands and helps me." As family is supportive, there is no problem to manage home and office responsibilities. Anusha says, "As my family is highly supportive, I can easily manage time for job and home responsibilities." Her family is extremely helpful; so that she has not faced any difficulties to manage home responsibilities. The same kind of situation can be found in other respondents as for example Pooja says, "My family is very much understanding; thereby, it is not a problem." As there is family support, her home responsibilities can be shared by others and she could concentrate only on in-office responsibilities. Kalpana says, " It is difficult. I am able to convince the family that I need to go to the job." Her family is supporting her to manage home responsibilities. All of these above-mentioned interviewees find that managing home and office responsibilities is difficult but their family members are highly supportive; so that, it is easy to manage.

Ambika finds it is very hard to manage home and office responsibilities. She is very much busy at home; so, she is "unable to publish more books as I [she] do not get time to study well."

She cannot give much time for her career development as she has tight time. As she finishes office, straight she has to start household activities that make her tired and it affects her office activities as well. Sakuntala is also not happy with much more home responsibilities. Males think that household activities should be done by only females. She says:

It is very difficult. We both work in the same place but once we go home, I have to cook for him and look after his guests. So, like mine others also might have the same condition.

When a child is sick only mom has to feed, make it sleep and give medicine on time. It means it not possible to explain.

Husband and wife both equally work at the office but in the home, a husband does not care about household activities - everything has to be managed by a wife. It makes her very difficult to manage home and office responsibilities. Here, she realises the impacts of patriarchal culture - women should manage all household activities. In the same way, Smirti says that after getting married, home responsibilities have been increased which has created challenges. In order to manage the increased home responsibilities, she has reduced the time for sleep and enjoyment. Shanti says that she has more activities in the house; so that, she is feeling difficulties to manage home and office responsibilities. Similarly, Kumari, Shirjana, Laxmi, Saraswoti and Radha also presented similar kind of experience in managing job and home responsibilities. They find it is very challenging as they have not got as much as family support.

4.6. Equality in the Organizational Level

4.6.1. Recruitment and Selection Process

Different education institutions have their own recruitment and selection process. As there are more competitors, to be selected in the leadership position is complicated. But it is clear that there is no discrimination between male and female to be selected. In government institution,

there is some reservation quota for females but in private sectors, there is no such quota; and male and female have to go through same recruitment and selection process (Sharma and Tamang, 2016). In order to know the recruitment and selection process of Nepalese higher education institutions, question number 9 was designed.

In the institution where Sarita is working does not have any discrimination between male and female in the recruitment and selection process. She says, "There is no difference in this university. Male and female both are treated equally. I haven't experienced any such you know special preference given women to yet. But, both are treated equally. There is nothing in none of the area or nothing has been prioritised for women or males." She has not mentioned anything how an employee is recruited but she has clarified that same process is applied for both genders. According to Raji, there is fair competition in which performance test and interview are used to select the most suitable candidate(s). Both male and female have to go through the same process. Similarly, Pooja also says, "It is fair but women have to come forward. While recruiting, we do group discussion and have a performance test." It tries to say that there is no barrier to females but they are reserved themselves. In competition, they have to show their ability to be selected. There is no discrimination in this institution – the more capable one can be selected to the position; thereby, to be selected females' own ability and performance can be the most determining aspects.

In the same way, Ambika says, "There is no discrimination between male and female." In her institution, there is no such gender discrimination between male and female. Sakuntala also says, "There is same process for both male and female, no discrimination. " The same kind of experienced has been provided by other interviewees including Purnakala, etc. They say that there is no discrimination between male and female in the course of selecting for a new position(s). This data indicates that if females are capable, they can be easily selected in the

position. But Maya has a bit different experience in her institution and she says, "In the case of new recruitment, exams and interviews are taken. If one can pass the written exam, then he/she can use source and force to be selected." She feels a kind of political pressure in the course of selecting a new employee(s). Except for Maya, every interviewee has said that there is no discriminatory recruitment and selection system in their organizations.

4. 6.2. Promotion in Leadership Position

Question number 10 tries to know how the employees are promoted and whether there is any particular discrimination between male and female in the institutions where the respondents are working or not. Morley and Crossousard (2014) say that both male and female think that leadership is not suitable for females and this concept can affect in promotion of women in leadership positions. In order to find actual data in the context of higher education sector in Nepal, this question has been designed.

4.6.1.1. Fair Promotion

The collected information tries to say that most of the organizations everyone is treated equally in promoting in higher positions. The institution where Raji has been working does not have any discrimination between male and female to be promoted. She says:

We have two types in higher-level positions: one in administrative and another is a professor. While being promoted as a professor, it is quite equal between male and female as there are same criteria and if anyone is qualified it does not matter whether you are male or female. In the administrative side also, there is similar ways for promotion.

If any employee, no matter the gender, is qualified for the vacant position, she/he can be easily promoted. No special provision has been made for different genders and there is no

discrimination. In the same way, Pooja says, "It is equal. It has exams, interviews and all added up to decide on promotion. There is nothing like that if you are women you get less chance. I have never felt and seen such a kind of practice." This information tries to indicate that the promotion is decided based on the skills and ability instead of any gender. If a female is capable there is no obstacle to her to be promoted based on gender. In the same way, Samjhana also says that there is no discrimination between male and female; certain criteria determine who is going to be promoted. The majority of the respondents have said that there is no discrimination between male and female to be promoted in the higher position. The institutions have their own promotion criteria that determine who should be promoted. According to Purnakala, after the promulgation of the new constitution, women are getting reservation quota that makes women easy to get promoted. She has just mentioned it but she has not explained in details how it helps. She has not mentioned any gender discrimination in promotion in her institution.

4.6.1.2. Gender Discrimination on Promotion

Ambika says that there is no fair promotion in her institution. She says, " This is the time of source and force. If one has good references that can get promotion and if does not have the power it does not matter how talent is he/she." This information indicates that the one who has a good source and force can be promoted; there is no value of talent and experience. Normally, in a patriarchal society, there is a better source of males compared to females; thereby, indirectly being female there is less chance to be promoted in the leadership or higher position. Similarly, Sakuntal also says that there is a difficulty for females to be promoted in higher position due to male-dominated culture of the organization but it has been perpetually improving and it is not same as it was in the past. In the same way, Maya has also felt a kind of discrimination in promotion because by nature and culture women have less confident compared to males and they cannot show their ability in a performance test. She says:

I feel some kind of domination and unequal activities. Most of the times women are scared to tell the truth and scared of getting transferred. They cannot say that the job is not given by a campus chief or someone else but came through competition. I feel women have less confidence to say something right. However, the new generation is completely different. Many things have changed at ground level. My friends and I came from the generation which believes that women should not dance, sing, laugh, talk loudly and many more restrictions. Due to this culture, a woman scares of a father; scares of campus chief and scares of a husband too. The new generation is different. Even a woman earns more than a man.

A female does not have less ability, but she cannot show due to patriarchal culture. She tries to clarify that in case of getting promotion also, females are being affected by this patriarchal perspective. Further, females have more household responsibilities; thereby, they cannot show their full ability and they are understood as unable to be promoted.

4.6.3. Payment Discrimination

Question number 11 tries to find out whether there is equal payment between male and female for the same position or any discrimination. In the past, females were confined within four walls of the house and they were not given any opportunity to involve in outside home job. As they were not supposed to do the job, it would be hard for them to get a job and if they get, their payment would be lower compared to males in a similar position (Rhee and Sigler, 2015).

In the past, males used to be paid more and females less for the same task but now there is no such type of discrimination in many regions but in case of higher education sector in Nepal, the answers to this question will clarify more.

4.6.3.1. Equal Payment

According to Sarita, there is equality in payment in her organization. In her own words - "Everything is the same. Females are given maternity leave. That is not there for males. Other things are same." Except for maternity leave for female, every facility is the same for male and female. Similarly, Raji says, "It is same. There is no difference. Here competition and payment both are equal." In her institution there is same recruitment and selection process for male and female; there is equal pay for both genders. Pooja also says that in lower labour work, still there might be discrimination but in the higher positions, payment is fixed and no discrimination. Similar kind of information is provided by Shanti, who says that in the farming and household works, there is much difference in wages paid to male and female for the same job and same hour but in the higher position, payment is not different for male and female. Ambika says, "Payment is different according to posts. However, there is no such difference between men and women." It indicates that there is no discrimination in payment based on gender. Other respondents including Sakuntala, Purnakala, Samjhana, Maya, Smirti, Gita, Radha and Anusha also say the same thing that there is no payment discrimination between male and female in their institutions. As a whole, every respondent except Rita finds that there is equal pay in their organization.

4.6.3.2. Discrimination in Payment

Rita has realised that in her institution there is pay discrimination. She says:

In this case (salary) there is no satisfaction. I feel females are paid less compared to males. Normally, let's see in our organization the male who works as HOD [head of the department], some are head of organization, some are head of the department, but there are vast differences in payment.

Compared to males, she has realised that she has paid less. She has seen this kind of discrimination in other organizations as well. Some of the organizations, the difference is very high. In the government job there is a fixed and equal payment set by the government and in the private sectors also there is equal pay for the same position. Payment may differ based on experience, expertise and qualification but not based on gender.

4.6.4. Working Culture

Working culture can be different from one organization to another. Here, the concern is about whether the working culture makes women difficult to fulfil their responsibilities or not. According to Boeri, Patacchini and Peri (2015), gender discrimination is not only limited a country, but it has also spread all over the world; only the discrimination ratio can be different. In a patriarchal society, its impacts can be seen everywhere, which determines everything including working culture. As Nepali society is based on patriarchal norms and values, its direct impacts can be seen in working culture. To know its impacts in the higher education sector to the female leadership, question number 12 has been designed.

The result of the text search query test on the response of this question shows that due to patriarchal culture, still there are fewer female employees in the organization. In addition, the working culture is affected by politics and male-dominated perception. In this regard, although there are no direct negative impacts, it is not suitable for female leadership.

4.6.4.1. Female Friendly Working Culture

As being a female leader, Sarita has not felt any difficulties to fulfil her roles and responsibilities. She says, "There is no discrimination and staffs are quite supportive. I have not found any difficulties to fulfil my job responsibilities." Every staff is supportive that makes a good working environment. In the same way, Ambika says, "There is no harassment in [her

institution]. It is no like other institutions. It is a good place for women to work." She does not have any complaint about working culture as there is no gender discrimination and females can perform their work freely without any hesitation. Similarly, Purnakala also finds a good working environment in her institution. She says, "It is easy for women here. But I do not know about the administrative side. I do not know about that at all. I have seen many unions including women union in this organization and some are guided by politics. "She has not experienced any difficulties but she believes that in other departments, there might be some problems for women; thereby, there are lots of unions."

In the same way, Smirti says, "It is good. We had a childcare center available. But once male campus chief appointed then that was closed. We don't have it now." To assist working mother there was childcare center but it has been closed now. Anyway, she finds there is a good working environment. Radha is also very much happy with the positive working culture in her institution. Females are respected there and she finds very easy to accomplish her roles and responsibilities. Likewise, Shanti says, "If male and female are working in the same position, there is no difference. University has same rule for both male and female. That I feel. If you visit another madam, you may find different experience. They may express based on the problem that they have faced." So, she does not find any discriminatory culture in her organization. Similarly, Kumari, Shirjana, Laxmi, and Saraswoti also find good working culture in their institutions. They do not have any complaint; there is no discrimination between male and female from facility to decision making power.

4.6.4.2. Discriminated Working Culture

Raji says, "In terms of gender, still it is not balanced. Recently women numbers have increased, otherwise, there was very fewer women participation in employment in the past. But we are always encouraging them to join in the organisation." She tries to say that in her organization

there are fewer female employees that makes her a kind of uneasy to work. If there are more females, then the working environment can be female-friendly. Similarly, Sakuntala says:

As this is an educational institution; it is not hard as the private sector. Although, this is the place of well-educated people; attitude towards women is still quite different. But we are well capable to overcome that. In my case also I believe there is nothing I can't do. If you ask somebody about me that might say that I am not a woman but a man. I never leave anything saying I can't do that is why it is quite easy for me but for some women it is hard. It is university but still has that attitude that women can't do. Likewise, women also have some kind of escaping attitude.

This information clarifies that still there is a negative attitude over female leadership, especially in private sectors. They do not believe women until they prove it. People do under-estimate to females' ability and they do not trust them. This kind of culture makes women very difficult to work and explore their optimum potentialities. Similarly, Kalpana finds that there is no good working environment but it is not clear why she is not happy with the working culture of her institution. Further, Anusha also finds unsuitable working environment in her institution due to higher number of males. She says, "There are more males which makes some kind of uneasy for females. In decision making, males voice get priority as there are more males. So, for females the working environment is not so favourable." While making any decision male voice is heard as they are in higher number. Due to male dominance, female have to follow males' decision and working in the mass of males, a kind of uneasiness can also be felt by the female staffs. Further, Kamala also finds that there is no good working culture as it is highly affected by politics. Females are not given space in decision-making process; thereby, she finds a kind of discriminated working culture. She says:

The working culture is totally politicised. Mostly, it is guided by politics. If she/he belongs to my group, it is fine otherwise no. Females are not being participated in decision making because in our college there is an executive board in which there are certain members and, in that board, there is no participation of females. If females are not nominated in the executive board, then they do not have participation. As I am in the portfolio, I am participated there but all others are males and they decide.

Women participation in executive board is very low; so that, women voice cannot be heard. Males are made superior and females are thought to be subordinated to males. In this regard, females do not find easy to work and they do not become motivated to fulfil their roles and responsibilities.

4.7. Causes of low number of participations

There might be numbers of reasons behind the lower number of female participations in leadership positions. Somasekhar (2017) says the women have the qualification but they are either confined within a house or they are in a lower position. Similarly, the report of The Rockefeller Foundation (2016) also found that throughout the business world, there is a lack of female representation in the leadership position. In order to find out the causes of the lower number of female leadership in the context of higher education institutions in Nepal, question number 13 was set. Different respondents have presented their arguments based on their knowledge and experience.

4.7.1. More Household Responsibilities

Sarita says that females have "more commitments at home [and] family" that does not let them to come out in the outer world. This data tries to say that they do not have time to think about job. In leadership positions, they should prepare and participate in the competition but due to

household responsibilities, they do not have much time to be prepared. As they do not prepare, they do not dare to compete. Rita says that in the patriarchal culture, females get married at an early age and they discontinue their education. They have to give more time for the family instead of education and career. This kind of tendency can be one of the key causes of a low number of female participations in leadership positions. In the same way, Kalpana also blames for the patriarchal culture for less representation of females in the leadership position. She says:

Because culturally this is our patriarchal society and from historically it is so. But from the next generation, it will not be so. Females will also come as equal as males. Before our generation, it used to be given less education to the females; after school level certificate (SLC) women used to get married. People had different thinking. Such thinking may change later.

She tries to clarify that in the patriarchal society women are not given equal education and they are limited within household activities. Although the perception has been continuously changing at present, women were not given equal education and they were discouraged to participate in any activities outside home. By culture, they were taught to follow males and respect them. Due to this kind of trend, female participation has been seen very low in decision-making level but the respondent is optimistic in increasing numbers of women leadership in near future as patriarchal culture has been changing slowly.

4.7.2. Socio-culture Environment and Equal Opportunity

Kamala also says, " It is culture. The system of your society is guided by the culture. It is said that opportunities should be given, but it is not a practice. It is only in saying." She believes that females are deprived of opportunities; thereby, there is low female representation in HE leadership in Nepal. Similarly, Gita also says, "It might be due to the socio-cultural

environment." She believes that if there was gender equality in the society, there would not be fewer women participation. Radha says:

They don't have favourable environment. Mostly, women have to manage entire work at home. In this university, there are no such criteria that give women a better privilege. It is thought that women should not be prioritised rather university should look for qualities. But am I just saying they should look for qualities but women with equal qualification should be prioritised. As far as I can remember, four women were kicked out of their job here.

Here, Radha believes that women should get opportunity to get leadership position. In her institution, the first priority is given to males if they have equal quality as females. She wants equal treatment for both genders. In this information, there is a kind of patriarchal smell behind low numbers of female participation. Similarly, Raji, Pooja, Ambika, Smirti, and Purnakala have the same perception that the patriarchal culture is the major cause of the lower number of female leadership in higher education institutions in Nepal. The data shows that there is a cultural barrier for females to get higher positions. If they are given opportunities without any discrimination, they can prove their ability.

4.7.3. Education, Family Background

Saraswoti says:

Firstly, it is due to lack of education. Family background also plays a role. Women are more limited to work and can't see the world outside. They have more responsibilities at home; so, they can't involve in extra activities. But the main reason is the lack of education. However, women participation in leadership has been increasing in this 21st century. Also, many women are being involved in policy-making process.

This information clarifies that education and family background determine women participation in the higher position. Same kinds of reasons have been presented by Maya and Anusha. In the past, women suffered from patriarchal culture but nowadays lots of changes have been seen in culture and belief; so that women are coming in leadership.

4.7.4. Abroad Education

But Shanti has a different perception, who says, "The studious females are going abroad for study, which might be a cause." There is a trend that after completion of higher education, they go abroad for further study. But it is imperative to note that males are also equally going abroad.; thereby, they are lower numbers in the leadership positions.

4.8. Challenges of Female Leadership

Challenges faced by female leadership may not be the challenges faced by male leadership in a patriarchal society. According to Hutchison and Jenkins (2013) women have to face numbers of challenges to run a leadership position. In order to find HE female leadership's challenges in Nepal, question number 14 was set.

4.8.1. Patriarchal Social Norms and Values

Sarita says that it is not easy to be a female leader because they have lots of home responsibilities from caring children to doing all household activities. She says:

It's not easy for a woman. You know that you are also from the same culture; the same place; you must have seen in your family too. We have to take care of the family and this your job also but it has not been that much tough for me. Family support is there. My husband supports me. [Father/Mother] in-law supports me. But, still it is difficult. You have to take care of your child; your children; I have two kids. So, I cannot you know

something they can share with me responsibility share but still as a mother I have my own responsibility. After 4 o'clock, I completely shut down the work of this university and then I have another responsibility

This information suggests that to come over patriarchal social norms and values can be one of the key challenges for females in Nepal. She clarifies that males do only office job and in the home they are free but female have double duty - home and office, which increases their burden and they cannot effectively accomplish their office responsibilities. In the same way, Kalpana says, "The society has created boundaries this and that; they come office late and leave early. People complain that they go to job even on Saturday. This perspective is a kind of torture." As Saruta, kalpana also believes that social norms and values is the challenge. Society does not accept females' leadership and it tries to make her leadership failure. So that, females have to struggle with the entire society and prove their ability and leadership quality.

Similarly, Samjhana says, "The patriarchal culture is the major problem for women to come forward." Other respondents including Shirjana, Saraswoti, Raji, Ambika, Sakuntala, Purnakala, Samjhana, Smirti, Radha and Anusha also find patriarchal culture as the major challenge for women to continue leadership position. This culture wants women to focus on house instead of office. Leadership position wants more time in office but the culture wants her more time in house. So, there is a kind of conflicting situation and persuading family can be one of the major challenges.

4.8.2. Persuading Family Members

Rita says:

In some cases, a husband does not want a wife to come forward. If she comes forward, he has to be known by wife's name. Previously, you talk about jealous, in the family, it could be the main problem. And due to family responsibility, they cannot come out of the

home. If she is married in hi-fi (sophisticated) family, the family wants her not to do any job in other organizations. If she does job, then they believe to be affected their prestige.

She believes that persuading family members can also be another challenge. Most of the families do not want to see their daughter in law to work outside; they want to see them working inside the house. So that, persuading family and continuing the job can be very difficult for the females in the patriarchal society.

4.8.3. Balancing Home and Office Responsibilities

Kamala finds taking care of children can be the major problem of females to continue leadership position. Leading people is a challenging job to which it requires more time but due to responsibility for taking care of children, females cannot give adequate time and they cannot explore their potentiality. Shanti does not see a female friendly environment in her institution whereas Kumari says that balancing home and office responsibilities is difficult. She says, "It is difficult. We have to go to our relatives' house. Need to give time for social and cultural events at the home. Need to give time at office as well. But, I have managed. But it is difficult." This information also suggests that in the patriarchal society there are more home responsibilities for females, which affects in effectively accomplishing leadership roles and responsibilities.

4.8.4. No Challenge

Laxmi does not find any challenge and she says that if women have strong will power, they can lead any organization. In the same way, Smirti says:

It depends. Which women we are talking about. If a woman prioritises family and children, then it might be true. But when a woman is self-centred then a woman can do

anything. Therefore, if everything needs to be pulled together then there is always something missing, one or the other.

The challenge depends on women. Most of the women give much time for the children and household activities; so, they cannot give adequate time for the office. If they try to be self-centred, then they can think about their career otherwise they think about their children and house. Females have a choice whether to create challenges for their leadership positions or not. It means to say that nobody creates challenges except females themselves.

4.9. Solutions/Empowerment

4.9.1. Government's Support

In the patriarchal society, women can be back warded and they need government support and encouragement to come forward (Morley and Crossousard, 2014). In order to find out what kind of support the government has been providing to uplift women in Nepal, question number 15 has been set.

4.9.1.1. Government's Reservation Seats and other Facilities

Government has given extra facilities for women to encourage them for further study and gain more knowledge. Sarita says,

Yes, there are several such facilities in government like if you try for some research grant then separate mark is allocated for female researchers. Similarly, for you know for promotion also there must be some separate provisions some separate marks, extra is given for females. In government, there is.

The government has allocated extra marks for female, which makes it easy to be selected. But in case of promotion in the higher position, there is no extra mark for female and Sarita wants

the government to allocate some extra marks; so that, females can easily reach in leadership positions.

Similarly, Rita also says that securing female reservation quota in all public sector is one of the important works of the government to increase women's presence. It encourages them and makes easy to be empowered. According to Kumari government has been allocating 33% quota for women in every public service jobs and political leadership positions. In the same way, to encourage females to go to school, it has been offering some incentives like free meal, oil, stationery items. Raji says:

Our literacy rate has just improved that was very low in the past. So, the government was more focus on improving that at ground level. We cannot just blame to government as we have women in two higher posts, President and Speaker. There might be other reasons but it clearly shows if women are capable they can take any position. Government has done a lot. In the educational sector like pre-education and women education, the government is doing good. Even our culture has also changed. Before women never used to go to work abroad but now they have gone almost everywhere.

This statement says that the government has done lots of things to empower and encourage women. In the past, there was low female literacy rate but now it has increased. More women are being educated and culture has also been changing. Women are holding higher positions of states, which is due to the government's reservation quota system. Purnkala, Samjhana, Gita and Anusha say that the government has done enough to encourage women. They also talk about reservation quota, encouragement program, incentives for female students and leadership training. After the restoration of democracy, lots of improvements have been made in women empowerment and opportunity areas. As for example female reservation quota in public sector

jobs, incentive to motivate females to go to school and different gender equality awareness programs.

4.9.1.2. Government's Weak Effort in Supporting Women Leadership

Kamala does not find any effective role of government to encourage women in leadership position. She says that in the government there are around 60 ministers but the female participation is nominal. She thinks that government is also affected by a patriarchal culture where is male domination over female. They should honestly give opportunity for women to participate in decision making positions. Shanti says, "I have seen less effort of government. In mathematics, we do panel session and try to see what can be done to increase female mathematicians. We found out that government could be the key to encourage women. There is low encouragement." The government has done something to encourage women to take leadership position but the effect is not sufficient; it has to equally promote women in every sector. But in private sector, there is nothing that encourages women or secures any position of female; thereby, there is low participation. In the same way, Pooja says that in her organization, there is no direct government support but if the women are capable there is no discrimination - they can easily get leadership position. The same kind of perception has been presented by Ambika and Sakuntala who say that some NGOs and INGOs have been doing something to empower women but the government has not done anything. Likewise, Radha blames the government that it has made policy but it is being a failure to effectively implement in practice.

4.9.1.3. No Necessary of Reservation Seats

Kalpana says that government has given reservation quota in most of the sectors but she thinks that it is not necessary as they are capable as equal to males. In her own words, "It has been giving reservation for female. But I think both male and female are equal. Females are also strong. I feel that female should not be given reservation seats even in a bus. Females are as

equal as males." It suggests that the government has been promoting women to hold leadership position by allocating reservation. As there is a reservation, it guarantees women participation.

4.9.2. Interviewees Views about Solution

All of the interviewees were educated women and holding leadership positions. They might better know about women leadership problem and effective solutions; so that, the final question (no 16) was designed to uncover this issue.

4.9.2.1. Family Support

Sarita believes that the solution should be searched from within the home. If she is supported by the family, most of the problems can be resolved. She says:

Yes, that is needed. Female involvement is needed. But I think that starts with family. If they have a supporting family, they will come up. We from this side well began providing them some facilities like providing them you know some types of for example vehicles if they leave the early vehicle to them or a that may not be possible everywhere. I think it has to be something with a family itself.

As a family is aware and equally behaves to females, she can easily fulfil her leadership roles and responsibilities. Same as Sarita, Saraswoti also says, "Of course, women need to have a full support from family. Family should avoid the mentality that women should be at home on an exact time and give sufficient time to improve. First important thing is education and second is support. We can't have anything without support, can we?" She believes that women are discriminated in the family; so that, they are not able to hold leadership positions.

4.9.2.2. *Change in Social Perception*

In the same way, Sakuntal says, "The main thing is that the social perception has to be changed towards women leadership." This information suggests that in order to empower females, gender equality is most. Smirti also realises the necessity of women awareness and change in patriarchal social norms and values.

Kalpana says, "It takes time. It has been slowly improving. Before it was very difficult for female. Now, people are starting to understand; that is why it is improving nowadays." She does not give any suggestion but hopeful that it can be solved in course of time.

4.9.2.3. *Women Education*

Rita believes that the relevant authorities should give much more focus on women education. Although, in her institution, females are given priority while recruiting and selecting process but only a few females give application and they are also not that much qualified; so that they are compelled to select male candidates. Kumari, Samjhana, Purnakala, Maya, Gita and Pooja give much more focus on education. As the females have required academic qualification, they can fight to get leadership positions. Similarly, Shrijana says that "awareness and education can contribute to increasing more women in the leadership position."

4.9.2.4. *Equal Opportunity*

Kamala says:

Every female may not get an opportunity. You also have to serve this organization as per required. You have to give time. As I promoted in the leadership I am working honestly; so that, people cannot blame me that I did not work as I am a female. If it requires to work from morning to evening, I do not mind. If I give priority to home, why should I

hold this position? It is my thinking. As being a woman, I don't want to listen that any complain. If someone complains that is fine, she/he can think from own perspective. One has to give time and be dedicated to the job. Nobody gives you opportunity, you must be hardworking and seek it. We should not fight rather go through systematically. Here, everything is guided by politics. You can easily imagine how is the politics in Nepal.

The above information suggests that women should be empowered to grab opportunities. If females do not have leadership abilities, knowledge about the subject matter, confident and will-power, it is impossible to increase women in HE leadership positions.

4.9.2.5. Awareness Programmes

Shanti says, "To change, mainly awareness programs are necessary." Females should have a kind of desire which should be aroused from the inner heart. If they are not motivated, neither they learn nor they can lead any organization. In the same way, according to Laxmi dedication and honesty in work contribute to succeed women in leadership positions. Likewise, Raji also says hard-working nature should be aroused in women to increase them in the leadership positions. Ambika lists a few aspects like "awareness, encouragement, motivation and cultural changes" which are required to succeed women in leadership positions.

4.10. Conclusion

To sum- up, in the findings of this study many stakeholders are interconnected because often in-depth data is required to investigate life experiences and this research focused on women's experience and challenges in higher education leadership. key themes derived from data using NVivo software were described and backed by participants interview responses. In this chapter eight key themes and its sub- themes were clearly structured and defined to make it simpler to understand for readers. As per findings many new themes and information had emerged than

the available literatures but most of the themes and information were co-related to the literature that is written in the second chapter (literature review). Next, the result (findings) will be reviewed thoroughly and discussed critically in line with related literatures in the discussion chapter.

Chapter 5: Discussion

This chapter critically discusses the various issues related to women experience in their leadership roles in higher education institutes in Nepal based on related theories and concepts discussed in literature review chapter. It reflects on how findings of this study relate to key themes and empirical studies discussed in the literature. This chapter is structured around discussing six main themes which are connected to both primary and secondary data so it can be discussed in detail and draw significant conclusions. The Diagram shows the discussed themes in the chapter below.

Figure 9: Themes selection for discussion

Blue coloured: Themes from Secondary data *Green coloured: Themes from primary data.*

(Source: Created by Author)

In the figure above blue highlighted themes are taken from conceptual framework/ literature reviews whereas green highlighted themes are taken themes from the primary data collected from interviews. In this chapter six main themes are selected for discussion. Some of the themes emerged from the primary data are interconnected therefore they are merged and discussed under one main themes. Such as when discussing barriers rather than separating into sub-themes such as social, organisational, governmental all are merged into one as barriers in women leadership. Likewise, perception and culture are discussed under discrimination and societal barriers. As many issues are interconnected to one another therefore the themes for discussion were carefully selected.

5.1. Women Experience in HE Leadership in Nepal

The research found that the women interviewed had kind of mixed experiences of leadership in HE. Some had not experienced any obstacles to holding leadership positions while others experienced significant difficulties. The following table presents key information about women experience in HE leadership in Nepal:

Table 5: Key data related to women experience in HE leadership in Nepal

Interviewees and answer no.	Key themes of data
Kamala, 1	Leadership is only suitable for males.

Gita, 1	Women leaderships do not get support from male employees.
Shanti, 3	Females are not easily trusted until they prove their ability.
Smriti, 17	Society cannot easily digest females' superiority.
Kalpana, 1	Males are jealous in female's superiority.
Sirjana, 13	There are fewer women employees in most of the organizations.
Laxmi, 9	In decision making, males' voice is heard as they are in majority.
Pooja, 3	Women were deprived of getting leadership opportunities.
Raji, 6	Female can satisfy more employees.
Rita, 2	Females do not have a dream to be leaders.
Saraswoti, 1	Found no significant difficulties for being selected in the position.
Sarita, 4	Society has a kind of discriminated perception.
Kumari, 4	There is some kind of patriarchal social impact that has direct/indirect adverse impacts over women in getting leadership positions.

(Source: Data from interviews)

In term of gender, still, there is no equal treatment in Nepal because of existing patriarchal social practice. The society perceives that leadership is, especially, acquired by birth and it is only suitable for males (Source: Kamala, no.1). As mentioned by Carlyle (2010) inborn attributes or heredities determine leadership and it can be found only in aristocratic families. In this context, the women leaders do not find good support from the society. If any female is appointed in a leadership position, the employees do not support as much as the male leaders (Source: Gita, no.1). Females are not easily trusted until they prove their ability (Source: Shanti, no.3). Great man theory also supports that in order to be a leader, a person must be from the aristocratic family. It represents culture, tradition, upbringings, education, etc and in case of women, patriarchal society does not provide that kind of environment; women cannot be a leader. But this theory has been challenged by behaviour theory which says that leadership quality can be learnt; so, anyone can be a leader. In case of Nepal, women representation in leadership positions has been increasing and currently, president of Nepal is a woman.

Shanti (no 3) says that in the leadership position, if there is male then he does not have any problem related to trust, but females are in the line of doubt. According to Falch (2010), Nepal has been adapting patriarchal culture that makes males superior to females and still there are no more impacts of behavioural theory which means to say that the society is not accepting that females can also be leaders. In this context, if any female is in the higher position, the society cannot easily digest the female superiority (Source: Smriti, no. 17) but this kind of situation has been slowly changing in urban areas where both male and females are being treated almost equally. Due to this reason, some of the women leaders in HE have got challenges. Although the society does not directly discriminate, in the core heart people have a kind of jealousy (Source: Kalpana, no. 1) that affects in getting adequate support. If they find any mistake in female leadership, it can be a bigger issue compared to male leadership. In appearance, everyone shows positive response but in their deeper feeling, they have a kind of uneasiness

that makes female leadership difficult to fulfil their roles and responsibilities. In the patriarchal society, females are supposed to be limited only in household activities (Source: Shanti, no. 13) and males are supposed to do office work, politics, etc. Males earn money and support families but females are limited within unpaid household activities (Evan, 2014). In this context, females become economically dependent to males. In the same way, as only males are involved in politics, females are deprived of getting key decision-making process of nation rules and regulations. In case of the home also, males do major decision and female must obey it otherwise they are considered as disloyal and unsocial women (Morley, 1999). In this circumstance, women do not dare to challenge social norms and values. If any woman becomes a leader, then society cannot easily digest. It represents that women are being systematically made backward and dependents of males.

As a result, there are fewer women employees in most of the organizations (Source: Sirjana, no.13). The HE leaders feel a minority in their own organization. There is no direct discrimination in the institutions - recruitment and selection, pay, promotion and other opportunities are same for both males and females but technically, to make any decision males voice is heard as they are in majority (Source: Laxmi, no. 9,10 and 11). Sametime, males try to pull legs indirectly as they feel a kind of uneasiness to work under males' leadership.

It does not mean that there is women discrimination everywhere especially in the present context because there are significant numbers of respondents who are not experiencing any discrimination. They have found the leadership position is quite interesting and easier. The more they work the more they find it easy. They have found good support from both male and female employees in order to fulfil their roles and responsibilities. This kind of response indicates that Nepali society has been rapidly changing from patriarchal social perception. After restoration of democracy, many things have been done to empower women and

participate them in leadership position. According to Pokharel (2008) Nepalese society has been gradually digesting female leadership and a kind of gender equality has been seen. Women participation in political leadership has been significantly increasing as for example in the local level election of 1997, there were 20% women members in parliament but later on female reservation has increased to 33%; so that, in 2017 local level election, there were altogether 45,000 female participants and out of them, 11,630 were elected which represents 41% of totality. Those women were from different geographies and social backgrounds (UNDP, 2017). The same kind of increased participation can be found in every sector of employment as well and it can be expected that their involvement in employment leadership positions will increase in the coming days.

Most of the women leaders are confident, capable and loyal in their roles and responsibilities; so that, they have not faced significant difficulties to fulfil their roles and responsibilities. In the beginning, women were deprived of getting leadership opportunities (Source: Pooja, no 3). Only the most intelligent women would get that position. It signifies right person in right place in female case. If there are no males available to hold the position, then the females would get the opportunity. It signifies that at that time there would not be an issue about women ability - it would be tested prior to offering a job. Women leaders find that they are more capable than males but they did not get an opportunity in the past; thereby, there are fewer numbers of women leaders in HE.

There are different types of leadership styles but as per the nature of organization, the leader has to apply the most suitable leadership style (Barman, 2009). In HE, women employees are in minority and to pass every decision, there is a key role of the males. In this situation, participatory leadership style is imperative. Females are more capable than males and mostly they are using participatory leadership style by which she can satisfy employees and explore

optimum potentiality to fulfil strategic objectives of the organization (Source: Raji, no. 6). The major assumption of participative leadership theory is that peoples' involvement in decision making contributes to increasing commitment, motivation, ownership and responsibility (Northouse, 2015). Due to this leadership style, most of the female leaders do not have any significant negative experience.

While talking about recruiting in the leadership positions that they have been holding now, most of them say that they did not have any desire to hold such position but they are thereby luck (Source: Rita, no. 2). They are offered leadership positions instead of coming through strong competition. Some fewer women leaders had keen desire to be HE leaders and they did hard work to be selected. At that time, there was not female reservation quota and to fight against males, it was very difficult. But as they were selected, they did not find any considerable difficulties as being females (Saraswoti, no. 1). At present, the situation has been changed because according to Chalise (2017) women are given lots of opportunities; that is why Nepal is the leading position to rectify international documents related to women equality and empowerment. Along with the progress in the field of women awareness and empowerment, gender discrimination has been significantly reduced. So, women leaders in HE have found easy to fulfil their roles and responsibilities. Still there are some kind of difficulties related to perception and thought but such things have been continuously reducing (Source: Sarita, no. 4). Chalise (2017) says that in the near future women in Nepal will not feel any difficulties to handle leadership position as being females.

Overall, still, there are some kinds of patriarchal social impacts has direct/indirect adverse impacts for women to get leadership position and continue it in the beginning phase (Source: Kumari, no. 4). It is imperative to say that HE women leaders' experience can be different as per their own abilities and attributes as well. If they are less capable, they may feel more

difficulties than those who are more capable to lead others. It means to say that female experience cannot be only understood through gender discrimination perspective; there is equal importance of skills and abilities (John, Robins and Pervin, 2010). Although there is mixed response, in the beginning phase, every female leader finds it as a challenging job because they did not have many role models and it might be new for them (Saraswoti, no. 9). Further, they have to work among the majority of the males. Everyone finds a kind of pressure of proving their leadership abilities and responsibilities. Some of the women leaders feel a kind of continuous and unfair pressure from different stakeholders as being them females but some other female leaders do not find any direct difficulties as being women but they are aware that patriarchal social perception can arouse a kind of jealous and backbiting as well.

5.2. Gender Discrimination and Leadership

Gender discrimination indicates a type of distinction, exclusion or preference based on a particular gender (ILO, 2003). It has been one of the major problems in the world. Its ratio might be different but it is imperative to say that in every country, there is a kind of discrimination between males and females. The discrimination can be categorised into two types: direct and indirect. If particular gender is negatively affected by the legal framework, it can be considered as direct discrimination whereas if the neutral rules and regulations negatively affect particular gender, it can be understood as indirect discrimination (ILO, 2003). In the case of women leadership in Nepal, there are both types of discriminations but more indirect discriminations than direct. The following table shows the situation of gender discrimination and women leadership in Nepal:

Table 6: Situation of gender discrimination and women leadership in Nepal

Interviewees and answer no.	Key themes of the data
Pooja, 4	Patriarchal social perception has created direct gender discrimination in women leaders in HE in Nepal.
Ambika, 5	Females were not given quality education.
Purnakala, 9	Indirectly, women are being still discriminated.
Samjhana, 11	In the recruitment and promotion process there is discrimination between male and female.
Sarita, 2	If no male is able to hold a particular position, only then a qualified female gets a chance.
Anusha, 20	In policy level no organization has discrimination but it exists in the practice.
Kamala, 14	Most of the females do not want to be leaders.

(Source: Data from interviews)

The patriarchal social perception has created direct gender discrimination in women leaders in HE in Nepal (Source: Pooja, no.4). It has set a discriminated social framework and it is very difficult to break overnight as it has become culture and tradition. The society believes that women are not born to lead people they are born to follow males' path. This kind of perception

discourages them from getting any leadership position. Most of the respondents did not have the dream to hold any leadership position because of the cultural framework. But due to their intelligence (identified through the position that they hold in school, college and university level education), they were offered those positions. Further, in the past females were not given quality education; so that, there were fewer women in the leadership position in HE in Nepal (Ambika, no. 5). Low participation of women in HE is not only the problem in developing countries like Nepal, but also can be equally experienced in developed countries as well. As for example "women hold only 20% of professorship in UK universities" and the recent publications of gender gaps in the UK clearly shows a problem (Oxford Royal Academy, 2017). In case of Nepal, women in HE leadership is very less which is experienced in course of finding out sample interviewees.

In low wages and unskilled jobs, there is still higher discrimination between males and females but in leadership positions, it cannot be seen. But indirect discrimination can be seen to some extent (Source: Purnakala, no. 9, 10 and 11). Due to patriarchal social practice, there are fewer women employees and if there are internal promotion opportunities, males have higher chance to be promoted as they are higher in number (Source: Samjhana, no. 11). The organization treats males and females equally but there is no extra point for females to be promoted in the higher position. In this case females have very less chance to get any leadership position.

If there is no suitable male to hold the leadership position, then females can get opportunities. It can be said that women get leadership positions by being the right place in the right time because Sarita says that women get leadership position if she is highly qualified or best fit in the position and no male is able to handle the position. Most of the HE leaders have got the positions as they are very much capable. The organizations knew their abilities and offered the leadership position (Source: Sarita, no. 2). According to the participants, leadership position

was not their choice but it was their compulsion (Sources: no. 2). They have accepted it as the job but not as any dream. It tries to say that women were indirectly discriminated in order to get leadership positions. In any organization no rule says women cannot be in the leadership positions but people do not trust over female leadership (Source: Anusha, no. 20); so that, according to the report of World Bank (2017) there is 39.28% women workforce in the world. It is all about the outcome of patriarchal social practice which is long and well-planned discrimination that discourages women from taking any leadership positions.

According to Pounder and Coleman (2002) patriarchal society characterises males and females differently as for example men are regarded as being more aggressive, rational, logical, decisive, confident and independent – showing men being stronger and more capable of taking leadership positions. Women are described as sensitive, warm, talkative, gentle, submissive, and emotional – mostly taken as too weak to lead (Pounder and Coleman, 2002). While nurturing male and female children, in a patriarchal society, people give priority for these different qualities that discourage females to be a leader but encourages males. The expectation of these female qualities can be considered as indirect discrimination. Here, females are not discriminated directly by the organization's rules and regulation; they are discriminated through social nurturing. Due to this, women do not want to be leaders. The respondents did not have any intention to be leaders. Neither they had role models nor they were motivated to hold any leadership position. Rather, they were taught to be kind, loyal, sensitive, submissive, etc. which indirectly discourage them from holding any leadership position. Most of the respondents did not want to be leaders. They thought that as other women they can also be normal employees and work under male leadership. But as the organizations did not get any male to fit in the position, the females were given opportunities (Source: Kamala, no. 14). So that, some of the respondents prefer to say that they got the position by chance and some others say that they hold it by compulsion not a choice. It indicates there was no interest of females to get any

leadership position. Behind this low intention, there is a considerable role of patriarchal cultural upbringing.

5.3. Women Abilities and Opportunities

Women in leadership positions are very low in number not only in developing countries but equally also in developed countries due to glass ceiling - invisible barriers to the minority groups and females to cross a certain level. As for example in the European Commission there were 12% female representatives in 1989-1992, 6% in 1992-1994, 25% in 1994-1999, 25% in 1999-2004, 29% in 2004-2009 and 33% in 2009-2014 (European Commission, 2013). The following table shows women abilities and opportunities in the context of Nepal:

Table 7: Women abilities and opportunities in HE in Nepal

Interviewees and answer no.	Key themes of the data
Kamala, 10	In the higher positions, women cannot be easily appointed
Kumari, 13	There is no visible gender discrimination but organizations do not trust females as leaders.
Shirjana, 9	There is biased social perception.
Raji, 6	Women are more or equally capable to males but not less
Saraswoti, 4	Employees feel uncomfortable under women leadership.

Ambika, 6	Women are sincerer and responsible for the job than males.
Sakuntala, 3	Nowadays, concept about women leadership has been changed.
Purnakal,	Family members are strongly supporting female to get leadership positions and continue their jobs.
Samjhana, 7	Both male and female have been equally working unlike in the past.
Maya, 7	The family is being very much supportive.
Smirti, 5	Nowadays, women are getting the education that makes them able to hold leadership positions.
Gita, 5	Still in some of the rural areas, the society is not liberal and women are being confined within four walls of the house.
Radha, 6	Some women lack confidence but they are able to hold leadership positions.
Anusha, 16	Some of the women need support to enhance required skills.

(Source: Data from interviews)

In the higher positions, women cannot be easily appointed (Source: Kamala, no. 10). Across the world, a kind of invisible barrier exists, and it discriminates females from getting leadership positions. For example, in Nepal, there is no visible gender discrimination in course of

appointing a leader in any organization but due to patriarchal cultural perception, the organization does not trust female on this key position (Source: Kumari, no. 13). The females can be selected in leadership positions if human resource management does not find any male. The respondents advocate on no apparent discrimination in selection and recruitment, payment and promotion but they have complained over biased social perception (Source: Shirjana, no. 9). Mostly, the women cannot get opportunities for leadership positions and if by chance they get opportunity, they are not easily trusted until and unless they prove their ability in action. As they prove by action, then they do not feel that much uneasiness to work but still employees feel a kind of uncomfortable to work under female leadership and they are waiting time to pull their legs down and make them failure (Source: Saraswoti, no.4). The social glass ceiling deprives women from getting leadership opportunities. Some people argue that women are less capable; thereby, they are deprived of opportunity but this is not the truth. If women were not discriminated, they would not be weaker than males. Due to discrimination, they are weaker than males; so that, they should be given priority instead of blaming as weak. By birth, they might get some leadership attributes as males but in the patriarchal society males' attributes can be further developed with the appropriate environment but females' attributes can be undermined and depressed. In this situation, it is unfair to blame females' ability and deprive them of leadership opportunities.

Abilities can be increased as women are given opportunities but the society is depriving them of opportunity and blaming to be less capable. The respondents are not ready to accept the blame of being less capable and they say that women are more or equally capable to males but not less (Source: Raji, no. 6). In the same way, they can be sincerer and more responsible to the job than males; thereby, they can better lead any organization compared to males (Ambika, no. 6). Some of the women are the victim of patriarchal social perception and some are not

getting women remodel. In such condition, they require effective empowerment program but it does not mean that there is no empowerment program.

After the restoration of democracy, lots of NGOs and INGs emerged rapidly, and most of them worked in the field of women awareness and empowerment. Those NGOs and INGOs identified that lack of awareness is one of the key problems of women; thereby, in different regions, women awareness programs were launched. In order to increase their abilities, girls were encouraged to go to school and women were given adult education. Further, they were provided career development training through which they became able to increase their ability. In the same way, they were encouraged to get leadership position to which they were offered leadership training as well. In the family also, they are getting adequate support which is the result of changing patriarchal social perception. If family members do not support, it can be hard to learn leadership abilities and skills.

In the past, the society used to think that leadership position is only suitable for males but now this kind of concept has been changed (Source: Sakuntala, no. 3); thereby, the family members are strongly supporting female to get leadership positions and to accomplish their roles and responsibilities (Source: Purnakal, no. 7). All of the families of HE female leaderships are happy with their achievement. In the same way, family does not believe that household activities are only fulfilled by females. Both male and female have been equally working unlike in the past (Source: Samjhana, no. 7). If females would be responsible for all of the household activities, then she would not have opportunity to develop leadership abilities as she would not have time to involve in any organization or get leadership training or education. The family is being very much supportive (Source: Maya, no. 7); so that, female leaders are being able to manage home and office responsibilities. Overall, it can be said that, compared to the past, women have got good environment to learn knowledge, skills and abilities. In this context, it

cannot be said that only males are able to hold leadership positions; females can also have leadership abilities. In the past, women were deprived of education (Source: Smirti, no. 5) and there were no NGOs/INGs to empower women leadership. In such a context, males would have a better advantage for leadership positions. Women would be considered not to have leadership abilities and they would not be interested to hold leadership positions as well. Although the situation has been changed, still, some of the people think that females are less capable than males. But it is not reality rather it is another form of male domination. If they are categories as unable, they can be discouraged, and males can hold leadership position. Still, some of the rural areas still the society is not liberal and women are being confined within four walls of the house (Source: Gita, no. 5).

The women leaders believe that they are not weak compared to males (Source: Radha, no. 6). They can better lead an organization if they get opportunities. As females were suppressed in the past, some of the women, still, need extra support to develop skills (Source: Anusha and Maya, no.16). Considering this fact, the government, NGOs and INGOs are offering female awareness program. In some of the rural areas, the government has been providing incentives for girls to go to school. Further, to include women in political leadership, there is 33% reservation quota that helps to hold the leadership positions. As they hold the leadership position, they can be motivated to learn required skills. Further, they can be role model for other women. This kind of political reservation quota contributes to developing leadership skills and abilities. It helps them come forward in the society. In the same way, in civil service sectors also, the government has allocated 33% female reservation quota by which women participation has been secured. If there is reservation quota, they can be encouraged to develop required skills and abilities because it ensures their participation. So, opportunity can also be imperative to increase abilities. If they are not given opportunities, then they cannot develop

abilities as well. There is interconnection between ability and opportunity. Nowadays, Nepalese women are getting leadership opportunities and they have increased abilities as well.

5.4. Women Education

Women education has a direct relationship with the development of abilities, skills and knowledge. It means to say that if there is no education, one can be deprived of enhancing skills and abilities. According to Holsinger and Jacob (2009) women education has a direct relation to health, empowerment, employment, prestige, poverty alleviation and gender equality. In a patriarchal society woman are not given good education; thereby, they can be back warded in the society and further they can be dependent on males. Patriarchal society has several cultural factors that make women cripple and confined within four walls of the home (Source: Maya, no 4). Beauvoir (1949) says that women are treated as a slave and they do not have any freedom. In her book ‘*The second sex*’, she has clarified that every social practice has been making female second sex or inferior sex in the society. Later, the feminist movement has contributed to revolt against the masculine domination; so that, they got equality in each and every aspect including education, health and politics. The following table includes key aspects related to women education in Nepal:

Table 8: Women education situation in Nepal

Interviewees and answer no.	Key themes of the data
Maya, 4	Patriarchal society has several cultural factors that make women cripple and confined within four walls of the home.

Radha, 16	In order to come forward, women must be participated in decision making positions in every sector.
Gita, 9	Females are getting equal education nowadays.
Smirti, 5	In the past, there was discrimination between male and female in education.
Maya, 4	Society used to confine women within household activities.
Purnakala, 4	Still the effects of patriarchal culture can be seen in rural areas.
Sakuntala, 5	Now, both male and female are getting an equal education.
Pooja, 5	Traditionally, women education was not given much importance.
Raji, 13	Due to discrimination in education (in past), there is a low number of employees at HE in Nepal (impacts at present).
Saraswoti, 8	It cannot be said that women are less capable than males.
Kumari, 3	The society believes that females are not suitable because they are not supposed to hold that position
Shanti, 6	Females are given opportunities nowadays, but it was not in the past.

Kamala, 6	Females are as capable as males.
Rita, 14	Females are equally capable but society treats them as less capable.
Kalpana, 6	Still women are not given adequate opportunity to develop their career.

(Source: Data from interviews)

In order to come forward, women must be participated in decision making positions in every sector (Source: Radha, no. 16). The movement opened doors for women to get equal opportunities but it is imperative to say that culture cannot be changed overnight; it takes a long time.

Due to feminist movement, at present, women are also getting equal education that contributes them to increase ability (Source: Gita, no. 9, 10 and 11). In the developed countries the number of women graduates are higher than males. As for example over "six million students across OECD countries graduated from higher education intuition with a bachelor's degree; 58% of them were women." (Damme, 2016) In the same way, 60% low performers are found to be males due to negligence and low motivation. According to Pareja (2017), about two-third of world females are literate. Although in developed countries and urban area of developing countries, both males and females are getting equal education; in rural areas of developing countries still a kind of discrimination in education can be seen. As for example according to UN Women (2012), in the rural area, 39% females attend secondary school whereas 45% males but in the urban area 59% females and 60% males attend secondary school. In the rural areas female dropout rate is double than male. This information suggests that women are still not getting higher education as equal as males.

In case of Nepal, there was discrimination in education between males and female in the past (Source: Smirti, no. 5). The society used to think that there is no meaning of giving education for females as they have to marry and go in others' houses. It was believed that there is no use of female education; they need only to learn household activities (Source: Maya, no. 4). This kind of patriarchal social concept deprived females getting of equal education opportunities but the patriarchal social concept has been gradually changing at present. Still the effects of patriarchal culture can be seen in rural areas but it has been changed in urban areas (Source: Purnakala, no. 4). Now, in secondary education, there are more females than males. According to Shrestha (2021), "The past two years, girls continue to outnumber boys with 278,450 female students taking the exam (Secondary Education Examination) against 259,732 male students." Due to this education, the number of the application in civil service examination have outnumbered male applicants. In the fiscal year 2015-16, there were 53.53% females and in 2014-15 it was increased by 60.12% (Shrestha, 2021). Although there are more female applicants, in 2016 only 38% females passed Public Service Commission (PSC) exam. So, there might be some issue regarding quality education of female. Compared to males, females have more cultural, traditional, organizational, home responsibilities, etc. that might be causes of low success in PSC exam. Overall, it can be said that women are getting equal education in Nepal.

A few decades back, there was not equal education between males and females in Nepal due to the impact of patriarchal culture but now people are being aware and they are giving equal education for both male and female (Source: Sakuntala, no. 5). Still in some of the rural areas, people are being much more affected by the traditional belief and patriarchal concepts; they do not have much knowledge about the importance of education for women (Source: Pooja, no. 5). As women were not given equal education, they can be deprived of getting opportunities. Uneducated people can have less ability compared to educated one. In HE of Nepal, there are

fewer women in the leadership position which is due to a discriminated education system which was practiced a few decades back (Source: Raji, no. 13). Every respondent agrees that, in Nepal, there was discrimination in education in the past but now both males and females are getting equal education. Also, some of the respondents say that in the rural area, still there is a kind of discrimination (Source: Pooja, no. 5) as for example boys are admitted in the private boarding school, which is supposed to have better quality and girls are sent to the government school, which is free and does not provide quality education. It means to say that gender discrimination in education is still existing in remote areas but it can be eliminated along with increasing awareness. Except in some rural areas, parents are conscious about the importance of female education; thereby, they send them to school and give as equal education as males. As women become educated, they can grab leadership position in HE but in the past, they were very limited; thereby, in these positions only fewer women can be seen.

In case of women ability, no research says women are less capable than males in general (Source: Saraswoti, no. 8). Every individual can have her/his own special attributes which can be promoted by the culture. Nepali society has male-dominated culture that contributes males to be more capable and females less capable due to unequal distribution of opportunities. The society used to say that she is female and she knows nothing (Source: Saraswoti, no. 4). It was believed that only males can be able to hold any leadership position but females are not suitable because they are not supposed to hold that position (Source: Kumari, no. 3). In this regard, they were made less capable. On the one hand, they were not given education and on the other hand, they were not given an opportunity to expose their ability. In this regard, they were made victimised for a long time.

In the past, women were not given an opportunity to in decision making position but at present women are also treated equally (Shanti, no. 6). Further, in different sectors like education, civil

service jobs and politics, they are given extra priority to motivate and encourage them. In the past, they were deprived of education and other opportunities. If someone is not getting the suitable environment, it is not possible to enhance inborn abilities. The women leadership in HE in Nepal do not agree that females are less capable than males rather they say that females are either equal or more than males (Source: Kamala, no. 6). In the same way, they say that females can better lead a team than males because females are more serious and responsible to their duty. If females are given leadership opportunities, they can easily handle the situation and fulfil strategic objectives of the organization. Women leaders are helpful and they genuinely focus on their roles and responsibilities. The women leadership in HE in Nepal say that women are also equally capable but the culture has made them less capable (Source: Rita, no. 14). They are up brought in patriarchal culture and tradition that discouraged them to challenge existing culture and grab any leading position. Still, women are not given adequate opportunities but not due to lack of ability rather due to the impact of patriarchal culture (Source: Kalpana, no.6 and 14).

5.5. Women Empowerment Situation

It is obvious from the findings that females are dominated by males when it comes to holding leadership positions. Therefore, females require special empowerment to compete with males. Key information related to women empowerment in Nepal has been presented by the following table:

Table 9: Women empowerment situation in Nepal

Interviewees and answer no.	Key themes of the data
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Rita, 16	Nepalese women need strong support to come over social boundaries.
Kamala, 2	Women do not have role models; so, they should be pioneer themselves.
Shanti, 15	Family members are supporting to empower women.
Kumari, 15	Unlike in the past, Nepalese women have, now, developing role models, and getting family support, government's reservation quota and NGOs/INGOs support.
Shirjana, 7	Family support is key to empower women.
Laxmi, 7	Nowadays, family or society is being very much open in case of women education, job, health, etc.

(Source: Data from interviews)

In the case of women in Nepal, they should be empowered for their career development as they were suppressed in the society for a long time period (Source: Rita, no. 16). This might be the transitional period from suppressed situation to equality. They do not find many role models in the society; so, they should be themselves role models (Source: Kamala, no. 1 and 2). After the restoration of democracy, lots of things have been done for women empowerment from government, NGOs and INGs sides (Pokharel, 2008).

Nepal government has played a crucial role to empower women and to participate them in decision making positions. So that, international documents recognized Nepal in the leading position related to women equality and empowerment. There are numbers of women related

international documents which are honoured and recognized by Nepal government (Chalise, 2017). Women empowerment movement in Nepal can be traced back to 1918 along with the establishment of women committee for the propose of women welfare and empowerment. In 1920 significant, Prime Minister Chandra Shamsher Janga Bahadur Rana abolished Sati Practice in which women used to be forced to burn alive with the corpse of her husband. There was continue and slow reform in the sector of women welfare but in the last few decades reform has been seen quantitatively and rapid (Chalise, 2017). The government has ensured 33% women reservation quota in every civil service jobs and political positions as well. In the higher position of leadership also it secures female's participation as for example in president or vice president one position must have a woman. This kind of provision can be found in local level leadership as well for instance mayor or deputy mayor one must be woman. This kind of compulsive quota system has contributed to promoting women in leadership positions. In order to fulfil the political position, the political parties are empowering women from their own sides. In the same way, due to the quota system in public services, the family members highly supporting, empowering and encouraging women (Source: Shanti, no. 15). Now, women can be found in each and every social service sector as well as in political leadership positions. It has contributed other women to come forward and hold leadership positions.

Nowadays, numbers of NGOs and INGOs have been working to empower women in both rural and urban areas of Nepal (Sharma and Tamang, 2016). They are providing adult education, leadership training, awareness about women rights, health education, and so on. These kinds of activities keep a great value to empower women. In the past, it would be odd to hold any leadership position and women did not want that position but now they are being encouraged. Unlike past, Nepalese women have, now, role models, family support, government's reservation quota, and NGOs/INGOs support. These aspects are being significant in order to empower women (Source: Kumari, no. 15 and 16).

In the past, Nepali society was very much included by the patriarchal cultural belief; thereby the family members did not want to see any female family member to work outside home environment. But now the family has given full support to develop a career outside the home. (Source: Kumari, no. 4). The female respondents say that they have got full support from their family to continue leadership position. The support can be different in type as such helping in household activities, giving moral support to accomplishing her office roles and responsibilities, providing relevant information, offering encouragement and so on. Family support can be regarded as one of the major achievements in case of women empowerment sector because if the family does not support females in developing her career; it is very difficult her to challenge family and go against its wise (Source: Shirjana, no. 7 and 8). Now, the family or society is being very much open for women and it has been equally supporting both male and female (Source: Laxmi, no. 7). In different sectors like employment, education, politics, health, etc. the family has been equally supporting females. It means to say that there is no discrimination between male and female. Rather, they believe that females are weaker; thereby, they should be given extra support or priority. As a result, in the higher education, females have outnumbered males. In the same way, women participation has been increased in different sectors and in coming days their participation can be as equal as males in every leadership position.

5.6. Barriers in Women Leadership Empowerment

It is not easy to empower women in Nepal because in course of empowering, several obstacles can appear. According to Morley (1999), culture can be one of the major obstacles to empower women. The following table shows the key information related to women leadership empowerment in Nepal:

Table 10: Women leadership empowerment barriers in Nepal

Interviewees and answer no.	Key themes of the data
Shanti, 14	Culture is one of the key barriers.
Saraswoti, 14	In the past women were not given equal opportunity in decision-making process and education, which significantly affected in women empowerment and development process.
Raji, 14	Compared to urban areas, more patriarchal social impacts can be found in rural areas at present.
Pooja, 14	People in rural area do not want any women empowerment program because they think that it is merely wastage of time.
Sakuntala, 14	Females are discouraged from taking leadership responsibilities in many rural societies.
Kamala, 13	Lower cast and class women face more challenges to be a leader.
Shirjana, 13	Organizations give the first priority to males than females in leadership positions.
Shanti, 13	Still there is a continuation of gender discrimination.
Ambika, 15	There is a lack of adequate finance in empowering women.

Maya, 10	As males are outnumbered, their voice can be significant; so females find difficult to manage their leadership positions.
Smirti, 9	The women leadership in HE in Nepal do not find any discrimination in wages, promotion, and the selection and recruitment process.

(Source: Data from interviews)

Culture is everything that a person does as the social being and it is neither created nor changed overnight (Source: Shanti, no. 14). It is continuously changing based on social needs and requirements but some changes can be very slow whereas others can be very quick. Nepal has been adapting patriarchal culture for a long time period, in which women have been treated as second sex. In decision making positions, women were not participated; they were not given equal education; they were back-warded culturally (Source: Saraswoti, no. 14). In this type of society, it is very difficult to accept any type of women superiority. Uneducated and traditional people believe that there is no value of women empowerment as they think that women's roles and responsibilities should be limited within domestic activities. If they are empowered and they start to work outside the house which it is not accepted. This kind of social perception does not support any program that is related to women empowerment rather it creates obstacle directly or indirectly. It is imperative to say that the stronger socio-culture the powerful obstacle can be experienced. In some of the rural areas, there is strong patriarchal socio-cultural practice but in the urban area patriarchal concept is being weaker day by day (Source: Raji, no. 14). That is the reason, more challenges can be experienced in course of empowering women in rural areas compared to urban areas. Indeed, in urban areas boy and girl get equal education but in urban areas there is a kind of discrimination. It is very difficult to convince parents about the importance of education to girls. People in rural area do not want any women empowerment

program because they think that it is merely wastage of time (Source: Pooja, no. 14). They are very much busy in their own work and they have no realization over the importance of women empowerment in career development.

Social class and caste can be another significant challenge that can be faced in course of empowering women in Nepalese society. From the very beginning, leadership position was used to held by the upper class and higher caste males. As mentioned earlier, females are discouraged to take leadership responsibilities as they are taught that it is not suitable for them; so that they are not interested to be empowered or to learn leadership skills and abilities (Source: Sakuntala, no. 14). Only a few females would accept to be empowered and take leadership positions and those women would be from higher class and caste. Lower caste and class women do not have right to lead any society or organization as per practice as upper class and caste people would not accept any leader from lower class and caste. This kind of discrimination has been existing from long time in Nepalese society. In this regard, lower class and caste women themselves would reject to be empowered on the one hand and the society does not accept their leadership on the other hand (Source: Kamala, no. 7 and 13). So, the rigid power of caste and class can also be one of the key challenges to empower women. Most of the interviewees did not have any aim to hold leadership position; they are in this position which was due to compulsion because the organization did not find any suitable males and she was given opportunity (Source: Shirjana, no. 13). Society has created different types of discrimination such as: first, there is gender discrimination; second there is class discrimination; third, there is caste discrimination. Due to gender discrimination, even higher-class women also can not dare to hold leadership position because, in the patriarchal society, women should follow the decision of males (Source: Shanti, no. 13). In this situation, lower caste or poorer class women's leadership dream cannot be imagined; thereby, the interviewees did not have any dream to lead organizations.

In the same way, the lack of adequate financial investment can be another challenge to empower women. Nepal is one of the poorest countries in the world. Its income is mainly from remittance, tourism and farming. As its income is very low, the government cannot spend much money to empower women (Pokheral, 2008). There are several NGOs and INGOs which are separately spending money in different small projects and that does not become much effective (Source: Ambika, no. 15). If all of those organizations work together, they can have adequate finance and they can manage a large project effectively to empower women. Currently, small organizations are working in small projects and most of the amount is spent in their own administration. It means to say that the amount is not effectively reached to the target group. Morley and Crossousard's (2014) report has found that in South Asian countries, there are many women empowerment programs of NGOs and INGOs but they lack sufficient economy to manage long-lasting and intensive project. If all of the organizations and government accumulate the fund and work together; it would be effective and it would create synergy. Overall, small projects are focusing on similar types of normal programs but for the long run intensive training and development program, there is a lack of sufficient fund.

Likewise, organization culture can be another key challenge because organization's culture is affected by the patriarchal practice that makes females uneasy, unfriendly and unaccommodating (Morley and Crossousard, 2014). Although there is no direct gender discrimination, there are several indirect discriminations. As for example in most of the organizations all of the employees are males and if there is female leadership, her decision cannot be followed. As males are outnumbered, their voice can be significant (Source: Maya, no. 10). If there are more males, female feels psychologically weak as well. Until and unless, there is women-friendly organization culture, it is very difficult to empower women because they do not have any motivation, and they face many negative impacts. The women leadership in HE in Nepal do not find any discrimination in wages, promotion, and selection and

recruitment process (Source: Smirti, no. 9, 10 and 11) but males are jealous over female leadership and they want to pull females leadership's legs down (Source: Smirti, no. 3). Directly, males or females do not show disregard but indirectly they feel a kind of uneasiness and they want to failure of female leadership. This kind of organization culture does not help to empower women. As females are made failure, others cannot dare to get any leadership position and they do not have charm to increase leadership skills and abilities.

Similarly, women perceptions about leadership can be another challenge of empowering women in Nepal (Source: Kamala, no. 16). The women perceive that leadership is very much challenging job and it cannot be done by women. Further, it has more responsibilities but women cannot give much time due to home responsibilities ((Hausmann, 2009). This kind of perception pulls women back from being empowered and getting leadership positions. If women do not have motivation from their inner heart, they cannot learn leadership skills and abilities. Rather they enjoy in their household activities. In this regard, spreading awareness about women skills and abilities to develop career can be the imperative aspect (Source: Shanti, no. 16). Awareness helps to change the perception of leadership and they can be motivated to learn new knowledge, skills and abilities. The respondents used to think that leadership is not their position; thereby, they did not have any dream to be a leader. It indicates that there is a strong negative cultural perception about leadership abilities which are mainly characterised as males' attributes. Until and unless, this kind of perception is not changed, it is difficult to empower women leaders in Nepal.

In the same way, discrimination in the recruitment and selection process can be another challenge to empower women. There is no discrimination in recruitment and selection but normally women are not selected in leadership positions (Source: Kamala, no. 10). The management has a concept that leaders should be males as they have leadership attributes like

boldness, decision making power, influencing personality, aggressive, etc; thereby, females are not selected in leadership positions. Further, it is said that females have much more household responsibilities that may affect in giving time and their performance (Ezbilgin, 2009). Instead of depriving them from getting leadership opportunities, they should be given extra privilege as they were suppressed of patriarchal social beliefs and practices. By organization's law, there is no such discrimination in selection and recruitment but in practice, females are not given opportunities. If they are not given opportunities, how could they be empowered to lead any organization? If they do not get a chance for leadership positions, they cannot be motivated to learn leadership skills and abilities.

Further, families can also be another barrier to empower women. Some of the families are not being able to come over patriarchal perception. According to Rao (2005) in most of the Asian countries, females are not given equal education. In the case of Nepal, still in the rural areas, there is discrimination in education between male and female (Source: Saraswoti, no. 4). Most of the families in rural areas do not want females to work outside homes. They have a lack of awareness about gender equality, career development, etc. They give only focus on their household activities. Such kinds of families reject any type of female empowerment program (Source: Saraswoti, no. 13). Neither they take any initiative to develop leadership skills nor they support such program. But it is imperative to say that in the urban areas, families can be rarely obstacles to develop leadership attributes. Most of the respondents' family members are very much understanding and they have supported as per required. As for example, they are supporting in household activities; leaving them free to work in office; providing moral and psychological support; and so on. If the family members were not supporting, they could not effectively lead the organization. Overall, it can be said that in some of the rural areas families' patriarchal perception has become as a key obstacle to empowering women leaders in Nepal.

Likewise, gender and authority can also be considered as another obstacle to empowering women in Nepal. According to Morley and Crossousard (2014) leadership is associated to masculine attributes (competitive, ruthless and politically networked) and such kind of attributes cannot be available in women as they are perceived as kind, loving and caring. This kind of social perception discourages women to be empowered and hold leadership positions. They believe that leadership is not suitable position to women and they ignore to learn any leadership skills and abilities. Majority of respondents believe that patriarchal social perception is the major challenge to empower women (Source: Responses of no 13). In patriarchal society women are up-brought as secondary or supplement of males; so that, they do not dare to challenge the long-established cultural values. In the home, there is no equal job responsibilities for both male and female. As the males finish office duty, they are free but as females finish office duty, they have more household activities including cooking, cleaning, washing and caring children. The society perceives that household activities should be completed by females and there is no responsibility of male members (Source: Saraswoti, no. 4). In rural areas, still, the boys are asked to read but girls are asked to help household activities. This is a direct discrimination between males and females from childhood. This kind of culture affects long term as well.

Similarly, corruption and political interference can also be considered as another obstacle to empowering women leaders in Nepal. It has affected in employees' selection and recruitment process, performance appraisal process and promotion (Source: Ambika, no. 10). If there is no value of skills and abilities, there is no meaning of being empowered. Compared to females, males are more active in corruption and they have better political power. So that, males have higher chance to get leadership position or to be promoted. In this circumstance, it is very difficult women to persuade and empower. Nepalese HE leadership displays nepotism which does not favour women. If there would be fair evaluation system, then women would also get

equal opportunities but due to nepotism, capable women can also be deprived of opportunity. Mostly males involve in political parties and they get better opportunities but females do not give much interest in politics; they are busy in their household activities (Source: Smirti, no. 7). Further, some of the positions are sold as the result of corruption. Males are considered as the head of the house and he controls the economy as well. He can make decision about economy but females do not have that opportunity. So that, in corruption and political interference, males can be better benefited than females. The stronger this culture the more complication to persuade and empower female leadership. In this regard, corruption and political interference can also be considered as a key obstacle.

Chapter 6: Conclusion, Recommendations and Future

Research

This research was focused on investigating women leaders working in higher education and their challenges and empowerment situation in Nepal. Very few research has been done in Nepalese context and around women educational leadership topic. It is really important to research on this topic of women leadership in education sector because women's participation is vital for countries economic and social prosperity and education sector is the main starting point for that prosperity (Acharya, 2020).

This chapter presents a gist of the research findings which make readers clear about the overall outcome and how those outcomes have managed to answer the research questions set out at the beginning of the thesis. There is lack of sufficient research on the topic in Nepal mainly using in-depth interviews of females' perspective and their experience of leadership in HE. Therefore, this research aimed at women leadership experiences (getting into leadership role and leading) in higher education institutes in Nepal. To make it simpler research questions and findings are highlighted of this research followed by contribution to knowledge, contribution practice, recommendation and future research.

6.2. Research questions and findings

In this conclusion chapter all four research questions are revised to see if they have been answered thereby objectives of the research set are fulfilled. Table below shows the result of the research data according to research questions.

Table 11: Research questions and findings

<p>Research question one:</p> <p>What are the women’s experiences about leadership positions in HE in Nepal?</p>	<p>Despite have overall good experience many women feel still patriarch culture is playing key role on shaping culture and policies: making uneasy for women. Most women are in leadership positions more by circumstance rather than deliberate attempt and planning. Women are equally capable but other responsibilities coming on their way. Main issue here is not after getting into leadership position but before getting into (journey) in leadership positions.</p>
<p>Research Question Two:</p> <p>What are the women's perceptions of gender equality in HE leadership?</p>	<p>Women are still trusted less to lead, face indirect discrimination form by traditional belief, still indirectly women are taken as good in households only. Better policies in place but psychological inequality in behaviour and indirect discrimination are still there. No discrimination in payment but promotion is where women come in second choice.</p>

<p>Research Question Three:</p> <p>What are the main factors/barriers that prevent women from taking leadership roles?</p>	<p>Despite being equally capable as men women encounter many barriers along the way. Women have to prove more, facing many organisational, personal and societal challenges and that fuelling to have less desire on leadership positions.</p>
<p>Research Question Four:</p> <p>What can be done to increase women leadership in HE?</p>	<p>Government quotas systems, awareness programmes, and policies are having good impact but in slow pace. More social awareness programme, creating role model, amending policies to help women balance work-home responsibilities and good education at ground level would help to bring the change fast in right direction.</p>

Research question one: What are the women’s experiences about leadership positions in HE in Nepal?

Overall women had a mixed experience regarding their experience once they got into leadership positions. But stories are different if we see their overall journey to be there; it is harder than men who made a journey to the same position. It is clear from the study that women are facing many issues to come to leadership positions from family, institutional culture and societal perceptions. Direct result of facing these issues is that women sometimes have

encounter doubt on their ability to lead but it is not true once they take a leadership role. Overall women's experience in leadership positions was dependent on many issues. In the past, there was no equal leadership opportunity between male and female which was due to the existing patriarchal social norms and values. Traditionally, females were seen as subordinate to males, as a result, leadership roles were mostly given to the males. But, at present, this type of social perception has been changing and gender equality movement has got priority in every sector including in leadership opportunity. It is imperative to say that employees do not easily trust women as a leader until she proves her ability through work. If there would be male leadership, everyone would respect, trust and cooperate him but female leadership does not get this kind of environment. In this regard, women leadership has been facing difficulties in achieving the strategic objectives of the organization in the context of Nepal. This conclusion is one of the major contributions of the research because it helps related authorities to pay more attention on changing patriarchal social view instead of merely bringing changes in the rules and regulations.

Research Question Two: What are the women's perceptions of gender equality in HE leadership?

Some of the women leaders in HE, Nepal find that fulfilling their roles and responsibilities is difficult due to unnecessary backbiting, jealous and uncooperative nature of the employees over female leaderships. Both male and female employees feel a kind of uneasy if there is a female leader. They do not dare to directly express such uneasiness but it can be depicted through their behaviour. If the employees are not satisfied with leadership, it is a very difficult for leaders to fulfil strategic objectives of the organization as they do not receive constructive feedback and positive support. There are many policies in place implemented at organisational and governmental level to tackle the gender inequality in workplace. However, many

participants were facing indirect practices against women despite policy says otherwise. Mainly, when promoting women to higher positions traditional perceptions affecting and making women looking like not being capable for higher positions. There are very few experiences of difference in payment in higher educations in Nepal despite many literatures pointing different direction. Another main issue women have face is working culture of institutions. All institutions have policies in place make better workplace but very few institutions have female friendly culture to promote their women employees. Still females are perceived to be house caretaker by men in organisations and treating indirectly in that way despite being in same positions as women.

Research Questions Three: What are the main factors/barriers that prevent women from taking leadership roles?

This research question does not stand in isolation as this question cover some of the issues from research questions one and two. Barriers that women are facing in leadership positions in HE come under three categories. These are Organisational level, Societal level and Personal level. Especially in context of Nepal main issue was more at the ground level than the top. Social norm and its practices were playing key role on shaping organisational culture, policies, and practices. Likewise, patriarchal believe rooted in the society has always been main cause to limit women capacity in different psychological and practical ways. At starting traditional belief in the family with low education level is making harder for women to get a good education, have a proper training, go out and explore new environment thereby less women were there to fulfil leadership positions even though positions are vacant due to quota system. Similarly, it is quite interesting to find out that women already at the top positions are also struggling due to less family support. Without family support and belief women in higher positions find hard to make time for new training, for networking and attend important

meetings. As a result, women are likely to look more outdated when it comes to skills development. Managing home and work responsibilities was one of the main barriers highlighted by almost all participants. The family does not let females to participate in any leadership training or empowerment program. Further, some of the societies believe that inferior class and caste cannot be a leader. A woman from lower caste and class cannot rule others as she is supposed to be inferior. Due to this kind of social perception women feel inferior and they are not motivated to hold leadership positions. Even after getting such a position, it is not easy them to fulfil their roles.

Most of the civil service organizations, the leadership position is fulfilled by internal promotion in which money, political power, and muscle can be used to be promoted, and mostly such things are used by males. In this sense, still the organization culture is not favourable to women in getting leadership positions. The respondents are very much confident that females are not less capable than men; they are either equal or more capable than males. The major issue is the opportunity of getting leadership positions. Here, it is notable to say that females have reservation quota in every political position and social service job but in case of promotion, they do not have any priority.

Research Questions Four: What can be done to increase women leadership in HE?

Traditional Nepalese culture believes that women should not get an education and should not involve in any outside job. This culture has made them submissive and suppressed. In fact, they were not unable, but they were made so. In the rural area, still, women are not supposed to be leaders or employees; they are supposed to confine within household activities. Therefore, to tackle real problems as highlighted by above three research questions that women are facing required practical solution. problems are often solved better by those who faces them. Participants were happy to share their though and felling on the issues. According to their

views, to increase women participation there should be equal effort from families, government and women themselves. Mainly government society should focus on creating awareness on the issue. After that women would be seen equally in household thereby, they get extra time for their career and work. Until then organisation should focus on making policy and work environment women friendly to manage work home responsibilities.

6.3. Contribution to knowledge

This study is purely qualitative research and based on higher education for that reason philosophy and approaches were designed to address qualitative research. Therefore, finding of this study has its own limitations such as if the study is conducted in different time with using different approach and methods can have slightly different result. But as this study has collected data by in-depth face to face interviews and has managed to get rich in data. This study has managed to made number of contributions to the field of women leadership in HE in the context of Nepal.

- ❖ Women leadership is complex and need bottom-up approach to improve: From this study is has given Indication that women leadership issues in Nepal is less about policies in organisations level but more about family and social awareness issue. Comparatively fewer research has been done in Nepal and even less in HE (Female) as a result there are fewer literatures available therefore literatures are compared from similar neighbouring countries in South Asia. Therefore, study itself is a contribution in the field. Also, even though from literature and conceptual framework themes were drawn earlier, finding's themes were keep emphasizing to ground level such as girls' education, health, family, patriarchal culture and so on. In most cases government has a quota system but there are less capable women to fill those quotas suggests bigger

issue in bottom of the hierarchical leadership journey. Therefore, in develop countries women leadership are being discussed on the issues such as qualities and effectiveness whereas in countries like Nepal still more work needs to be done about basic health and how women get good educations at the grass level (Schools and colleges).

- ❖ Excluding males' views: Another contribution of this study is that still most of the decisions are influenced by men directly or indirectly. Men's views were playing a key part in the research even without participating directly because even before taking part in this study some participants wanted to ask to their husbands. Patriarchal culture has affected almost everyone and to explore the issue in the future research men point of views equally matter in getting clear picture of the issue. It is because most of the time men as a father and as a husband are taking most of the decisions on women career selection too. Therefore, it is obvious that research in the Nepalese context (rooted by patriarchal culture) is completely different to most of the other context.
- ❖ Research direction: Another contribution of this study is that clear direction for the future research in the related field. Future research can be conducted including more institutions and males' perspective to have more generalisable data. Also, relation of patriarchal cultural view and women career could be a better research ground to get this issue more in-depth research.

6.4. Contribution to practice

Analysis and findings of this study has managed to provide some number of useful recommendations to put in practice for many of its stakeholders such as women leaders/ aspired to be a future leader, Men leaders, NGOS and INGOS, Family, society and policy makers (organisations and government). However, recommendations are only for directions and constrain brought by its limitation in this study should not completely be ignored.

- ❖ Women in already in leadership or aspired to be leaders in HE should make a good planning as they will encounter many barriers along the way. It is always better to be or find some female role model so societies perceptions can be changed and will be much easier in the future. Similarly, internal networking is very important to keep updated and make leadership effective. Also, making sure skills are updated time to time is another key issue highlighted by the study. As we eventually become what we think applies in leadership too. Women should aspire to be mentally strong and do not doubt on their skills and qualities to be a leader.
- ❖ Men in society and in leadership should be aware that women leadership styles bring many new qualities such as empathy and caring that will help to make working place better and prosperous in many ways. Their participation will have direct positive impact on success of organisation, society, economy and family. Therefore, encouraging women to leadership is better in many ways.
- ❖ As stated above family will be better off as women is involved in leadership positions. Not only economically but also socially will be beneficial for a family. In family it will help to reduce the burden in one person economically and have shared responsibilities. Therefore, family should encourage women for education, training and look for leadership positions. When family gets better then society will get better eventually. Again, people in society should give helping hand in women to overcome their challenges so all can have a better place to live.
- ❖ Policymaker such as government and organisation can see where women are struggling and which level they are struggling thereby make or amend policies to encounter those issue. By doing those synergy can be created and prosperity for all can be easily achieved.

- ❖ From this study NGOs and INGOs can learn and make sure they can put their resources to directly impacted areas to have strong effect on causes thereby help women to overcome the barriers in all different levels.

6.5. Recommendations

Although the number of women in leadership positions has been increasing due to social awareness regarding gender equality, focus on education, government reservation quota and the effort from several NGOs and INGOs, there are lots of things to do to increase women in leadership positions.

There is reservation quota for women in political leadership but such privilege cannot be found in employment leadership sectors. Although the government has allocated quota for women in civil service employment, it does not ensure their participation in leadership positions. Moreover, most of the organizations fulfil leadership positions from their internal promotion method but in such promotion, there is no extra point for women. Such reservation is significance to encourage women for leadership positions. It is important because women did not get a good education in the past; they were discriminated and there was no female role model as well and still they have more household activities. In this situation, they cannot compete with males and therefore opportunities should be given to bring them forward. Currently, the government has allocated reservation quota only in political sectors and civil service employment but in private sector there is no reservation; So, it would be better if reservation is allocated in public sector jobs as well as employment leaderships; so that, women would be empowered and the number of women in leadership would be significantly increased.

A large scale of women awareness and empowerment project is required. Such a project should devise long term planning and strategies to ensure gender equality in every sector. It means to

say that only a unified project can be better effective to aware and empower women. Currently, government, NGOs and INGOs are working separately and they are spreading the financial resources. Mostly, they have a similar type of projects and short-term vision. They are working only to show to the society instead of genuinely women empowerment. Further, they spend most of the finance in their internal management and only a little amount is spent for the target groups. In this condition, if there would be a unified project and every authority work together, it would be effective to empower women and increase their participation significantly in leadership positions.

The Major focus of the authorities should be in increasing leadership skills and abilities. If females have better abilities, they can have a better chance to be selected and after getting leadership positions they can easily fulfil their roles and responsibilities. If there is weak female leadership, she has to face lots of difficulties. It means to say that although reservation quota is required, it is not only the solution because if they do not have required skills and abilities, they cannot continue the position and it will have several negative impacts for organizations as well as on female leaders. In this regard, related authorities have to focus more on female leadership skills and abilities which can be developed through different awareness, empowerment, motivation and training programs.

Similarly, in the patriarchal societies, women are supposed to engage only in household activities from childcare to preparing meals. Mostly, males do only office work and after office hour they are free but females have a double duty - at home and office. Due to more work in the house, females cannot approach in any paid job. As they are busy in household activities, they do not have time to prepare for job competition and even after getting a job, they cannot effectively fulfil their job responsibilities due to tension of excessive household activities. In order to explore their optimum potentiality and succeed in her leadership career, they are

required to get suitable home environment. The family members have to share household responsibilities and support them in career development. In order to change the home environment, government, NGOs and INGOs should increase more social awareness. If every family member is responsible and supportive, this problem can be solved and the number of female in leadership can be increased in every sector and they can be successful in their roles and responsibilities. Which is beneficial to females, families and societies as a whole in long-term.

In the same way, females should increase the level of confidence that they can also be leaders. They have the ability but it is hidden inside; they do not want to expose due to lack of confidence. Currently, there are several role models in every sector and they should look at those successful women. Some of the women think that they are women and they cannot do but this is the wrong concept, it must be changed and should understand that both genders are equal. If there is any discrimination, they should revolt against it. They can face discrimination everywhere from home to office but they should not tolerate it. In order to increase this kind of awareness, the government can give female awareness of education at school level. Also, the government should pass strong laws against any discriminations to women.

Finally, females' early marriage social tradition should be stopped. In most of the rural families, the parents marry their children in early age. So that, especially for bridegroom, family responsibility can be increased, and they cannot complete their education. Their key focus can be to do household activities instead of education and career development. Considering this fact, early marriage system has to be stopped to which government, NGOs and INGOs should spread awareness about the significance of female education in career development.

6.6. Limitation and suggestion for Future Research

This research is limited to women leadership in HE institutions in Nepal. It has identified women leadership experiences and challenges in this sector and its conclusion can be merely generalised in the HE sector, but in other sectors, it will not be worthwhile to generalise. In other sectors, this research can be used as a reference. It is imperative to say that in different settings, there might be various types of experiences and challenges; thereby, all of those sectors should be brought into the issue of study. For example, experiences and challenges of women leadership in health and social care sector, security sector, journalism sector, etc. can be future research issue. As it is studied separately, a better insight can be gained and that contributes to increasing women leadership in every sector of the society.

In the same way, education is imperative to empower women and increase their participation in leadership positions. It means to say that women education is also an equally important issue that should be brought into the issue of study to better understand women leadership situation in Nepal. This study has slightly touched this issue but it could not go in deeper level as it was not the primary concern of the research. In this regard, this research has not offered a detailed insight of women education in Nepal but in order to better understand women leadership, it should be understood; thereby, future research should focus on women education in Nepal. Indeed, there is a close relationship between education and leadership. If women are deprived of a good education, it is very difficult for them to get any leadership opportunity. As for example, in employment sectors, there is education criteria for applying in the leadership position. In a patriarchal society, women are not given former education and they are not supposed to be leader. To empower women and increase their number in leadership positions, they should be given quality education. In this regard, depth research about this issue is required. There are several articles on this filed but there is no research that has identified

women education situation in different classes, castes and regions. If it is identified separately, the government, NGOs and INGOs could better target the particular group where women are more deprived of education.

Another future research could be related to changes in patriarchal social perception and practice in Nepal. Women leadership is directly affected by the social practice and along with changes, women situation could also be different. This research has included some of the social changes but it has not been able to make a deeper investigation over them. At present, there are rapid changes in social perceptions and practices on women. Their voice has been heard and to empower them, lots of organizations are perpetually working. It means to say that the society is being liberal to women and there is a concept of gender equality at present. Along with changes in patriarchal perception, women situation in education, health, leadership, etc. can be changed. It can be said that women leadership situation is the mirror of the social practice; thereby, it would be better any future research to focus on patriarchal social changes in Nepal. Changes may not be seen equal in every social group; it might be different based on area, class and caste. In this regard, the future research would be better to study changes in patriarchal social practice based on different social clusters.

Thus, women experiences and challenges in different sectors, women education in various social clusters and changes in patriarchal social perception are the key areas related to women leadership to be focused on future research. If these areas are effectively covered, women could be better empowered and their numbers can be increased in leadership positions.

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Appendix

Appendix 1: Interview Questions

Leadership Experience

Q. N. 1. How do you describe your experience as a woman leader working here?

Q. N. 2. What made you decide to embark on this leadership position?

Culture and Perception

Q. N. 3. How do you find males' perception over female leadership?

Q. N. 4. How has the patriarchal culture been affecting female to hold the leadership position?

Women Education and Ability

Q. N. 5. Do you think females are getting equal education as the males? Or there is some kind of discrimination?

Q. N. 6. What do you think about women ability to lead the team? Do you think it is different than men or do you think women are more capable?

Family Restrictions

Q. N. 7. What is your family response regarding this position? Do they support you?

Q. N. 8. How do you manage both job and home responsibilities?

Organizational Barriers

Q. N. 9. What is the recruitment and selection process of this institution? Is there any discrimination for female? Did you find any difficulties to be recruited as being a female?

Q. N. 10. How does this institute treat for male and female while promoting in the leadership position? Any discrimination?

Q. N. 11. Do you find any discrimination in payment between male and female in this institution?

Q. N. 12. How is the working culture of this institution? Is it suitable for female leadership or patriarchal culture has made female leadership difficult to fulfil job responsibilities?

Government Support

Q. N. 13. What do you think about government support to encourage women to take leadership positions?

Gender Discrimination

Q. N. 14. What are the major challenges that particularly the female leadership has to face in course fulfilling their roles and responsibilities?

Empowerment Situation

Q. N. 15. What might be the key reasons behind a low number of women leaders in higher education institutions?

Q. N. 16. In your opinion, how could women's numbers be increased in leadership position

Appendix 2: Participant Consent Form

**Title of the Study: Women in Educational Leadership: Challenges and Empowerment
Situation in Higher Education of Nepal.**

Researcher: Amir Miyan (B00298145)

DBA (Doctor of Business Administration) Research Student

University of the West of Scotland

Paisley, Scotland

UK.

Many thanks for agreeing to participate in my research project and your assistance is much appreciated.

Participant's Statement

- I am sufficiently briefed about the project and given a chance to ask the questions.
- I confirm that I clearly understand the information provided about the project.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and I have the right to withdraw at any time.
- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
- I understand that this project has been subject to ethical reviews provided by the University of the west of Scotland.

Hereby, I agree to take part in the above project.

Participant's Name: _____

Date: _____

Signature: _____

Appendix 3: Ethical Approval Letter from the University of The West of Scotland

Amir Miyan
B00298145

27 July 2017

School of Business
and Enterprise
Paisley Campus
Paisley PA1 2BE
Scotland

Tel 0141 848 3000
Direct 0141 848 3932

Dear Amir

Ethics Application Number: B&E208

Title of Study: Women in educational leadership: empowerment and challenges in higher education in Nepal

The School of Business & Enterprise Ethics Committee has considered your application and we are pleased to inform you that your application has been successful. Therefore approval to conduct the research as outlined in your application has been given.

We wish you well in your DBA research.

Yours sincerely

Dr A Kourouklis
Chair
School of Business & Enterprise Ethics Committee

Professor Malcolm Foley
Dean of the School

Appendix 4: Some examples of the Thematic Analysis code in NVivo

(Producing a Thematic 'Map' of the analysis).

Text Search Query - Results Preview

Appendix 5: Interview transcription (Sample)

File: 11 **Position: Manager head of exam section**

Age: 47 **Marital Status: Married**

Children: 1 **Institution: (hidden for confidentiality)**

[Information conversation where interviewer explains about research topic, background and what it tries to achieve. The participant is assured of confidentiality and asked to sign the consent form. Also, asked for permission to recording].

Interviewer [Q. 1]: Ok let me start. How long have you been working?

Respondent: In this university it has been 20 years.

Interviewer [Q. 2]: How do you describe your experience as a leader?

Respondent: I have been doing what I supposed to do. How you feel is affected by how the working environment is. I have to give 9-5 for the examination department I am working. We have separate department and not allowed to go outside as well. Even, we are not allowed to have more interact with working colleagues in the same department. It is because, when we talk to friends, unknowingly, we might disclose confidential information. I give more time compared to others as I live locally. When most of the staffs go to home I still stay in the office and stay longer as much time as needed. In terms of work, we have always worked as a leader and teach our juniors. That time I was young thus I could give more time for the job.

Interviewer [Q. 3]: what is your educational background?

Respondent: I have done double masters, one in mathematics and another in sociology. My background is humanities not science.

Interviewer [Q. 4]: What made you decide to embark on this leadership position? Had you thought of this before?

Respondent: No, I had never thought of this field. I was doing master then I had to get married. So, I could not continue my study. Then I started teaching mathematics at school up to class 8. This university was quite small that time. The university was looking for warden for girls' hostel. My husband used to work here in environmental science department as a lecturer, now he is professor, he also used to work in both boys' hostel as a warden and also as a lecturer. He had go Vienna to do his PhD. We had small child that time. Next, University offered me to be a warden as I already had bachelor degree and was doing my master. But in the university, we have a rule that only university staff can work as a warden. Thus, I was offered to work in examination department too. I think I got this work just by staying at home. I would like to thank to the teacher who helped me but I have shown the work better than expected. I have proved myself.

Interviewer [Q. 5]: How hard or easy to work as being women?

Respondent: It is not hard. Only thing is that when meeting is arranged, male with equal position gets invited but not me. I am not involved in those kinds of meetings. I have told them many times that they are avoiding me. I have no complain about any other behaviour. We have work in our exam section maximum till 11 pm, me and other boys, but never felt any inappropriate behaviour. We worked as friend, talk as if we all are same. But only thing I feel is that I never invited to the meetings.

Interviewer [Q. 6]: Why do you think is that?

Respondent: I don't know. May they think that only male can make decisions and get work done. But now they have given me a full responsibility of one whole school of law. In that

school, we have dean as a head in teaching department and in administrative department side, I am the head. I have not started to work yet but soon. I will be the one to handle all the staffs in that department.

Interviewer [Q. 7]: it means you have huge responsibilities now?

Respondent: yes, it has increased.

Interviewer [Q. 9]: How do you see women's ability to lead the team?

Respondent: I have many women working under me. But as I see, women work more than men do. Ladies do not walk around but gents just walk out of office talk to other gents. We cannot do that, we only concentrate on work.

Interviewer [Q. 10]: In your view, how women are perceived by men in regard to females leadership?

Respondent: We have male dominated culture. Women are treated as a second-class citizen. Even my husband, who is well educated, has done PhD and professor, has that kind of attitude. For example, we both come to work at same time around 9 and leave office at exact same time but once we enter a house he has his own gents style and I have to work on domestic work such as cleaning, arranging and cooking. However, although women do double work, no man feels that way, neither my husband nor my senior bosses.

Interviewer [Q. 11]: Have you ever raised that issue at home?

Respondent: I do that frequently. Only thing he has to say is that 'No, I have not done that, never feel that way'. Men act like we can understand nothing. But in my personal view, no woman is less capable than men.

Interviewer [Q. 12]: How would you like to describe yourself as a leader?

Respondent: I am punctual and loyal at work. I always give 100% at work. I never cheat anyone. I am having this kind of behaviour from early age. When I was in college level in Janakpur, we had to wear 'saree' and gents used to stay by the gate and flirt to us. That time, lots of girls used to bow their head and walk away. But I have never done that and do not like to do that at all. I have always been walking tall. In my family, there is no brother, we only have sisters; that is why, my father used to treat us like boys. Thus, I have done almost every stuff that boys do and never feel low being girl. By that reasons, I am so strong. I have one daughter, she also has developed that kind of strong behaviour. She never scares to speak-up, stay alone at home and feels nothing difficult. My husband is also quite happy that I am strong and can stay at home alone. Today also, I went to USA. I think, if I don't do anything wrong, why should I scare.

Interviewer [Q. 13]: How equal do you think the promotional process in the organisation?

Respondent: It is equal. It has exams, interviews and all added up to decide on promotion. There is nothing like that, if you are women you get less chance. I have never felt and seen such a kind of practice.

Interviewer [Q. 14]: How has the patriarchal culture been affecting female to hold the leadership position? what men think working under women?

Respondent: I have never felt such a kind of behaviour on my male sub-ordinates. But other male colleagues who are on equal position feel bad as I say something to them. Recently, I have experienced same issue. I become professor just around 2 months back. While competing, we had 8 candidates with only one lady, that is me; and only 2 seats were available. Me and one male colleague were selected for the post, then other colleagues, we had been working in same department, suddenly changed their attitude. They started avoiding and even talking to me – I think, they thought that this will evaluate us. But once they heard that I was transferred

to another department, they started to come and talk to me. If there were ladies in that case, they also might feel but gents felt more. I have seen this everywhere, even in America; where is lady president in America. Recently, the woman should be winning the presidency also did not win.

Interviewer [Q. 15]: Why women are less in leadership position?

Respondent: In my opinion, it is due to childhood environment. How hard the situation of a family is; Sons are sent to private school whereas daughters are sent to governmental school. Works at home are differentiated between son and daughter. Women were not able to move into leadership positions is because they came from the environment that make ladies to do more domestic work. But new generation has got an equal opportunity; girls are sent to schools and getting married after completion of their study. We will definitely have more women in leadership in future. In past, it has happened all because of environment of family, attitude regarding that after marriage all work should be done my women; and men even should not even change a diaper of his child although he just sitting there doing nothing. Women are not moving upwards in south Asian countries is because that they have to do all the work. While at work they work equal to men; At home, men read newspapers, watch TV, Laptops and work on the internet but women have to look after family and children. If a woman focuses more on professional life, her children do not move to right direction. As women can't give to children; their study plummet. Parents might go higher but children go into bad direction. It means, women have to manage both role. But now, I have seen that as woman works; man does house work. Women in next generation will go up.

Interviewer [Q. 16]: How happy is your family with your success?

Respondent: All members are very happy. Even my dad and mom does not have a son, they see me as a son; I have got good government job – it very proud moment for my parents.

Interviewer [Q. 17]: What about support?

Respondent: I have very good support of my family. My husband also has done a lot for me, otherwise, it was not possible to come here. But attitude of men will never disappear easily in Nepal.

Interviewer [Q. 18]: Women are lacked behind by many reasons, what is your thought on that?

Respondent: It is right in some cases. Some women feel that they are women and cannot do as they want. In my family, I see lots of women that they have completely left studying once they are married.

Interviewer [Q. 19]: In your view, how can that be changed?

Respondent: To change we have to make them educated, and it has to start from birth place. Once women get married, they should prioritise the education first; once you get education you can achieve anything.

Interviewer [Q. 20]: Does society play a role in this matter?

Respondent: yes, society has a big role to play in this issue. Let's take an example, when a man comes home at 12 pm no one asks questions; but for a woman, it should not have to be 12 pm, at 10 pm, she should have to give clarification at home – in other hand society also will talk about that (shaking head side to side). When a man walks alone in street, nobody cares: when a woman walks alone, men of this society will be willing to go there. Laws are made but it is not implemented well. I heard lots of news, not only news against women, but of stealing and killing; but I never heard the news that how those people are punished. If media spreads the news about wrong doing and sentences given for that; then people will get positive message. In cases of women, if people can hear the news of doing something wrong and punishment that brings then women can feel safe and people will be aware.

Interviewer [Q. 21]: Many women might see you as role model, they might want to be like you and come to leadership role, at organisational prospective what barriers can you see?

Respondent: I have not worked in any organisations but in this organisation, there is no such a kind of organisational barriers for women. Only some kind of hidden attitude about women ability is somewhere there. Not in a big way but just like in the subconscious mind.

Interviewer [Q. 22]: how fair is the recruitment process?

Respondent: It is fair but women have to come forward. While recruiting, we do group discussion and have a performance test. When I was at group discussion to be an officer for exam section, there was discussion on the topic called 'reservation for women' that time I had speak against that. I said, it is not reservation that women need but family environment should be sorted first and give quality on education for women, then women will come forward automatically. A Woman might get job by reservation but she has to updated herself every day to be fit for the job – that is not possible if the home environment is not in favour. First, education should be provided and society has to change. To give reservation, we need educated women first.

Interviewer [Q. 23]: How is the culture in this organisation for women?

Respondent: I did not find any hard working in this culture although I have worked till very night. From this university, I have gone to India and worked alone as a superintendent but never had any difficulties. I have never felt inappropriate behaviour by any men in this institution as it might depend on you as well.

Interviewer [Q. 24]: How about maternity leave?

Respondent: When I came, I already had a baby so I don't know anything about this issue. I guess women can take 2 months of leave. If women live nearby and have a baby; they are allowed to go for break to feed a baby.

Interviewer [Q. 25]: What about government support to encourage women?

Respondent: We don't have direct support from government in this organisation. We have more male teacher and they have not done particularly anything to encourage women. It is easy to work with them there is no discrimination but we have given work equally as men. However, we are not participated in any meetings. Moreover, they do not have any thoughts on encouraging or giving reservation to women to go for higher position.

Interviewer [Q. 26]: How about payment?

Respondent: It is fixed. There is no difference in payment. There is some difference in lower labour worker. They have to work on daily wages and it is difference between men and women but I am not fully sure about that.

Interviewer [Q. 27]: What plan do you have for future?

Respondent: I have just given a manager post and transferred to another department. I want to learn and do something in there. I am fully confident about that.

Interviewer [Q. 28]: Learning means?

Respondent: I mean I want to learn new working style there and put my views to upper level to see whether I will be listened or not. Thus, I am quite happy to be transferred there, although, I have been working here for 20 years. I am ready to take challenge, let's see how it works.

Interviewer [Q. 29]: For your upcoming new responsibilities, I would like to say all the best. We are almost at the end of our interview. Would you like to ask anything?

Respondent: I have nothing to ask. It takes time to change the society. Things are changing a lot. People are having very few children and not bothering whether it is boy or girl. However, education is vital to women. If women get reservation on education then things will change rapidly.

Interviewer [Q. 30]: Thanks for giving your valuable time.

Respondent: Thank you for that.

(The End)